

CDO User Guide

Climate Data Operator
Version 2.0.0
October 2021

Uwe Schulzweida – *MPI for Meteorology*

Contents

1. Introduction	7
1.1. Building from sources	7
1.1.1. Compilation	8
1.1.2. Installation	8
1.2. Usage	8
1.2.1. Options	9
1.2.2. Environment variables	10
1.2.3. Operators	10
1.2.4. Parallelized operators	10
1.2.5. Operator parameter	10
1.2.6. Operator chaining	11
1.2.7. Chaining Benefits	11
1.3. Advanced Usage	12
1.3.1. Wildcards	12
1.3.2. Argument Groups	13
1.3.3. Apply Keyword	13
1.4. Memory Requirements	14
1.5. Horizontal grids	15
1.5.1. Grid area weights	15
1.5.2. Grid description	15
1.5.3. ICON - Grid File Server	19
1.6. Z-axis description	19
1.7. Time axis	20
1.7.1. Absolute time	20
1.7.2. Relative time	21
1.7.3. Conversion of the time	21
1.8. Parameter table	21
1.9. Missing values	21
1.9.1. Mean and average	22
1.10. Percentile	22
1.10.1. Percentile over timesteps	23
2. Reference manual	24
2.1. Information	25
2.1.1. INFO - Information and simple statistics	26
2.1.2. SINFO - Short information	27
2.1.3. DIFF - Compare two datasets field by field	28
2.1.4. NINFO - Print the number of parameters, levels or times	29
2.1.5. SHOWINFO - Show variables, levels or times	30
2.1.6. SHOWATTRIBUTE - Show attributes	31
2.1.7. FILEDES - Dataset description	32
2.2. File operations	33
2.2.1. APPLY - Apply operators	34
2.2.2. COPY - Copy datasets	35
2.2.3. TEE - Duplicate a data stream and write it to file	36
2.2.4. PACK - Pack data	36
2.2.5. REPLACE - Replace variables	37
2.2.6. DUPLICATE - Duplicates a dataset	37
2.2.7. MERGEGRID - Merge grid	37
2.2.8. MERGE - Merge datasets	38

2.2.9.	SPLIT - Split a dataset	39
2.2.10.	SPLITTIME - Split timesteps of a dataset	41
2.2.11.	SPLITSEL - Split selected timesteps	42
2.2.12.	DISTGRID - Distribute horizontal grid	43
2.2.13.	COLLGRID - Collect horizontal grid	44
2.3.	Selection	45
2.3.1.	SELECT - Select fields	46
2.3.2.	SELMULTI - Select multiple fields via GRIB1 parameters	48
2.3.3.	SELVAR - Select fields	49
2.3.4.	SELTIME - Select timesteps	51
2.3.5.	SELBOX - Select a box of a field	53
2.3.6.	SELCIRCLE - Select cells inside a circle	54
2.3.7.	SELGRIDCELL - Select grid cells	55
2.3.8.	SAMPLEGRID - Resample grid	55
2.3.9.	SELYEARIDX - Select year by index	55
2.3.10.	SELSURFACE - Extract surface	56
2.4.	Conditional selection	57
2.4.1.	COND - Conditional select one field	58
2.4.2.	COND2 - Conditional select two fields	58
2.4.3.	CONDC - Conditional select a constant	59
2.4.4.	MAPREDUCE - Reduce fields to user-defined mask	60
2.5.	Comparison	61
2.5.1.	COMP - Comparison of two fields	62
2.5.2.	COMPC - Comparison of a field with a constant	63
2.6.	Modification	64
2.6.1.	SETATTRIBUTE - Set attributes	66
2.6.2.	SETPARTAB - Set parameter table	68
2.6.3.	SET - Set field info	70
2.6.4.	SETTIME - Set time	71
2.6.5.	CHANGE - Change field header	73
2.6.6.	SETGRID - Set grid information	74
2.6.7.	SETZAXIS - Set z-axis information	75
2.6.8.	INVERT - Invert latitudes	76
2.6.9.	INVERTLEV - Invert levels	76
2.6.10.	SHIFTXY - Shift field	77
2.6.11.	MASKREGION - Mask regions	78
2.6.12.	MASKBOX - Mask a box	79
2.6.13.	SETBOX - Set a box to constant	80
2.6.14.	ENLARGE - Enlarge fields	81
2.6.15.	SETMISS - Set missing value	82
2.6.16.	SETGRIDCELL - Set the value of a grid cell	84
2.7.	Arithmetic	85
2.7.1.	EXPR - Evaluate expressions	87
2.7.2.	MATH - Mathematical functions	90
2.7.3.	ARITHC - Arithmetic with a constant	92
2.7.4.	ARITH - Arithmetic on two datasets	93
2.7.5.	MONARITH - Monthly arithmetic	94
2.7.6.	YEARARITH - Yearly arithmetic	95
2.7.7.	YHOURLARITH - Multi-year hourly arithmetic	96
2.7.8.	YDAYARITH - Multi-year daily arithmetic	97
2.7.9.	YMONARITH - Multi-year monthly arithmetic	98
2.7.10.	YSEASARITH - Multi-year seasonal arithmetic	99
2.7.11.	ARITHDAYS - Arithmetic with days	100
2.7.12.	ARITHLAT - Arithmetic with latitude	100
2.8.	Statistical values	101
2.8.1.	TIMCUMSUM - Cumulative sum over all timesteps	108
2.8.2.	CONSECSTAT - Consecutive timestep periods	108
2.8.3.	VARSSTAT - Statistical values over all variables	109

2.8.4.	ENSSTAT - Statistical values over an ensemble	110
2.8.5.	ENSSTAT2 - Statistical values over an ensemble	112
2.8.6.	ENSVAL - Ensemble validation tools	113
2.8.7.	FLDSTAT - Statistical values over a field	115
2.8.8.	ZONSTAT - Zonal statistical values	117
2.8.9.	MERSTAT - Meridional statistical values	119
2.8.10.	GRIDBOXSTAT - Statistical values over grid boxes	121
2.8.11.	VERTSTAT - Vertical statistical values	122
2.8.12.	TIMSELSTAT - Time range statistical values	123
2.8.13.	TIMSELPCTL - Time range percentile values	124
2.8.14.	RUNSTAT - Running statistical values	125
2.8.15.	RUNPCTL - Running percentile values	126
2.8.16.	TIMSTAT - Statistical values over all timesteps	127
2.8.17.	TIMPCTL - Percentile values over all timesteps	128
2.8.18.	HOURLSTAT - Hourly statistical values	129
2.8.19.	HOURLPCTL - Hourly percentile values	130
2.8.20.	DAYSTAT - Daily statistical values	131
2.8.21.	DAYPCTL - Daily percentile values	132
2.8.22.	MONSTAT - Monthly statistical values	133
2.8.23.	MONPCTL - Monthly percentile values	134
2.8.24.	YEARMONSTAT - Yearly mean from monthly data	135
2.8.25.	YEARSTAT - Yearly statistical values	136
2.8.26.	YEARPCTL - Yearly percentile values	137
2.8.27.	SEASSTAT - Seasonal statistical values	138
2.8.28.	SEASPCTL - Seasonal percentile values	139
2.8.29.	YHOURLSTAT - Multi-year hourly statistical values	140
2.8.30.	DHOURLSTAT - Multi-day hourly statistical values	142
2.8.31.	YDAYSTAT - Multi-year daily statistical values	144
2.8.32.	YDAYPCTL - Multi-year daily percentile values	146
2.8.33.	YMONSTAT - Multi-year monthly statistical values	147
2.8.34.	YMONPCTL - Multi-year monthly percentile values	149
2.8.35.	YSEASSTAT - Multi-year seasonal statistical values	150
2.8.36.	YSEASPCTL - Multi-year seasonal percentile values	152
2.8.37.	YDRUNSTAT - Multi-year daily running statistical values	153
2.8.38.	YDRUNPCTL - Multi-year daily running percentile values	155
2.9.	Correlation and co.	156
2.9.1.	FLDCOR - Correlation in grid space	157
2.9.2.	TIMCOR - Correlation over time	157
2.9.3.	FLDCOVAR - Covariance in grid space	158
2.9.4.	TIMCOVAR - Covariance over time	158
2.10.	Regression	159
2.10.1.	REGRES - Regression	160
2.10.2.	DETREND - Detrend time series	160
2.10.3.	TREND - Trend of time series	161
2.10.4.	TRENDARITH - Add or subtract a trend	162
2.11.	EOFs	163
2.11.1.	EOFS - Empirical Orthogonal Functions	164
2.11.2.	EOFCOEFF - Principal coefficients of EOFs	166
2.12.	Interpolation	167
2.12.1.	REMAPBIL - Bilinear interpolation	168
2.12.2.	REMAPBIC - Bicubic interpolation	169
2.12.3.	REMAPNN - Nearest neighbor remapping	170
2.12.4.	REMAPDIS - Distance weighted average remapping	171
2.12.5.	REMAPCON - First order conservative remapping	172
2.12.6.	REMAPCON2 - Second order conservative remapping	174
2.12.7.	REMAPLAF - Largest area fraction remapping	176
2.12.8.	REMAP - Grid remapping	177
2.12.9.	REMAPETA - Remap vertical hybrid level	178

2.12.10.VERTINTML - Vertical interpolation	180
2.12.11.VERTINTAP - Vertical pressure interpolation	181
2.12.12.VERTINTGH - Vertical height interpolation	182
2.12.13.INTLEVEL - Linear level interpolation	183
2.12.14.INTLEVEL3D - Linear level interpolation from/to 3D vertical coordinates	183
2.12.15.INTTIME - Time interpolation	184
2.12.16.INTYEAR - Year interpolation	185
2.13. Transformation	186
2.13.1. SPECTRAL - Spectral transformation	187
2.13.2. SPEC CONV - Spectral conversion	188
2.13.3. WIND2 - D and V to velocity potential and stream function	188
2.13.4. WIND - Wind transformation	189
2.13.5. FOURIER - Fourier transformation	190
2.14. Import/Export	191
2.14.1. IMPORTBINARY - Import binary data sets	192
2.14.2. IMPORTCMSAF - Import CM-SAF HDF5 files	193
2.14.3. IMPORTAMSR - Import AMSR binary files	194
2.14.4. INPUT - Formatted input	195
2.14.5. OUTPUT - Formatted output	196
2.14.6. OUTPUTTAB - Table output	197
2.14.7. OUTPUTGMT - GMT output	198
2.15. Miscellaneous	200
2.15.1. GRADSDES - GrADS data descriptor file	202
2.15.2. AFTERBURNER - ECHAM standard post processor	203
2.15.3. FILTER - Time series filtering	205
2.15.4. GRIDCELL - Grid cell quantities	206
2.15.5. SMOOTH - Smooth grid points	207
2.15.6. DELTAT - Difference between timesteps	207
2.15.7. REPLACEVALUES - Replace variable values	208
2.15.8. VARGEN - Generate a field	209
2.15.9. TIMSORT - Timsort	210
2.15.10.WINDTRANS - Wind Transformation	211
2.15.11.ROTUVB - Rotation	212
2.15.12.MROTUVB - Backward rotation of MPIOM data	212
2.15.13.MASTRFU - Mass stream function	213
2.15.14.DERIVEPAR - Derived model parameters	213
2.15.15.ADISIT - Potential temperature to in-situ temperature and vice versa	214
2.15.16.RHOPOT - Calculates potential density	214
2.15.17.HISTOGRAM - Histogram	215
2.15.18.SETHALO - Set the left and right bounds of a field	215
2.15.19.WCT - Windchill temperature	216
2.15.20.FDNS - Frost days where no snow index per time period	216
2.15.21.STRWIN - Strong wind days index per time period	216
2.15.22.STRBRE - Strong breeze days index per time period	217
2.15.23.STRGAL - Strong gale days index per time period	217
2.15.24.HURR - Hurricane days index per time period	217
2.15.25.CMORLITE - CMOR lite	218
2.15.26.VERIFYGRID - Verify grid coordinates	219
3. Contributors	220
3.1. History	220
3.2. External sources	220
3.3. Contributors	220
A. Environment Variables	224
B. Parallelized operators	225

C. Standard name table	226
D. Grid description examples	227
D.1. Example of a curvilinear grid description	227
D.2. Example description for an unstructured grid	228
Operator index	229

1. Introduction

The Climate Data Operator (**CDO**) software is a collection of many operators for standard processing of climate and forecast model data. The operators include simple statistical and arithmetic functions, data selection and subsampling tools, and spatial interpolation. **CDO** was developed to have the same set of processing functions for GRIB [[GRIB](#)] and NetCDF [[NetCDF](#)] datasets in one package.

The Climate Data Interface [[CDI](#)] is used for the fast and file format independent access to GRIB and NetCDF datasets. The local [MPI-MET](#) data formats SERVICE, EXTRA and IEG are also supported.

There are some limitations for GRIB and NetCDF datasets:

GRIB datasets have to be consistent, similar to NetCDF. That means all time steps need to have the same variables, and within a time step each variable may occur only once. Multiple fields in single GRIB2 messages are not supported!

NetCDF datasets are only supported for the classic data model and arrays up to 4 dimensions. These dimensions should only be used by the horizontal and vertical grid and the time. The NetCDF attributes should follow the [GDT](#), [COARDS](#) or [CF Conventions](#).

The main **CDO** features are:

- More than 700 operators available
- Modular design and easily extendable with new operators
- Very simple UNIX command line interface
- A dataset can be processed by several operators, without storing the interim results in files
- Most operators handle datasets with missing values
- Fast processing of large datasets
- Support of many different grid types
- Tested on many UNIX/Linux systems, Cygwin, and MacOS-X

1.1. Building from sources

This section describes how to build **CDO** from the sources on a UNIX system. **CDO** uses the GNU configure and build system for compilation. The only requirement is a working ISO C++14 and ANSI C99 compiler.

First go to the [download](#) page (<https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/cdo>) to get the latest distribution, if you do not have it yet.

To take full advantage of **CDO** features the following additional libraries should be installed:

- Unidata [NetCDF](#) library (<https://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf>) version 3 or higher. This library is needed to process NetCDF [[NetCDF](#)] files with **CDO**.
- ECMWF [ecCodes](#) library (<https://software.ecmwf.int/wiki/display/ECC/ecCodes+Home>) version 2.3.0 or higher. This library is needed to process GRIB2 files with **CDO**.
- HDF5 [szip](#) library (http://www.hdfgroup.org/doc_resource/SZIP) version 2.1 or higher. This library is needed to process szip compressed GRIB [[GRIB](#)] files with **CDO**.
- [HDF5](#) library (<http://www.hdfgroup.org/HDF5>) version 1.6 or higher. This library is needed to import CM-SAF [[CM-SAF](#)] HDF5 files with the **CDO** operator `import_cmsaf`.

- **PROJ** library (<http://trac.osgeo.org/proj>) version 5.0 or higher. This library is needed to convert Sinusoidal and Lambert Azimuthal Equal Area coordinates to geographic coordinates, for e.g. remapping.
- **Magics** library (<https://software.ecmwf.int/wiki/display/MAGP/Magics>) version 2.18 or higher. This library is needed to create contour, vector and graph plots with **CDO**.

CDO is a multi-threaded application. Therefore all the above libraries should be compiled thread safe. Using non-threadsafe libraries could cause unexpected errors!

1.1.1. Compilation

Compilation is done by performing the following steps:

1. Unpack the archive, if you haven't done that yet:

```
gunzip cdo-$VERSION.tar.gz      # uncompress the archive
tar xf cdo-$VERSION.tar         # unpack it
cd cdo-$VERSION
```

2. Run the configure script:

```
./configure
```

- Optionally with NetCDF [\[NetCDF\]](#) support:

```
./configure --with-netcdf=<NetCDF root directory>
```

- and with ecCodes:

```
./configure --with-ecCodes=<ecCodes root directory>
```

For an overview of other configuration options use

```
./configure --help
```

3. Compile the program by running make:

```
make
```

The program should compile without problems and the binary (`cdo`) should be available in the `src` directory of the distribution.

1.1.2. Installation

After the compilation of the source code do a `make install`, possibly as root if the destination permissions require that.

```
make install
```

The binary is installed into the directory `<prefix>/bin`. `<prefix>` defaults to `/usr/local` but can be changed with the `--prefix` option of the configure script.

Alternatively, you can also copy the binary from the `src` directory manually to some `bin` directory in your search path.

1.2. Usage

This section describes how to use **CDO**. The syntax is:

```
cdo [ Options ] Operator1 [ -Operator2 [ -OperatorN ] ]
```

1.2.1. Options

All options have to be placed before the first operator. The following options are available for all operators:

- a Generate an absolute time axis.
- b <nbits> Set the number of bits for the output precision. The valid precisions depend on the file format:

<format>	<nbits>
grb1, grb2	P1 - P24
nc1, nc2, nc4, nc4c, nc5	I8/I16/I32/F32/F64
nc4, nc4c, nc5	U8/U16/U32
grb2, srv, ext, ieg	F32/F64

For *srv*, *ext* and *ieg* format the letter L or B can be added to set the byteorder to Little or Big endian.

- cmor CMOR conform NetCDF output.
- C, --color Colorized output messages.
- double Using double precision floats for data in memory.
- eccodes Use ecCodes to decode/encode GRIB1 messages.
- f <format> Set the output file format. The valid file formats are:

File format	<format>
GRIB version 1	grb1/grb
GRIB version 2	grb2
NetCDF	nc1
NetCDF version 2 (64-bit offset)	nc2/nc
NetCDF-4 (HDF5)	nc4
NetCDF-4 classic	nc4c
NetCDF version 5 (64-bit data)	nc5
SERVICE	srv
EXTRA	ext
IEG	ieg

GRIB2 is only available if **CDO** was compiled with ecCodes support and all NetCDF file types are only available if **CDO** was compiled with NetCDF support!

- g <grid> Define the default grid description by name or from file (see chapter 1.3 on page 15). Available grid names are: r<NX>x<NY>, lon=<LON>/lat=<LAT>, F<XXX>, gme<NI>
- h, --help Help information for the operators.
- no_history Do not append to NetCDF *history* global attribute.
- netcdf_hdr_pad, --hdr_pad, --header_pad <nbr> Pad NetCDF output header with *nbr* bytes.
- k <chunktype> NetCDF4 chunk type: auto, grid or lines.
- L Lock I/O (sequential access).
- m <missval> Set the missing value of non NetCDF files (default: -9e+33).
- O Overwrite existing output file, if checked.
Existing output file is checked only for: ens<STAT>, merge, mergetime
- operators List of all operators.
- P <nthreads> Set number of OpenMP threads (Only available if OpenMP support was compiled in).
- pedantic Warnings count as errors.
- percentile <method> Percentile method: nrank nist rtype8 numpy numpy_lower numpy_higher numpy_nearest
- reduce_dim Reduce NetCDF dimensions.
- R, --regular Convert GRIB1 data from global reduced to regular Gaussian grid (only with cgribex lib).
- r Generate a relative time axis.
- S Create an extra output stream for the module TIMSTAT. This stream contains the number of non missing values for each output period.
- s, --silent Silent mode.
- single Using single precision floats for data in memory.

<code>--sortname</code>	Alphanumeric sorting of NetCDF parameter names.
<code>-t <partab></code>	Set the GRIB1 (cgribex) default parameter table name or file (see chapter 1.6 on page 21). Predefined tables are: echam4 echam5 echam6 mpiom1 ecmwf remo
<code>--timestat_date <srcdate></code>	Target timestamp (temporal statistics): first, middle, midhigh or last source timestep.
<code>-V, --version</code>	Print the version number.
<code>-v, --verbose</code>	Print extra details for some operators.
<code>-w</code>	Disable warning messages.
<code>--worker <num></code>	Number of worker to decode/decompress GRIB records.
<code>-z szip</code>	SZIP compression of GRIB1 records.
<code>jpeg</code>	JPEG compression of GRIB2 records.
<code>zip[_1-9]</code>	Deflate compression of NetCDF4 variables.

1.2.2. Environment variables

There are some environment variables which influence the behavior of **CDO**. An incomplete list can be found in [Appendix A](#).

Here is an example to set the environment variable `CDO_RESET_HISTORY` for different shells:

```
Bourne shell (sh):  CDO_RESET_HISTORY=1 ; export CDO_RESET_HISTORY
Korn shell (ksh):  export CDO_RESET_HISTORY=1
C shell (csh):     setenv CDO_RESET_HISTORY 1
```

1.2.3. Operators

There are more than 700 operators available. A detailed description of all operators can be found in the [Reference Manual](#) section.

1.2.4. Parallelized operators

Some of the **CDO** operators are shared memory parallelized with OpenMP. An OpenMP-enabled C compiler is needed to use this feature. Users may request a specific number of OpenMP threads `nthreads` with the `'-P'` switch.

Here is an example to distribute the bilinear interpolation on 8 OpenMP threads:

```
cdo -P 8 remapbil,targetgrid infile outfile
```

Many **CDO** operators are I/O-bound. This means most of the time is spent in reading and writing the data. Only compute intensive **CDO** operators are parallelized. An incomplete list of OpenMP parallelized operators can be found in [Appendix B](#).

1.2.5. Operator parameter

Some operators need one or more parameter. A list of parameter is indicated by the separator `','`:

- STRING

String parameters require quotes if the string contains blanks or other characters interpreted by the shell. The following command select variables with the name `pressure` and `tsurf`:

```
cdo selvar,pressure,tsurf infile outfile
```

- FLOAT

Floating point number in any representation. The following command sets the range between 0 and 273.15 of all fields to missing value:

```
cdo setrtomiss,0,273.15 infile outfile
```

- **BOOL**

Boolean parameter in the following representation TRUE/FALSE, T/F or 0/1. To disable the weighting by grid cell area in the calculation of a field mean, use:

```
cdo fldmean,weights=FALSE infile outfile
```

- **INTEGER**

A range of integer parameter can be specified by *first/last[/inc]*. To select the days 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9 use:

```
cdo selday,5/9 infile outfile
```

The result is the same as:

```
cdo selday,5,6,7,8,9 infile outfile
```

1.2.6. Operator chaining

Operator chaining allows to combine two or more operators on the command line into a single **CDO** call. This allows the creation of complex operations out of more simple ones: reductions over several dimensions, file merges and all kinds of analysis processes. All operators with a fixed number of input streams and one output stream can pass the result directly to an other operator. For differentiation between files and operators all operators must be written with a prepended "-" when chaining.

```
cdo -monmean -add -mulc,2.0 infile1 -daymean infile2 outfile          (CDO example call)
```

Here monmean will have the output of add while add takes the output of mulc,2.0 and daymean. infile1 and infile2 are inputs for their predecessor. When mixing operators with an arbitrary number of input streams extra care needs to be taken. The following examples illustrates why.

1. `cdo info -timavg infile1 infile2`
2. `cdo info -timavg infile?`
3. `cdo timavg infile1 tmpfile`
`cdo info tmpfile infile2`
`rm tmpfile`

All three examples produce identical results. The time average will be computed only on the first input file.

Note(1): In section 1.3.2 we introduce argument groups which will make this a lot easier and less error prone.

Note(2): Operator chaining is implemented over POSIX Threads (pthreads). Therefore this **CDO** feature is not available on operating systems without POSIX Threads support!

1.2.7. Chaining Benefits

Combining operators can have several benefits. The most obvious is a performance increase through reducing disk I/O:

```
cdo sub -dayavg infile2 -timavg infile1 outfile
```

instead of

```
cdo timavg infile1 tmp1
cdo dayavg infile2 tmp2
cdo sub tmp2 tmp1 outfile
rm tmp1 tmp2
```

Especially with large input files the reading and writing of intermediate files can have a big influence on the overall performance.

A second aspect is the execution of operators: Limited by the algorithms potentially all operators of a chain can run in parallel.

1.3. Advanced Usage

In this section we will introduce advanced features of **CDO**. These include operator grouping which allows to write more complex **CDO** calls and the `apply` keyword which allows to shorten calls that need an operator to be executed on multiple files as well as wildcards which allow to search paths for file signatures. These features have several restrictions and follow rules that depend on the input/output properties. These required properties of operators can be investigated with the following commands which will output a list of operators that have selected properties:

```
cdo --attribs [arbitrary/filesOnly/onlyFirst/noOutput/obase]
```

- *arbitrary* describes all operators where the number of inputs is not defined.
- *filesOnly* are operators that can have other operators as input.
- *onlyFirst* shows which operators can only be at the most left position of the polish notation argument chain.
- *noOutput* are all operators that do not print to any file (e.g info)
- *obase* Here *obase* describes an operator that does not use the output argument as file but e.g as a file name base (output base). This is almost exclusively used for operators the split input files.

```
cdo -splithour baseName_
could result in: baseName_1 baseName_2 ... baseName_N
```

For checking a single or multiple operator directly the following usage of `--attribs` can be used:

```
cdo --attribs operatorName
```

1.3.1. Wildcards

Wildcards are a standard feature of command line interpreters (shells) on many operating systems. They are placeholder characters used in file paths that are expanded by the interpreter into file lists. For further information the [Advance Bash Scripting Guide](#) is a valuable source of information. Handling of input is a central issue for **CDO** and in some circumstances it is not enough to use the wildcards from the shell. That's why **CDO** can handle them on its own.

all files	2020-2-01.txt 2020-2-11.txt 2020-2-15.txt 2020-3-01.txt 2020-3-02.txt 2020-3-12.txt 2020-3-13.txt 2020-3-15.txt 2021.grb 2022.grb
wildcard	filelist results
2020-3* and 2020-3-?.txt	2020-3-01.txt 2020-3-02.txt 2020-3-12.txt 2020-3-13.txt 2020-3-15.txt
2020-3-?1.txt	2020-3-01.txt
*.grb	2021.grb 2020.grb

Use single quotes if the input stream names matched to a single wildcard expression. In this case **CDO** will do the pattern matching and the output can be combined with other operators. Here is an example for this feature:

```
cdo timavg -select,name=temperature 'infile?' outfile
```

In earlier versions of **CDO** this was necessary to have the right files parsed to the right operator. Newer version support this with the argument grouping feature (see [1.3.2](#)). We advice the use of the grouping mechanism instead of the single quoted wildcards since this feature could be deprecated in future versions.

Note: Wildcard expansion is not available on operating systems without the `glob()` function!

1.3.2. Argument Groups

In section 1.2.6 we described that it is not possible to chain operators with an arbitrary number of inputs. In this section we want to show how this can be achieved through the use of *operator grouping* with angled brackets []. Using these brackets **CDO** can assigned the inputs to their corresponding operators during the execution of the command line. The ability to write operator combination in a parenthesis-free way is partly given up in favor of allowing operators with arbitrary number of inputs. This allows a much more compact way to handle large number of input files.

The following example shows an example which we will transform from a non-working solution to a working one.

```
cdo -infon -div -fldmean -cat infile1 -mulc,2.0 infile2 -fldmax infile3
```

This example will throw the following error:

```
cdo (Warning): Did you forget to use '[' and/or ']' for multiple variable input operators?
cdo (Warning): use option --variableInput, for description
```

```
cdo (Abort): Too few streams specified! Operator div needs 2 input streams and 1 output stream!
```

The error is raised by the operator *div*. This operator needs two input streams and one output stream, but the *cat* operator has claimed all possible streams on its right hand side as input because it accepts an arbitrary number of inputs. Hence it didn't leave anything for the remaining input or output streams of *div*. For this we can declare a group which will be passed to the operator left of the group.

```
cdo -infon -div -fldmean -cat [ infile1 -mulc,2.0 infile2 ] -fldmax infile3
```

For full flexibility it is possible to have groups inside groups:

```
cdo -infon -div -fldmean -cat [ fileA1 infileC2 -merge [ infileB1 infileB2 ] ] -fldmax infileD
```

1.3.3. Apply Keyword

When working with medium or large number of similar files there is a common problem of a processing step (often a reduction) which needs to be performed on all of them before a more specific analysis can be applied. Usualy this can be done in two ways: One option is to use *merge* to glue everything together and chain the reduction step after it. The second option is to write a *for-loop* over all inputs which perform the basic processing on each of the files separately and call *merge* one the results. Unfortunately both options have side-effects: The first one needs a lot of memory because all files are read in completely and reduced afterwards while the latter one creates a lot of temporary files. Both memory and disk IO can be bottlenecks and should be avoided.

The *apply* keyword was introduced for that purpose. It can be used as an operator, but it needs at least one operator as a parameter, which is applied in parallel to all related input streams in a parallel way before all streams are passed to operator next in the chain.

The following is an example with three input files:

```
cdo -merge -apply,-daymean [ file1 file2 file3 ] outfile
```

would result in:

```
cdo -merge -daymean file1 -daymean file2 -daymean file3 outfile
```

Figure 1.1.: Usage and result of apply keyword

Apply is especially useful when combined with wildcards. The previous example can be shortened further.

```
cdo -merge -apply,-daymean [ file? ] outfile
```

As shown this feature allows to simplify commands with medium amount of files and to move reductions further back. This can also have a positive impact on the performance.

An example where performance can take a hit.

```
cdo -yearmean -daymean -merge [ f1 ... f40 ]
```

An improved but ugly to write example.

```
cdo -yearmean -merge [ -daymean f1 -daymean f2 ... -daymean f40 ]
```

Apply saves the day. And creates the call above with much less typing.

```
cdo -yearmean -merge [ -apply,-daymean [ f1 ... f40 ] ]
```

Figure 1.2.: Apply keyword simplifies command and execution

In the example in figure 1.2 the resulting call will dramatically save process interaction as well as execution times since the reduction (daymean) is applied on the files first. That means that the merge operator will receive the reduced files and the operations for merging the whole data is saved. For other **CDO** calls further improvements can be made by adding more arguments to apply (1.3)

A less performant example.

```
cdo -aReduction -anotherReduction -daymean -merge [ f1 ... f40 ]
```

```
cdo -merge -apply,"-aReduction -anotherReduction -daymean" [ f1 ... f40 ]
```

Figure 1.3.: Multi argument apply

Restrictions: While the apply keyword can be extremely helpful it has several restrictions (for now!).

- Apply inputs can only be files, wildcards and operators that have 0 inputs and 1 output.
- Apply can not be used as the first **CDO** operator.
- Apply arguments can only be operators with 1 input and 1 output.
- Grouping inside the Apply argument or input is not allowed.

1.4. Memory Requirements

This section roughly describes the memory requirements of **CDO**. **CDO** tries to use as little memory as possible. The smallest unit that is read by all operators is a horizontal field. The required memory depends mainly on the used operators, the data format, the data type and the size of the fields.

The operators have partly very different memory requirements. Many **CDO** modules like **FLDSTAT** process one horizontal field at a time. Memory-intensive modules such as **ENSSTAT** and **TIMSTAT** require all fields of a time step to be held in memory. Of course, the memory requirements of each operator add up when they are combined. Some operators are parallelized with OpenMP. In multi-threaded mode (see

option *-P*) the memory requirement can increase for these operators. This increase grows with the number of threads used.

The data type determines the number of bytes per value. Single precision floating point data (float) occupies 4 bytes per value. All other data types are read as double precision floats and thus occupy 8 bytes per value. With the **CDO** option *--single* all data is read as single precision floats. This can reduce the memory requirement by a factor of 2.

1.5. Horizontal grids

Physical quantities of climate models are typically stored on a horizontal grid. **CDO** supports structured grids like regular lon/lat or curvilinear grids and also unstructured grids.

1.5.1. Grid area weights

One single point of a horizontal grid represents the mean of a grid cell. These grid cells are typically of different sizes, because the grid points are of varying distance.

Area weights are individual weights for each grid cell. They are needed to compute the area weighted mean or variance of a set of grid cells (e.g. `fldmean` - the mean value of all grid cells). In **CDO** the area weights are derived from the grid cell area. If the cell area is not available then it will be computed from the geographical coordinates via spherical triangles. This is only possible if the geographical coordinates of the grid cell corners are available or derivable. Otherwise **CDO** gives a warning message and uses constant area weights for all grid cells.

The cell area is read automatically from a NetCDF input file if a variable has the corresponding “cell_measures” attribute, e.g.:

```
var:cell_measures = "area: cell_area" ;
```

If the computed cell area is not desired then the **CDO** operator `setgridarea` can be used to set or overwrite the grid cell area.

1.5.2. Grid description

In the following situations it is necessary to give a description of a horizontal grid:

- Changing the grid description (operator: `setgrid`)
- Horizontal interpolation (all remapping operators)
- Generating of variables (operator: `const`, `random`)

As now described, there are several possibilities to define a horizontal grid.

1.5.2.1. Predefined grids

Predefined grids are available for global regular, gaussian or icosahedral-hexagonal GME grids.

Global regular grid: `global_<DXY>`

`global_<DXY>` defines a global regular lon/lat grid. The grid increment `<DXY>` can be selected at will. The longitudes start at `<DXY>/2 - 180°` and the latitudes start at `<DXY>/2 - 90°`.

Zonal latitudes: zonal_<DY>

zonal_<DY> defines a grid with zonal latitudes only. The latitude increment <DY> can be selected at will. The latitudes start at <DY>/2 - 90°. The boundaries of each latitude are also generated. The number of longitudes is 1.

Global regular grid: r<NX>x<NY>

r<NX>x<NY> defines a global regular lon/lat grid. The number of the longitudes <NX> and the latitudes <NY> can be selected at will. The longitudes start at 0° with an increment of (360/<NX>)°. The latitudes go from south to north with an increment of (180/<NY>)°.

One grid point: lon=<LON>/lat=<LAT>

lon=<LON>/lat=<LAT> defines a lon/lat grid with only one grid point.

Full regular Gaussian grid: F<XXX>

F<XXX> defines a global regular Gaussian grid. XXX specifies the number of latitudes lines between the Pole and the Equator. The longitudes start at 0° with an increment of (360/nlon)°. The gaussian latitudes go from north to south.

Global icosahedral-hexagonal GME grid: gme<NI>

gme<NI> defines a global icosahedral-hexagonal GME grid. NI specifies the number of intervals on a main triangle side.

1.5.2.2. Grids from data files

You can use the grid description from an other datafile. The format of the datafile and the grid of the data field must be supported by **CDO**. Use the operator 'sinfo' to get short informations about your variables and the grids. If there are more then one grid in the datafile the grid description of the first variable will be used. Add the extension :N to the name of the datafile to select grid number N.

1.5.2.3. SCRIP grids

SCRIP (Spherical Coordinate Remapping and Interpolation Package) uses a common grid description for curvilinear and unstructured grids. For more information about the convention see [SCRIP]. This grid description is stored in NetCDF. Therefor it is only available if **CDO** was compiled with NetCDF support!

SCRIP grid description example of a curvilinear MPIOM [MPIOM] GROB3 grid (only the NetCDF header):

```
netcdf grob3s {
  dimensions:
    grid_size = 12120 ;
    grid_corners = 4 ;
    grid_rank = 2 ;
  variables:
    int grid_dims(grid_rank) ;
    double grid_center_lat(grid_size) ;
      grid_center_lat:units = "degrees" ;
      grid_center_lat:bounds = "grid_corner_lat" ;
    double grid_center_lon(grid_size) ;
      grid_center_lon:units = "degrees" ;
      grid_center_lon:bounds = "grid_corner_lon" ;
    int grid_imask(grid_size) ;
      grid_imask:units = "unitless" ;
```

```

        grid_imask:coordinates = "grid_center_lon grid_center_lat" ;
double  grid_corner_lat(grid_size, grid_corners) ;
        grid_corner_lat:units = "degrees" ;
double  grid_corner_lon(grid_size, grid_corners) ;
        grid_corner_lon:units = "degrees" ;

// global attributes:
        :title = "grob3s" ;
}

```

1.5.2.4. CDO grids

All supported grids can also be described with the **CDO** grid description. The following keywords can be used to describe a grid:

Keyword	Datatype	Description
gridtype	STRING	Type of the grid (gaussian, lonlat, curvilinear, unstructured).
gridsize	INTEGER	Size of the grid.
xsize	INTEGER	Size in x direction (number of longitudes).
ysize	INTEGER	Size in y direction (number of latitudes).
xvals	FLOAT ARRAY	X values of the grid cell center.
yvals	FLOAT ARRAY	Y values of the grid cell center.
nvertex	INTEGER	Number of the vertices for all grid cells.
xbounds	FLOAT ARRAY	X bounds of each gridbox.
ybounds	FLOAT ARRAY	Y bounds of each gridbox.
xfirst, xinc	FLOAT, FLOAT	Macros to define xvals with a constant increment, xfirst is the x value of the first grid cell center.
yfirst, yinc	FLOAT, FLOAT	Macros to define yvals with a constant increment, yfirst is the y value of the first grid cell center.
xunits	STRING	units of the x axis
yunits	STRING	units of the y axis

Which keywords are necessary depends on the gridtype. The following table gives an overview of the default values or the size with respect to the different grid types.

gridtype	lonlat	gaussian	projection	curvilinear	unstructured
gridsize	xsize*ysize	xsize*ysize	xsize*ysize	xsize*ysize	ncell
xsize	nlon	nlon	nx	nlon	gridsize
ysize	nlat	nlat	ny	nlat	gridsize
xvals	xsize	xsize	xsize	gridsize	gridsize
yvals	ysize	ysize	ysize	gridsize	gridsize
nvertex	2	2	2	4	nv
xbounds	2*xsize	2*xsize	2*xsize	4*gridsize	nv*gridsize
ybounds	2*ysize	2*ysize	2*xsize	4*gridsize	nv*gridsize
xunits	degrees	degrees	m	degrees	degrees
yunits	degrees	degrees	m	degrees	degrees

The keywords nvertex, xbounds and ybounds are optional if area weights are not needed. The grid cell corners xbounds and ybounds have to rotate counterclockwise.

CDO grid description example of a T21 gaussian grid:

```

gridtype = gaussian
xsize    = 64
ysize    = 32
xfirst   = 0

```

```

xinc      = 5.625
yvals     = 85.76  80.27  74.75  69.21  63.68  58.14  52.61  47.07
           41.53  36.00  30.46  24.92  19.38  13.84   8.31   2.77
           -2.77  -8.31 -13.84 -19.38 -24.92 -30.46 -36.00 -41.53
           -47.07 -52.61 -58.14 -63.68 -69.21 -74.75 -80.27 -85.76

```

CDO grid description example of a global regular grid with 60x30 points:

```

gridtype = lonlat
xsize    = 60
ysize    = 30
xfirst   = -177
xinc     = 6
yfirst   = -87
yinc     = 6

```

The description for a projection is somewhat more complicated. Use the first section to describe the coordinates of the projection with the above keywords. Add the keyword **grid_mapping_name** to describe the mapping between the given coordinates and the true latitude and longitude coordinates. **grid_mapping_name** takes a string value that contains the name of the projection. A list of attributes can be added to define the mapping. The name of the attributes depend on the projection. The valid names of the projection and their attributes follow the NetCDF CF-Convention.

CDO supports the special grid mapping attribute **proj_params**. These parameters will be passed directly to the PROJ library to generate the geographic coordinates if needed.

The geographic coordinates of the following projections can be generated without the attribute **proj_params**, if all other attributes are available:

- **rotated_latitude_longitude**
- **lambert_conformal_conic**
- **lambert_azimuthal_equal_area**
- **sinusoidal**
- **polar_stereographic**

It is recommended to set the attribute **proj_params** also for the above projections to make sure all PROJ parameters are set correctly.

Here is an example of a **CDO** grid description using the attribute **proj_params** to define the PROJ parameter of a polar stereographic projection:

```

gridtype = projection
xsize    = 11
ysize    = 11
xunits   = "meter"
yunits   = "meter"
xfirst   = -638000
xinc     = 150
yfirst   = -3349350
yinc     = 150
grid_mapping = crs
grid_mapping_name = polar_stereographic
proj_params = "+proj=stere +lon_0=-45 +lat_ts=70 +lat_0=90 +x_0=0 +y_0=0"

```

The result is the same as using the CF conform Grid Mapping Attributes:

```

gridtype = projection
xsize    = 11
ysize    = 11
xunits   = "meter"
yunits   = "meter"
xfirst   = -638000
xinc     = 150

```

```

yfirst    = -3349350
yinc      = 150
grid_mapping = crs
grid_mapping_name = polar_stereographic
straight_vertical_longitude_from_pole = -45.
standard_parallel = 70.
latitude_of_projection_origin = 90.
false_easting = 0.
false_northing = 0.

```

CDO grid description example of a regional rotated lon/lat grid:

```

gridtype = projection
xsize    = 81
ysize    = 91
xunits   = "degrees"
yunits   = "degrees"
xfirst   = -19.5
xinc     = 0.5
yfirst   = -25.0
yinc     = 0.5
grid_mapping_name = rotated_latitude_longitude
grid_north_pole_longitude = -170
grid_north_pole_latitude = 32.5

```

Example **CDO** descriptions of a curvilinear and an unstructured grid can be found in [Appendix D](#).

1.5.3. ICON - Grid File Server

The geographic coordinates of the ICON model are located on an unstructured grid. This grid is stored in a separate grid file independent of the model data. The grid files are made available to the general public via a file server. Furthermore, these grid files are located at DKRZ under /pool/data/ICON/grids.

With the **CDO** function `setgrid,<gridfile>` this grid information can be added to the data if needed. Here is an example:

```
cdo sellonlatbox,-20,60,10,70 -setgrid,<path_to_gridfile> icodatafile result
```

ICON model data in NetCDF format contains the global attribute `grid_file_uri`. This attribute contains a link to the appropriate grid file on the ICON grid file server. If the global attribute `grid_file_uri` is present and valid, the grid information is added automatically. The `setgrid` function is then no longer necessary. **CDO** evaluates this attribute and downloads the grid file on demand if it is not already present. The grid file is stored in the current directory. The environment variable `CDO_DOWNLOAD_PATH` can be used to select a different directory for storing the grid file.

If the grid files are available locally, like at DKRZ, they do not need to be fetched from the grid file server. Use the environment variable `CDO_ICON_GRIDS` to set the root directory of the ICON grids. Here is an example for the ICON grids at DKRZ:

```
CDO_ICON_GRIDS=/pool/data/ICON
```

1.6. Z-axis description

Sometimes it is necessary to change the description of a z-axis. This can be done with the operator `setzaxis`. This operator needs an ASCII formatted file with the description of the z-axis. The following keywords can be used to describe a z-axis:

Keyword	Datatype	Description
zaxistype	STRING	type of the z-axis
size	INTEGER	number of levels
levels	FLOAT ARRAY	values of the levels
lbounds	FLOAT ARRAY	lower level bounds
ubounds	FLOAT ARRAY	upper level bounds
vctsize	INTEGER	number of vertical coordinate parameters
vct	FLOAT ARRAY	vertical coordinate table

The keywords **lbounds** and **ubounds** are optional. **vctsize** and **vct** are only necessary to define hybrid model levels.

Available z-axis types:

Z-axis type	Description	Units
surface	Surface	
pressure	Pressure level	pascal
hybrid	Hybrid model level	
height	Height above ground	meter
depth_below_sea	Depth below sea level	meter
depth_below_land	Depth below land surface	centimeter
isentropic	Isentropic (theta) level	kelvin

Z-axis description example for pressure levels 100, 200, 500, 850 and 1000 hPa:

```
zaxistype = pressure
size      = 5
levels    = 10000 20000 50000 85000 100000
```

Z-axis description example for ECHAM5 L19 hybrid model levels:

```
zaxistype = hybrid
size      = 19
levels    = 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19
vctsize   = 40
vct       = 0 2000 4000 6046.10938 8267.92578 10609.5117 12851.1016 14698.5
           15861.125 16116.2383 15356.9258 13621.4609 11101.5625 8127.14453
           5125.14062 2549.96875 783.195068 0 0 0
           0 0 0 0.000338993268 0.00335718691 0.0130700432 0.0340771675
           0.0706498027 0.12591666 0.201195419 0.295519829 0.405408859
           0.524931908 0.646107674 0.759697914 0.856437683 0.928747177
           0.972985268 0.992281914 1
```

Note that the **vctsize** is twice the number of levels plus two and the vertical coordinate table must be specified for the level interfaces.

1.7. Time axis

A time axis describes the time for every timestep. Two time axis types are available: absolute time and relative time axis. **CDO** tries to maintain the actual type of the time axis for all operators.

1.7.1. Absolute time

An absolute time axis has the current time to each time step. It can be used without knowledge of the calendar. This is preferably used by climate models. In NetCDF files the absolute time axis is represented by the unit of the time: "day as %Y%m%d.%f".

1.7.2. Relative time

A relative time is the time relative to a fixed reference time. The current time results from the reference time and the elapsed interval. The result depends on the calendar used. **CDO** supports the standard Gregorian, proleptic Gregorian, 360 days, 365 days and 366 days calendars. The relative time axis is preferably used by numerical weather prediction models. In NetCDF files the relative time axis is represented by the unit of the time: "*time-units since reference-time*", e.g "days since 1989-6-15 12:00".

1.7.3. Conversion of the time

Some programs which work with NetCDF data can only process relative time axes. Therefore it may be necessary to convert from an absolute into a relative time axis. This conversion can be done for each operator with the **CDO** option '-r'. To convert a relative into an absolute time axis use the **CDO** option '-a'.

1.8. Parameter table

A parameter table is an ASCII formatted file to convert code numbers to variable names. Each variable has one line with its code number, name and a description with optional units in a blank separated list. It can only be used for GRIB, SERVICE, EXTRA and IEG formatted files. The **CDO** option '-t <partab>' sets the default parameter table for all input files. Use the operator 'setpartab' to set the parameter table for a specific file.

Example of a **CDO** parameter table:

134	aps	surface pressure [Pa]
141	sn	snow depth [m]
147	ahfl	latent heat flux [W/m**2]
172	slm	land sea mask
175	albedo	surface albedo
211	siced	ice depth [m]

1.9. Missing values

Missing values are data points that are missing or invalid. Such data points are treated in a different way than valid data. Most **CDO** operators can handle missing values in a smart way. But if the missing value is within the range of valid data, it can lead to incorrect results. This applies to all arithmetic operations, but especially to logical operations when the missing value is 0 or 1.

The default missing value for GRIB, SERVICE, EXTRA and IEG files is $-9.e^{33}$. The **CDO** option '-m <missval>' overwrites the default missing value. In NetCDF files the variable attribute '_FillValue' is used as a missing value. The operator 'setmissval' can be used to set a new missing value.

The **CDO** use of the missing value is shown in the following tables, where one table is printed for each operation. The operations are applied to arbitrary numbers a , b , the special case 0, and the missing value *miss*. For example the table named "addition" shows that the sum of an arbitrary number a and the missing value is the missing value, and the table named "multiplication" shows that 0 multiplied by missing value results in 0.

addition	b		miss
a	$a + b$		<i>miss</i>
miss	<i>miss</i>		<i>miss</i>
subtraction	b		miss
a	$a - b$		<i>miss</i>
miss	<i>miss</i>		<i>miss</i>
multiplication	b	0	miss
a	$a * b$	0	<i>miss</i>
0	0	0	0
miss	<i>miss</i>	0	<i>miss</i>
division	b	0	miss
a	a/b	<i>miss</i>	<i>miss</i>
0	0	<i>miss</i>	<i>miss</i>
miss	<i>miss</i>	<i>miss</i>	<i>miss</i>
maximum	b		miss
a	$\max(a, b)$		<i>a</i>
miss	<i>b</i>		<i>miss</i>
minimum	b		miss
a	$\min(a, b)$		<i>a</i>
miss	<i>b</i>		<i>miss</i>
sum	b		miss
a	$a + b$		<i>a</i>
miss	<i>b</i>		<i>miss</i>

The handling of missing values by the operations "minimum" and "maximum" may be surprising, but the definition given here is more consistent with that expected in practice. Mathematical functions (e.g. *log*, *sqrt*, etc.) return the missing value if an argument is the missing value or an argument is out of range.

All statistical functions ignore missing values, treating them as not belonging to the sample, with the side-effect of a reduced sample size.

1.9.1. Mean and average

An artificial distinction is made between the notions mean and average. The mean is regarded as a statistical function, whereas the average is found simply by adding the sample members and dividing the result by the sample size. For example, the mean of 1, 2, *miss* and 3 is $(1 + 2 + 3)/3 = 2$, whereas the average is $(1 + 2 + \text{miss} + 3)/4 = \text{miss}/4 = \text{miss}$. If there are no missing values in the sample, the average and mean are identical.

1.10. Percentile

There is no standard definition of percentile. All definitions yield to similar results when the number of values is very large. The following percentile methods are available in **CDO**:

Percentile method	Description
nrank	Nearest Rank method, the default method used in CDO
nist	The primary method recommended by NIST
rtype8	R's type=8 method
numpy	numpy.percentile with the option interpolation set to 'linear'
numpy_lower	numpy.percentile with the option interpolation set to 'lower'
numpy_higher	numpy.percentile with the option interpolation set to 'higher'
numpy_nearest	numpy.percentile with the option interpolation set to 'nearest'

The percentile method can be selected with the **CDO** option `--percentile`. The Nearest Rank method is the default percentile method in **CDO**.

The different percentile methods can lead to different results, especially for small number of data values. Consider the ordered list {15, 20, 35, 40, 50, 55}, which contains six data values. Here is the result for the 30th, 40th, 50th, 75th and 100th percentiles of this list using the different percentile methods:

Percentile P	nrank	nist	rtype8	numpy	numpy lower	numpy higher	numpy nearest
30th	20	21.5	23.5	27.5	20	35	35
40th	35	32	33	35	35	35	35
50th	35	37.5	37.5	37.5	35	40	40
75th	50	51.25	50.42	47.5	40	50	50
100th	55	55	55	55	55	55	55

1.10.1. Percentile over timesteps

The amount of data for time series can be very large. All data values need to be held in memory to calculate the percentile. The percentile over timesteps uses a histogram algorithm, to limit the amount of required memory. The default number of histogram bins is 101. That means the histogram algorithm is used, when the dataset has more than 101 time steps. The default can be overridden by setting the environment variable `CDO_PCTL_NBINS` to a different value. The histogram algorithm is implemented only for the Nearest Rank method.

2. Reference manual

This section gives a description of all operators. Related operators are grouped to modules. For easier description all single input files are named `infile` or `infile1`, `infile2`, etc., and an arbitrary number of input files are named `infile`s. All output files are named `outfile` or `outfile1`, `outfile2`, etc. Further the following notion is introduced:

$i(t)$ Timestep t of `infile`

$i(t, x)$ Element number x of the field at timestep t of `infile`

$o(t)$ Timestep t of `outfile`

$o(t, x)$ Element number x of the field at timestep t of `outfile`

2.1. Information

This section contains modules to print information about datasets. All operators print their results to standard output.

Here is a short overview of all operators in this section:

info	Dataset information listed by parameter identifier
infn	Dataset information listed by parameter name
map	Dataset information and simple map
sinfo	Short information listed by parameter identifier
sinfn	Short information listed by parameter name
diff	Compare two datasets listed by parameter id
diffn	Compare two datasets listed by parameter name
npar	Number of parameters
nlevel	Number of levels
nyear	Number of years
nmon	Number of months
ndate	Number of dates
ntime	Number of timesteps
ngridpoints	Number of gridpoints
ngrids	Number of horizontal grids
showformat	Show file format
showcode	Show code numbers
showname	Show variable names
showstdname	Show standard names
showlevel	Show levels
showltype	Show GRIB level types
showyear	Show years
showmon	Show months
showdate	Show date information
showtime	Show time information
showtimestamp	Show timestamp
showattribute	Show a global attribute or a variable attribute
partab	Parameter table
codetab	Parameter code table
griddes	Grid description
zaxisdes	Z-axis description
vct	Vertical coordinate table

2.1.1. INFO - Information and simple statistics

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile
```

Description

This module writes information about the structure and contents for each field of all input files to standard output. A field is a horizontal layer of a data variable. All input files need to have the same structure with the same variables on different timesteps. The information displayed depends on the chosen operator.

Operators

- info** Dataset information listed by parameter identifier
Prints information and simple statistics for each field of all input datasets. For each field the operator prints one line with the following elements:
- Date and Time
 - Level, Gridsize and number of Missing values
 - Minimum, Mean and Maximum
The mean value is computed without the use of area weights!
 - Parameter identifier
- infon** Dataset information listed by parameter name
The same as operator [info](#) but using the name instead of the identifier to label the parameter.
- map** Dataset information and simple map
Prints information, simple statistics and a map for each field of all input datasets. The map will be printed only for fields on a regular lon/lat grid.

Example

To print information and simple statistics for each field of a dataset use:

```
cdo infon infile
```

This is an example result of a dataset with one 2D parameter over 12 timesteps:

-1 :	Date	Time	Level	Size	Miss	Minimum	Mean	Maximum	Name
1 :	1987-01-31	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	232.77	266.65	305.31	SST
2 :	1987-02-28	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	233.64	267.11	307.15	SST
3 :	1987-03-31	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	225.31	267.52	307.67	SST
4 :	1987-04-30	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	215.68	268.65	310.47	SST
5 :	1987-05-31	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	215.78	271.53	312.49	SST
6 :	1987-06-30	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	212.89	272.80	314.18	SST
7 :	1987-07-31	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	209.52	274.29	316.34	SST
8 :	1987-08-31	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	210.48	274.41	315.83	SST
9 :	1987-09-30	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	210.48	272.37	312.86	SST
10 :	1987-10-31	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	219.46	270.53	309.51	SST
11 :	1987-11-30	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	230.98	269.85	308.61	SST
12 :	1987-12-31	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	241.25	269.94	309.27	SST

2.1.2. SINFO - Short information

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile
```

Description

This module writes information about the structure of `infile`s to standard output. `infile`s is an arbitrary number of input files. All input files need to have the same structure with the same variables on different timesteps. The information displayed depends on the chosen operator.

Operators

sinfo Short information listed by parameter identifier
Prints short information of a dataset. The information is divided into 4 sections. Section 1 prints one line per parameter with the following information:

- institute and source
- time c=constant v=varying
- type of statistical processing
- number of levels and z-axis number
- horizontal grid size and number
- data type
- parameter identifier

Section 2 and 3 gives a short overview of all grid and vertical coordinates. And the last section contains short information of the time coordinate.

sinfon Short information listed by parameter name
The same as operator [sinfo](#) but using the name instead of the identifier to label the parameter.

Example

To print short information of a dataset use:

```
cdo sinfon infile
```

This is the result of an ECHAM5 dataset with 3 parameter over 12 timesteps:

```

-1 : Institut Source T Steptype Levels Num Points Num Dtype : Name
 1 : MPIMET ECHAM5 c instant 1 1 2048 1 F32 : GEOSP
 2 : MPIMET ECHAM5 v instant 4 2 2048 1 F32 : T
 3 : MPIMET ECHAM5 v instant 1 1 2048 1 F32 : TSURF
Grid coordinates :
 1 : gaussian : points=2048 (64x32) F16
           longitude : 0 to 354.375 by 5.625 degrees_east circular
           latitude : 85.7606 to -85.7606 degrees_north
Vertical coordinates :
 1 : surface : levels=1
 2 : pressure : levels=4
           level : 92500 to 20000 Pa
Time coordinate :
           time : 12 steps
YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss YYYY-MM-DD hh:mm:ss
1987-01-31 12:00:00 1987-02-28 12:00:00 1987-03-31 12:00:00 1987-04-30 12:00:00
1987-05-31 12:00:00 1987-06-30 12:00:00 1987-07-31 12:00:00 1987-08-31 12:00:00
1987-09-30 12:00:00 1987-10-31 12:00:00 1987-11-30 12:00:00 1987-12-31 12:00:00

```

2.1.3. DIFF - Compare two datasets field by field

Synopsis

```
<operator>[,options] infile1 infile2
```

Description

Compares the contents of two datasets field by field. The input datasets need to have the same structure and its fields need to have the same header information and dimensions. Try the option *names* if the number of variables differ. Exit status is 0 if inputs are the same and 1 if they differ.

Operators

diff Compare two datasets listed by parameter id
Provides statistics on differences between two datasets. For each pair of fields the operator prints one line with the following information:

- Date and Time
- Level, Gridsize and number of Missing values
- Number of different values
- Occurrence of coefficient pairs with different signs (S)
- Occurrence of zero values (Z)
- Maxima of absolute difference of coefficient pairs
- Maxima of relative difference of non-zero coefficient pairs with equal signs
- Parameter identifier

$$Absdiff(t, x) = |i_1(t, x) - i_2(t, x)|$$

$$Reldiff(t, x) = \frac{|i_1(t, x) - i_2(t, x)|}{\max(|i_1(t, x)|, |i_2(t, x)|)}$$

diffn Compare two datasets listed by parameter name
The same as operator **diff**. Using the name instead of the identifier to label the parameter.

Parameter

<i>maxcount</i>	INTEGER	Stop after maxcount different fields
<i>abslim</i>	FLOAT	Limit of the maximum absolute difference (default: 0)
<i>rellim</i>	FLOAT	Limit of the maximum relative difference (default: 1)
<i>names</i>	STRING	Consideration of the variable names of only one input file (left/right) or the intersection of both (intersect).

Example

To print the difference for each field of two datasets use:

```
cdo diffn infile1 infile2
```

This is an example result of two datasets with one 2D parameter over 12 timesteps:

	Date	Time	Level	Size	Miss	Diff	S	Z	Max_Absdiff	Max_Reldiff	Name
1	: 1987-01-31	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	273	F	F	0.00010681	4.1660e-07	: SST
2	: 1987-02-28	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	309	F	F	6.1035e-05	2.3742e-07	: SST
3	: 1987-03-31	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	292	F	F	7.6294e-05	3.3784e-07	: SST
4	: 1987-04-30	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	183	F	F	7.6294e-05	3.5117e-07	: SST
5	: 1987-05-31	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	207	F	F	0.00010681	4.0307e-07	: SST
7	: 1987-07-31	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	317	F	F	9.1553e-05	3.5634e-07	: SST
8	: 1987-08-31	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	219	F	F	7.6294e-05	2.8849e-07	: SST
9	: 1987-09-30	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	188	F	F	7.6294e-05	3.6168e-07	: SST
10	: 1987-10-31	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	297	F	F	9.1553e-05	3.5001e-07	: SST
11	: 1987-11-30	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	234	F	F	6.1035e-05	2.3839e-07	: SST
12	: 1987-12-31	12:00:00	0	2048	1361	267	F	F	9.3553e-05	3.7624e-07	: SST
11 of 12 records differ											

2.1.4. NINFO - Print the number of parameters, levels or times

Synopsis

<operator> infile

Description

This module prints the number of variables, levels or times of the input dataset.

Operators

npar	Number of parameters Prints the number of parameters (variables).
nlevel	Number of levels Prints the number of levels for each variable.
nyear	Number of years Prints the number of different years.
nmon	Number of months Prints the number of different combinations of years and months.
ndate	Number of dates Prints the number of different dates.
ntime	Number of timesteps Prints the number of timesteps.
ngridpoints	Number of gridpoints Prints the number of gridpoints for each variable.
ngrids	Number of horizontal grids Prints the number of horizontal grids.

Example

To print the number of parameters (variables) in a dataset use:

```
cdo npar infile
```

To print the number of months in a dataset use:

```
cdo nmon infile
```

2.1.5. SHOWINFO - Show variables, levels or times

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile
```

Description

This module prints the format, variables, levels or times of the input dataset.

Operators

showformat	Show file format Prints the file format of the input dataset.
showcode	Show code numbers Prints the code number of all variables.
showname	Show variable names Prints the name of all variables.
showstdname	Show standard names Prints the standard name of all variables.
showlevel	Show levels Prints all levels for each variable.
showtype	Show GRIB level types Prints the GRIB level type for all z-axes.
showyear	Show years Prints all years.
showmon	Show months Prints all months.
showdate	Show date information Prints date information of all timesteps (format YYYY-MM-DD).
showtime	Show time information Prints time information of all timesteps (format hh:mm:ss).
showtimestamp	Show timestamp Prints timestamp of all timesteps (format YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss).

Example

To print the code number of all variables in a dataset use:

```
cdo showcode infile
```

This is an example result of a dataset with three variables:

```
129 130 139
```

To print all months in a dataset use:

```
cdo showmon infile
```

This is an examples result of a dataset with an annual cycle:

```
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12
```

2.1.6. SHOWATTRIBUTE - Show attributes

Synopsis

```
showattribute[,attributes] infile
```

Description

This operator prints the attributes of the data variables of a dataset.

Each attribute has the following structure:

```
[var_nm@][att_nm]
```

var_nm Variable name (optional). Example: pressure

att_nm Attribute name (optional). Example: units

The value of **var_nm** is the name of the variable containing the attribute (named **att_nm**) that you want to print. Use wildcards to print the attribute **att_nm** of more than one variable. A value of **var_nm** of '*' will print the attribute **att_nm** of all data variables. If **var_nm** is missing then **att_nm** refers to a global attribute.

The value of **att_nm** is the name of the attribute you want to print. Use wildcards to print more than one attribute. A value of **att_nm** of '*' will print all attributes.

Parameter

attributes STRING Comma-separated list of attributes.

2.1.7. FILEDES - Dataset description

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile
```

Description

This module provides operators to print meta information about a dataset. The printed meta-data depends on the chosen operator.

Operators

partab	Parameter table Prints all available meta information of the variables.
codetab	Parameter code table Prints a code table with a description of all variables. For each variable the operator prints one line listing the code, name, description and units.
griddes	Grid description Prints the description of all grids.
zaxisdes	Z-axis description Prints the description of all z-axes.
vct	Vertical coordinate table Prints the vertical coordinate table.

Example

Assume all variables of the dataset are on a Gaussian N16 grid. To print the grid description of this dataset use:

```
cdo griddes infile
```

Result:

```
gridtype  : gaussian
gridsize  : 2048
xname     : lon
xlongname : longitude
xunits    : degrees_east
yname     : lat
ylongname : latitude
yunits    : degrees_north
xsize     : 64
ysize     : 32
xfirst    : 0
xinc      : 5.625
yvals     : 85.76058 80.26877 74.74454 69.21297 63.67863 58.1429 52.6065
           47.06964 41.53246 35.99507 30.4575 24.91992 19.38223 13.84448
           8.306702 2.768903 -2.768903 -8.306702 -13.84448 -19.38223
           -24.91992 -30.4575 -35.99507 -41.53246 -47.06964 -52.6065
           -58.1429 -63.67863 -69.21297 -74.74454 -80.26877 -85.76058
```

2.2. File operations

This section contains modules to perform operations on files.

Here is a short overview of all operators in this section:

apply	Apply operators on each input file.
copy	Copy datasets
cat	Concatenate datasets
tee	Duplicate a data stream
pack	Pack data
replace	Replace variables
duplicate	Duplicates a dataset
mergegrid	Merge grid
merge	Merge datasets with different fields
mergetime	Merge datasets sorted by date and time
splitcode	Split code numbers
splitparam	Split parameter identifiers
splitname	Split variable names
splitlevel	Split levels
splitgrid	Split grids
splitzaxis	Split z-axes
splittabnum	Split parameter table numbers
splithour	Split hours
splitday	Split days
splitseas	Split seasons
splityear	Split years
splityearmon	Split in years and months
splitmon	Split months
splitsel	Split time selection
distgrid	Distribute horizontal grid
collgrid	Collect horizontal grid

2.2.1. APPLY - Apply operators

Synopsis

```
apply,operators infile
```

Description

The apply utility runs the named operators on each input file. The input files must be enclosed in square brackets. This utility can only be used on a series of input files. These are all operators with more than one input file (infile). Here is an incomplete list of these operators: [copy](#), [cat](#), [merge](#), [mergetime](#), [select](#), [ENSSTAT](#). The parameter operators is a blank-separated list of **CDO** operators. Use quotation marks if more than one operator is needed. Each operator may have only one input and output stream.

Parameter

operators STRING Blank-separated list of CDO operators.

Example

Suppose we have multiple input files with multiple variables on different time steps. The input files contain the variables U and V, among others. We are only interested in the absolute windspeed on all time steps. Here is the standard **CDO** solution for this task:

```
cdo expr,wind="sqrt(u*u+v*v)" -mergetime infile1 infile2 infile3 outfile
```

This first joins all the time steps together and then calculates the wind speed. If there are many variables in the input files, this procedure is ineffective. In this case it is better to first calculate the wind speed:

```
cdo mergetime -expr,wind="sqrt(u*u+v*v)" infile1 \  
-expr,wind="sqrt(u*u+v*v)" infile2 \  
-expr,wind="sqrt(u*u+v*v)" infile3 outfile
```

However, this can quickly become very confusing with more than 3 input files. The apply operator solves this problem:

```
cdo mergetime -apply,-expr,wind="sqrt(u*u+v*v)" [ infile1 infile2 infile3 ] outfile
```

Another example is the calculation of the mean value over several input files with ensmean. The input files contain several variables, but we are only interested in the variable named XXX:

```
cdo ensmean -apply,-selname,XXX [ infile1 infile2 infile3 ] outfile
```

2.2.2. COPY - Copy datasets

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile outfile
```

Description

This module contains operators to copy or concatenate datasets. `infile` is an arbitrary number of input files. All input files need to have the same structure with the same variables on different timesteps.

Operators

- copy** Copy datasets
Copies all input datasets to outfile.
- cat** Concatenate datasets
Concatenates all input datasets and appends the result to the end of outfile. If outfile does not exist it will be created.

Example

To change the format of a dataset to NetCDF use:

```
cdo -f nc copy infile outfile.nc
```

Add the option `'-r'` to create a relative time axis, as is required for proper recognition by GrADS or Ferret:

```
cdo -r -f nc copy infile outfile.nc
```

To concatenate 3 datasets with different timesteps of the same variables use:

```
cdo copy infile1 infile2 infile3 outfile
```

If the output dataset already exists and you wish to extend it with more timesteps use:

```
cdo cat infile1 infile2 infile3 outfile
```

2.2.3. TEE - Duplicate a data stream and write it to file

Synopsis

```
tee,outfile2 infile outfile1
```

Description

This operator copies the input dataset to outfile1 and outfile2. The first output stream in outfile1 can be further processed with other cdo operators. The second output outfile2 is written to disk. It can be used to store intermediate results to a file.

Parameter

outfile2 STRING Destination filename for the copy of the input file

Example

To compute the daily and monthly average of a dataset use:

```
cdo monavg -tee,outfile_dayavg dayavg infile outfile_monavg
```

2.2.4. PACK - Pack data

Synopsis

```
pack infile outfile
```

Description

Packing reduces the data volume by reducing the precision of the stored numbers. It is implemented using the NetCDF attributes `add_offset` and `scale_factor`. The operator `pack` calculates the attributes `add_offset` and `scale_factor` for all variables. The default data type for all variables is automatically changed to 16-bit integer. Use the **CDO** option `-b` to change the data type to a different integer precision, if needed. Missing values are automatically transformed to the current data type.

2.2.5. REPLACE - Replace variables

Synopsis

```
replace infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

This operator replaces variables in `infile1` by variables from `infile2` and write the result to `outfile`. Both input datasets need to have the same number of timesteps. All variable names may only occur once!

Example

Assume the first input dataset `infile1` has three variables with the names `geosp`, `t` and `tslm1` and the second input dataset `infile2` has only the variable `tslm1`. To replace the variable `tslm1` in `infile1` by `tslm1` from `infile2` use:

```
cdo replace infile1 infile2 outfile
```

2.2.6. DUPLICATE - Duplicates a dataset

Synopsis

```
duplicate[ndup] infile outfile
```

Description

This operator duplicates the contents of `infile` and writes the result to `outfile`. The optional parameter sets the number of duplicates, the default is 2.

Parameter

ndup INTEGER Number of duplicates, default is 2.

2.2.7. MERGEGRID - Merge grid

Synopsis

```
mergegrid infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

Merges grid points of all variables from `infile2` to `infile1` and write the result to `outfile`. Only the non missing values of `infile2` will be used. The horizontal grid of `infile2` should be smaller or equal to the grid of `infile1` and the resolution must be the same. Only rectilinear grids are supported. Both input files need to have the same variables and the same number of timesteps.

2.2.8. MERGE - Merge datasets

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile1 outfile
```

Description

This module reads datasets from several input files, merges them and writes the resulting dataset to outfile.

Operators

- merge** Merge datasets with different fields
Merges time series of different fields from several input datasets. The number of fields per timestep written to outfile is the sum of the field numbers per timestep in all input datasets. The time series on all input datasets are required to have different fields and the same number of timesteps. The fields in each different input file either have to be different variables or different levels of the same variable. A mixture of different variables on different levels in different input files is not allowed.
- mergetime** Merge datasets sorted by date and time
Merges all timesteps of all input files sorted by date and time. All input files need to have the same structure with the same variables on different timesteps. After this operation every input timestep is in outfile and all timesteps are sorted by date and time.

Environment

- SKIP_SAME_TIME** If set to 1, skips all consecutive timesteps with a double entry of the same timestamp.

Note

The operators in this module need to open all input files simultaneously. The maximum number of open files depends on the operating system!

Example

Assume three datasets with the same number of timesteps and different variables in each dataset. To merge these datasets to a new dataset use:

```
cdo merge infile1 infile2 infile3 outfile
```

Assume you split a 6 hourly dataset with [splithour](#). This produces four datasets, one for each hour. The following command merges them together:

```
cdo mergetime infile1 infile2 infile3 infile4 outfile
```

2.2.9. SPLIT - Split a dataset

Synopsis

```
<operator>[,params] infile obase
```

Description

This module splits `infile` into pieces. The output files will be named `<obase><xxx><suffix>` where `suffix` is the filename extension derived from the file format. `xxx` and the contents of the output files depends on the chosen operator. `params` is a comma-separated list of processing parameters.

Operators

splitcode	Split code numbers Splits a dataset into pieces, one for each different code number. <code>xxx</code> will have three digits with the code number.
splitparam	Split parameter identifiers Splits a dataset into pieces, one for each different parameter identifier. <code>xxx</code> will be a string with the parameter identifier.
splitname	Split variable names Splits a dataset into pieces, one for each variable name. <code>xxx</code> will be a string with the variable name.
splitlevel	Split levels Splits a dataset into pieces, one for each different level. <code>xxx</code> will have six digits with the level.
splitgrid	Split grids Splits a dataset into pieces, one for each different grid. <code>xxx</code> will have two digits with the grid number.
splitzaxis	Split z-axes Splits a dataset into pieces, one for each different z-axis. <code>xxx</code> will have two digits with the z-axis number.
splittabnum	Split parameter table numbers Splits a dataset into pieces, one for each GRIB1 parameter table number. <code>xxx</code> will have three digits with the GRIB1 parameter table number.

Parameter

<code>swap</code>	STRING	Swap the position of <code>obase</code> and <code>xxx</code> in the output filename
<code>uuid=<attname></code>	STRING	Add a UUID as global attribute <code><attname></code> to each output file

Environment

<code>CDO_FILE_SUFFIX</code>	Set the default file suffix. This suffix will be added to the output file names instead of the filename extension derived from the file format. Set this variable to NULL to disable the adding of a file suffix.
------------------------------	---

Note

The operators in this module need to open all output files simultaneously. The maximum number of open files depends on the operating system!

Example

Assume an input GRIB1 dataset with three variables, e.g. code number 129, 130 and 139. To split this dataset into three pieces, one for each code number use:

```
cdo splitcode infile code
```

Result of 'dir code*':

```
code129.grb code130.grb code139.grb
```

2.2.10. SPLITTIME - Split timesteps of a dataset

Synopsis

`<operator> infile obase`

`splitmon[,format] infile obase`

Description

This module splits `infile` into timesteps pieces. The output files will be named `<obase><xxx><suffix>` where `suffix` is the filename extension derived from the file format. `xxx` and the contents of the output files depends on the chosen operator.

Operators

splithour	Split hours Splits a file into pieces, one for each different hour. <code>xxx</code> will have two digits with the hour.
splitday	Split days Splits a file into pieces, one for each different day. <code>xxx</code> will have two digits with the day.
splitseas	Split seasons Splits a file into pieces, one for each different season. <code>xxx</code> will have three characters with the season.
splityear	Split years Splits a file into pieces, one for each different year. <code>xxx</code> will have four digits with the year (YYYY).
splityearmon	Split in years and months Splits a file into pieces, one for each different year and month. <code>xxx</code> will have six digits with the year and month (YYYYMM).
splitmon	Split months Splits a file into pieces, one for each different month. <code>xxx</code> will have two digits with the month.

Parameter

`format` STRING C-style format for `strftime()` (e.g. `%B` for the full month name)

Environment

`CDO_FILE_SUFFIX` Set the default file suffix. This suffix will be added to the output file names instead of the filename extension derived from the file format. Set this variable to NULL to disable the adding of a file suffix.

Note

The operators in this module need to open all output files simultaneously. The maximum number of open files depends on the operating system!

Example

Assume the input GRIB1 dataset has timesteps from January to December. To split each month with all variables into one separate file use:

```
cdo splitmon infile mon
```

Result of 'dir mon*':

```
mon01.grb  mon02.grb  mon03.grb  mon04.grb  mon05.grb  mon06.grb
mon07.grb  mon08.grb  mon09.grb  mon10.grb  mon11.grb  mon12.grb
```

2.2.11. SPLITSEL - Split selected timesteps

Synopsis

```
splitsel,nsets[,noffset[,nskip]] infile obase
```

Description

This operator splits *infile* into pieces, one for each adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same selected time range. The output files will be named `<obase><nnnnnn><suffix>` where *nnnnnn* is the sequence number and *suffix* is the filename extension derived from the file format.

Parameter

<i>nsets</i>	INTEGER	Number of input timesteps for each output file
<i>noffset</i>	INTEGER	Number of input timesteps skipped before the first timestep range (optional)
<i>nskip</i>	INTEGER	Number of input timesteps skipped between timestep ranges (optional)

Environment

CDO_FILE_SUFFIX	Set the default file suffix. This suffix will be added to the output file names instead of the filename extension derived from the file format. Set this variable to NULL to disable the adding of a file suffix.
-----------------	---

2.2.12. DISTGRID - Distribute horizontal grid

Synopsis

```
distgrid,nx[,ny] infile obase
```

Description

This operator distributes a dataset into smaller pieces. Each output file contains a different region of the horizontal source grid. 2D Lon/Lat grids can be split into $nx*ny$ pieces, where a target grid region contains a structured longitude/latitude box of the source grid. Data on an unstructured grid is split into nx pieces. The output files will be named `<obase><xxx><suffix>` where suffix is the filename extension derived from the file format. xxx will have five digits with the number of the target region.

Parameter

<i>nx</i>	INTEGER	Number of regions in x direction, or number of pieces for unstructured grids
<i>ny</i>	INTEGER	Number of regions in y direction [default: 1]

Note

This operator needs to open all output files simultaneously. The maximum number of open files depends on the operating system!

Example

Distribute data on a 2D Lon/Lat grid into 6 smaller files, each output file receives one half of x and a third of y of the source grid:

```
cdo distgrid,2,3 infile.nc obase
```

Below is a schematic illustration of this example:

On the left side is the data of the input file and on the right side is the data of the six output files.

2.2.13. COLLGRID - Collect horizontal grid

Synopsis

```
collgrid[,nx[,names]] infile outfile
```

Description

This operator collects the data of the input files to one output file. All input files need to have the same variables and the same number of timesteps on a different horizontal grid region. If the source regions are on a structured lon/lat grid, all regions together must result in a new structured lat/long grid box. Data on an unstructured grid is concatenated in the order of the input files. The parameter *nx* needs to be specified only for curvilinear grids.

Parameter

<i>nx</i>	INTEGER	Number of regions in x direction [default: number of input files]
<i>names</i>	STRING	Comma-separated list of variable names [default: all variables]

Note

This operator needs to open all input files simultaneously. The maximum number of open files depends on the operating system!

Example

Collect the horizontal grid of 6 input files. Each input file contains a lon/lat region of the target grid:

```
cdo collgrid infile[1-6] outfile
```

Below is a schematic illustration of this example:

On the left side is the data of the six input files and on the right side is the collected data of the output file.

2.3. Selection

This section contains modules to select time steps, fields or a part of a field from a dataset.

Here is a short overview of all operators in this section:

select	Select fields
delete	Delete fields
selmulti	Select multiple fields
delmulti	Delete multiple fields
changemulti	Change identification of multiple fields
selparam	Select parameters by identifier
delparam	Delete parameters by identifier
selcode	Select parameters by code number
delcode	Delete parameters by code number
selname	Select parameters by name
delname	Delete parameters by name
selstdname	Select parameters by standard name
sellevel	Select levels
sellevelidx	Select levels by index
selgrid	Select grids
selzaxis	Select z-axes
selzaxisname	Select z-axes by name
selltype	Select GRIB level types
seltabnum	Select parameter table numbers
sel timestep	Select timesteps
seltime	Select times
selhour	Select hours
selday	Select days
selmonth	Select months
selyear	Select years
selseason	Select seasons
seldate	Select dates
selsmon	Select single month
sellonlatbox	Select a longitude/latitude box
selindexbox	Select an index box
selcircle	Select cells inside a circle
selgridcell	Select grid cells
delgridcell	Delete grid cells
samplegrid	Resample grid
selyearidx	Select year by index
bottomvalue	Extract bottom level
topvalue	Extract top level
isosurface	Extract isosurface

2.3.1. SELECT - Select fields

Synopsis

```
<operator>,params infile outfile
```

Description

This module selects some fields from `infile` and writes them to `outfile`. `infile` is an arbitrary number of input files. All input files need to have the same structure with the same variables on different timesteps. The fields selected depends on the chosen parameters. Parameter is a comma-separated list of "key=value" pairs. A range of integer values can be specified by `first/last[/inc]`. Wildcards are supported for string values.

Operators

select	Select fields Selects all fields with parameters in a user given list.
delete	Delete fields Deletes all fields with parameters in a user given list.

Parameter

<i>name</i>	STRING	Comma-separated list of variable names.
<i>param</i>	STRING	Comma-separated list of parameter identifiers.
<i>code</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or <code>first/last[/inc]</code> range of code numbers.
<i>level</i>	FLOAT	Comma-separated list of vertical levels.
<i>levrange</i>	FLOAT	First and last value of the level range.
<i>levidx</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or <code>first/last[/inc]</code> range of index of levels.
<i>zaxisname</i>	STRING	Comma-separated list of zaxis names.
<i>zaxisnum</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or <code>first/last[/inc]</code> range of zaxis numbers.
<i>ltype</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or <code>first/last[/inc]</code> range of GRIB level types.
<i>gridname</i>	STRING	Comma-separated list of grid names.
<i>gridnum</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or <code>first/last[/inc]</code> range of grid numbers.
<i>steptype</i>	STRING	Comma-separated list of timestep types.
<i>date</i>	STRING	Comma-separated list of dates (format YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss).
<i>startdate</i>	STRING	Start date (format YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss).
<i>enddate</i>	STRING	End date (format YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss).
<i>minute</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or <code>first/last[/inc]</code> range of minutes.
<i>hour</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or <code>first/last[/inc]</code> range of hours.
<i>day</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or <code>first/last[/inc]</code> range of days.
<i>month</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or <code>first/last[/inc]</code> range of months.
<i>season</i>	STRING	Comma-separated list of seasons (substring of DJFMAMJJASOND or ANN).
<i>year</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or <code>first/last[/inc]</code> range of years.

<i>dom</i>	STRING	Comma-separated list of the day of month (e.g. 29feb).
<i>timestep</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or first/last[/inc] range of timesteps. Negative values select timesteps from the end (NetCDF only).
<i>timestep_of_year</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or first/last[/inc] range of timesteps of year.
<i>timestepmask</i>	STRING	Read timesteps from a mask file.

Example

Assume you have 3 inputfiles. Each inputfile contains the same variables for a different time period. To select the variable T,U and V on the levels 200, 500 and 850 from all 3 input files, use:

```
cdo select,name=T,U,V,level=200,500,850 infile1 infile2 infile3 outfile
```

To remove the February 29th use:

```
cdo delete,dom=29feb infile outfile
```

2.3.2. SELMULTI - Select multiple fields via GRIB1 parameters

Synopsis

```
<operator>,selection-specification infile outfile
```

Description

This module selects multiple fields from `infile` and writes them to `outfile`. `selection-specification` is a filename or in-place string with the selection specification. Each selection-specification has the following compact notation format:

```
<type>(parameters; leveltype(s); levels)
```

`type` sel for select or del for delete (optional)
`parameters` GRIB1 parameter code number
`leveltype` GRIB1 level type
`levels` value of each level

Examples:

```
(1; 103; 0)
(33,34; 105; 10)
(11,17; 105; 2)
(71,73,74,75,61,62,65,117,67,122,121,11,131,66,84,111,112; 105; 0)
```

The following descriptive notation can also be used for selection specification from a file:

```
SELECT/DELETE, PARAMETER=parameters, LEVTYPE=leveltye(s), LEVEL=levels
```

Examples:

```
SELECT, PARAMETER=1, LEVTYPE=103, LEVEL=0
SELECT, PARAMETER=33/34, LEVTYPE=105, LEVEL=10
SELECT, PARAMETER=11/17, LEVTYPE=105, LEVEL=2
SELECT, PARAMETER=71/73/74/75/61/62/65/117/67/122, LEVTYPE=105, LEVEL=0
DELETE, PARAMETER=128, LEVTYPE=109, LEVEL=*
```

The following will convert Pressure from Pa into hPa; Temp from Kelvin to Celsius:

```
SELECT, PARAMETER=1, LEVTYPE= 103, LEVEL=0, SCALE=0.01
SELECT, PARAMETER=11, LEVTYPE=105, LEVEL=2, OFFSET=273.15
```

If `SCALE` and/or `OFFSET` are defined, then the data values are scaled as `SCALE*(VALUE-OFFSET)`.

Operators

selmulti Select multiple fields

delmulti Delete multiple fields

changemulti Change identification of multiple fields

Example

Change ECMWF GRIB code of surface pressure to Hirlam notation:

```
cdo changemulti,'{(134;1;*|1;105;*)}' infile outfile
```

2.3.3. SELVAR - Select fields

Synopsis

```

<operator>,params infile outfile
selcode,codes infile outfile
delcode,codes infile outfile
selname,names infile outfile
delname,names infile outfile
selstdname,stdnames infile outfile
sellevel,levels infile outfile
sellevidx,levidx infile outfile
selgrid,grids infile outfile
selzaxis,zaxes infile outfile
selzaxisname,zaxisnames infile outfile
selltype,ltypes infile outfile
seltabnum,tabnums infile outfile

```

Description

This module selects some fields from `infile` and writes them to `outfile`. The fields selected depends on the chosen operator and the parameters. A range of integer values can be specified by `first/last[/inc]`.

Operators

selparam	Select parameters by identifier Selects all fields with parameter identifiers in a user given list.
delparam	Delete parameters by identifier Deletes all fields with parameter identifiers in a user given list.
selcode	Select parameters by code number Selects all fields with code numbers in a user given list or range.
delcode	Delete parameters by code number Deletes all fields with code numbers in a user given list or range.
selname	Select parameters by name Selects all fields with parameter names in a user given list.
delname	Delete parameters by name Deletes all fields with parameter names in a user given list.
selstdname	Select parameters by standard name Selects all fields with standard names in a user given list.
sellevel	Select levels Selects all fields with levels in a user given list.
sellevidx	Select levels by index Selects all fields with index of levels in a user given list or range.
selgrid	Select grids Selects all fields with grids in a user given list.

selzaxis	Select z-axes Selects all fields with z-axes in a user given list.
selzaxisname	Select z-axes by name Selects all fields with z-axis names in a user given list.
selltype	Select GRIB level types Selects all fields with GRIB level type in a user given list or range.
seltabnum	Select parameter table numbers Selects all fields with parameter table numbers in a user given list or range.

Parameter

<i>params</i>	STRING	Comma-separated list of parameter identifiers.
<i>codes</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or first/last[/inc] range of code numbers.
<i>names</i>	STRING	Comma-separated list of variable names.
<i>stdnames</i>	STRING	Comma-separated list of standard names.
<i>levels</i>	FLOAT	Comma-separated list of vertical levels.
<i>levidx</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or first/last[/inc] range of index of levels.
<i>ltypes</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or first/last[/inc] range of GRIB level types.
<i>grids</i>	STRING	Comma-separated list of grid names or numbers.
<i>zaxes</i>	STRING	Comma-separated list of z-axis types or numbers.
<i>zaxisnames</i>	STRING	Comma-separated list of z-axis names.
<i>tabnums</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or range of parameter table numbers.

Example

Assume an input dataset has three variables with the code numbers 129, 130 and 139. To select the variables with the code number 129 and 139 use:

```
cdo selcode,129,139 infile outfile
```

You can also select the code number 129 and 139 by deleting the code number 130 with:

```
cdo delcode,130 infile outfile
```

2.3.4. SELTIME - Select timesteps

Synopsis

```

sel timestep,timesteps infile outfile
sel time,times infile outfile
sel hour,hours infile outfile
sel day,days infile outfile
sel month,months infile outfile
sel year,years infile outfile
sel season,seasons infile outfile
sel date,startdate[enddate] infile outfile
sel smon,month[nts1[nts2]] infile outfile

```

Description

This module selects user specified timesteps from `infile` and writes them to `outfile`. The timesteps selected depends on the chosen operator and the parameters. A range of integer values can be specified by `first/last[/inc]`.

Operators

sel timestep	Select timesteps Selects all timesteps with a timestep in a user given list or range.
sel time	Select times Selects all timesteps with a time in a user given list or range.
sel hour	Select hours Selects all timesteps with a hour in a user given list or range.
sel day	Select days Selects all timesteps with a day in a user given list or range.
sel month	Select months Selects all timesteps with a month in a user given list or range.
sel year	Select years Selects all timesteps with a year in a user given list or range.
sel season	Select seasons Selects all timesteps with a month of a season in a user given list.
sel date	Select dates Selects all timesteps with a date in a user given range.
sel smon	Select single month Selects a month and optional an arbitrary number of timesteps before and after this month.

Parameter

<i>timesteps</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or first/last[/inc] range of timesteps. Negative values select timesteps from the end (NetCDF only).
<i>times</i>	STRING	Comma-separated list of times (format hh:mm:ss).
<i>hours</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or first/last[/inc] range of hours.
<i>days</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or first/last[/inc] range of days.
<i>months</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or first/last[/inc] range of months.
<i>years</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list or first/last[/inc] range of years.
<i>seasons</i>	STRING	Comma-separated list of seasons (substring of DJFMAMJJASOND or ANN).
<i>startdate</i>	STRING	Start date (format YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss).
<i>enddate</i>	STRING	End date (format YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss) [default: startdate].
<i>nts1</i>	INTEGER	Number of timesteps before the selected month [default: 0].
<i>nts2</i>	INTEGER	Number of timesteps after the selected month [default: nts1].

2.3.5. SELBOX - Select a box of a field

Synopsis

```
sellonlatbox,lon1,lon2,lat1,lat2 infile outfile
selindexbox,idx1,idx2,idy1,idy2 infile outfile
```

Description

Selects a box of the rectangularly understood field.

Operators

sellonlatbox Select a longitude/latitude box
 Selects a regular longitude/latitude box. The user has to give the longitudes and latitudes of the edges of the box. Considered are only those grid cells with the grid center inside the lon/lat box. For rotated lon/lat grids the parameter needs to be rotated coordinates.

selindexbox Select an index box
 Selects an index box. The user has to give the indices of the edges of the box. The index of the left edge may be greater then that of the right edge.

Parameter

<i>lon1</i>	FLOAT	Western longitude in degrees
<i>lon2</i>	FLOAT	Eastern longitude in degrees
<i>lat1</i>	FLOAT	Southern or northern latitude in degrees
<i>lat2</i>	FLOAT	Northern or southern latitude in degrees
<i>idx1</i>	INTEGER	Index of first longitude (1 - nlon)
<i>idx2</i>	INTEGER	Index of last longitude (1 - nlon)
<i>idy1</i>	INTEGER	Index of first latitude (1 - nlat)
<i>idy2</i>	INTEGER	Index of last latitude (1 - nlat)

Example

To select the region with the longitudes from 30W to 60E and latitudes from 30N to 80N from all input fields use:

```
cdo sellonlatbox,-30,60,30,80 infile outfile
```

If the input dataset has fields on a Gaussian N16 grid, the same box can be selected with [selindexbox](#) by:

```
cdo selindexbox,60,11,3,11 infile outfile
```

2.3.6. SELCIRCLE - Select cells inside a circle

Synopsis

```
selcircle[lon,lat,radius] infile outfile
```

Description

Selects all grid cells with the center point inside a circle. The circle is described by geographic coordinates of the center and the radius of the circle. The resulting grid is unstructured.

Parameter

<i>lon</i>	FLOAT	Longitude of the center of the circle in degrees, default lon=0.0
<i>lat</i>	FLOAT	Latitude of the center of the circle in degrees, default lat=0.0
<i>radius</i>	STRING	Radius of the circle, default radius=1deg (units: deg, rad, km, m)

2.3.7. SELGRIDCELL - Select grid cells

Synopsis

```
<operator> ,indices infile outfile
```

Description

The operator selects grid cells of all fields from `infile`. The user must specify the index of each grid cell. The resulting grid in `outfile` is unstructured.

Operators

`selgridcell` Select grid cells

`delgridcell` Delete grid cells

Parameter

indices INTEGER Comma-separated list or first/last[/inc] range of indices

2.3.8. SAMPLEGRID - Resample grid

Synopsis

```
samplegrid, factor infile outfile
```

Description

This is a special operator for resampling the horizontal grid. No interpolation takes place. Resample `factor=2` means every second grid point is removed. Only rectilinear and curvilinear source grids are supported by this operator.

Parameter

factor INTEGER Resample factor, typically 2, which will half the resolution

2.3.9. SELYEARIDX - Select year by index

Synopsis

```
selyearidx infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

Selects field elements from `infile2` by a yearly time index from `infile1`. The yearly indices in `infile1` should be the result of corresponding [yearminidx](#) and [yearmaxidx](#) operations, respectively.

2.3.10. SELSURFACE - Extract surface

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile outfile  
isosurface,isovalue infile outfile
```

Description

This module computes a surface from all 3D variables. The result is a horizontal 2D field.

Operators

bottomvalue	Extract bottom level This operator selects the valid values at the bottom level. The NetCDF CF compliant attribute positive is used to determine where top and bottom are. If this attribute is missing, low values are bottom and high values are top.
topvalue	Extract top level This operator selects the valid values at the top level. The NetCDF CF compliant attribute positive is used to determine where top and bottom are. If this attribute is missing, low values are bottom and high values are top.
isosurface	Extract isosurface This operator computes an isosurface. The value of the isosurface is specified by the parameter isovalue. The isosurface is calculated by linear interpolation between two layers.

Parameter

<i>isovalue</i>	FLOAT	Isosurface value
-----------------	-------	------------------

2.4. Conditional selection

This section contains modules to conditional select field elements. The fields in the first input file are handled as a mask. A value not equal to zero is treated as "true", zero is treated as "false".

Here is a short overview of all operators in this section:

ifthen	If then
ifnotthen	If not then
ifthenelse	If then else
ifthenc	If then constant
ifnotthenc	If not then constant
reducegrid	Reduce input file variables to locations, where mask is non-zero.

2.4.1. COND - Conditional select one field

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

This module selects field elements from `infile2` with respect to `infile1` and writes them to `outfile`. The fields in `infile1` are handled as a mask. A value not equal to zero is treated as "true", zero is treated as "false". The number of fields in `infile1` has either to be the same as in `infile2` or the same as in one timestep of `infile2` or only one. The fields in `outfile` inherit the meta data from `infile2`.

Operators

ifthen If then

$$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} i_2(t, x) & \text{if } i_1([t,]x) \neq 0 \quad \wedge \quad i_1([t,]x) \neq \text{miss} \\ \text{miss} & \text{if } i_1([t,]x) = 0 \quad \vee \quad i_1([t,]x) = \text{miss} \end{cases}$$

ifnotthen If not then

$$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} i_2(t, x) & \text{if } i_1([t,]x) = 0 \quad \wedge \quad i_1([t,]x) \neq \text{miss} \\ \text{miss} & \text{if } i_1([t,]x) \neq 0 \quad \vee \quad i_1([t,]x) = \text{miss} \end{cases}$$

Example

To select all field elements of `infile2` if the corresponding field element of `infile1` is greater than 0 use:

```
cdo ifthen infile1 infile2 outfile
```

2.4.2. COND2 - Conditional select two fields

Synopsis

```
ifthenelse infile1 infile2 infile3 outfile
```

Description

This operator selects field elements from `infile2` or `infile3` with respect to `infile1` and writes them to `outfile`. The fields in `infile1` are handled as a mask. A value not equal to zero is treated as "true", zero is treated as "false". The number of fields in `infile1` has either to be the same as in `infile2` or the same as in one timestep of `infile2` or only one. `infile2` and `infile3` need to have the same number of fields. The fields in `outfile` inherit the meta data from `infile2`.

$$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} i_2(t, x) & \text{if } i_1([t,]x) \neq 0 \quad \wedge \quad i_1([t,]x) \neq \text{miss} \\ i_3(t, x) & \text{if } i_1([t,]x) = 0 \quad \wedge \quad i_1([t,]x) \neq \text{miss} \\ \text{miss} & \text{if } i_1([t,]x) = \text{miss} \end{cases}$$

Example

To select all field elements of `infile2` if the corresponding field element of `infile1` is greater than 0 and from `infile3` otherwise use:

```
cdo ifthenelse infile1 infile2 infile3 outfile
```

2.4.3. CONDC - Conditional select a constant

Synopsis

```
<operator>,c infile outfile
```

Description

This module creates fields with a constant value or missing value. The fields in `infile` are handled as a mask. A value not equal to zero is treated as "true", zero is treated as "false".

Operators

ifthenc If then constant

$$o(t,x) = \begin{cases} c & \text{if } i(t,x) \neq 0 \wedge i(t,x) \neq \text{miss} \\ \text{miss} & \text{if } i(t,x) = 0 \vee i(t,x) = \text{miss} \end{cases}$$

ifnotthenc If not then constant

$$o(t,x) = \begin{cases} c & \text{if } i(t,x) = 0 \wedge i(t,x) \neq \text{miss} \\ \text{miss} & \text{if } i(t,x) \neq 0 \vee i(t,x) = \text{miss} \end{cases}$$

Parameter

`c` FLOAT Constant

Example

To create fields with the constant value 7 if the corresponding field element of `infile` is greater than 0 use:

```
cdo ifthenc,7 infile outfile
```

2.4.4. MAPREDUCE - Reduce fields to user-defined mask

Synopsis

```
reducegrid,mask[,limitCoordsOutput] infile outfile
```

Description

This module holds an operator for data reduction based on a user defined mask. The output grid is unstructured and includes coordinate bounds. Bounds can be avoided by using the additional 'nobounds' keyword. With 'nocoords' given, coordinates are completely suppressed.

Parameter

<i>mask</i>	STRING	file which holds the mask field
<i>limitCoordsOutput</i>	STRING	optional parameter to limit coordinates output: 'nobounds' disables coordinate bounds, 'nocoords' avoids all coordinate information

Example

To limit data fields to land values, a mask has to be created first with

```
cdo -gtc,0 -topo,ni96 lsm_gme96.grb
```

Here a GME grid is used. Say temp_gme96.grb contains a global temperature field. The following command limits the global grid to landpoints.

```
cdo -f nc reduce,lsm_gme96.grb temp_gme96.grb tempOnLand_gme96.nc
```

Note that output file type is NetCDF, because unstructured grids cannot be stored in GRIB format.

2.5. Comparison

This section contains modules to compare datasets. The resulting field is a mask containing 1 if the comparison is true and 0 if not.

Here is a short overview of all operators in this section:

eq	Equal
ne	Not equal
le	Less equal
lt	Less than
ge	Greater equal
gt	Greater than
eqc	Equal constant
nec	Not equal constant
lec	Less equal constant
ltc	Less than constant
gec	Greater equal constant
gtc	Greater than constant

2.5.1. COMP - Comparison of two fields

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

This module compares two datasets field by field. The resulting field is a mask containing 1 if the comparison is true and 0 if not. The number of fields in `infile1` should be the same as in `infile2`. One of the input files can contain only one timestep or one field. The fields in `outfile` inherit the meta data from `infile1` or `infile2`. The type of comparison depends on the chosen operator.

Operators

eq Equal

$$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i_1(t, x) = i_2(t, x) \wedge i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x) \neq \text{miss} \\ 0 & \text{if } i_1(t, x) \neq i_2(t, x) \wedge i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x) \neq \text{miss} \\ \text{miss} & \text{if } i_1(t, x) = \text{miss} \vee i_2(t, x) = \text{miss} \end{cases}$$

ne Not equal

$$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i_1(t, x) \neq i_2(t, x) \wedge i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x) \neq \text{miss} \\ 0 & \text{if } i_1(t, x) = i_2(t, x) \wedge i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x) \neq \text{miss} \\ \text{miss} & \text{if } i_1(t, x) = \text{miss} \vee i_2(t, x) = \text{miss} \end{cases}$$

le Less equal

$$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i_1(t, x) \leq i_2(t, x) \wedge i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x) \neq \text{miss} \\ 0 & \text{if } i_1(t, x) > i_2(t, x) \wedge i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x) \neq \text{miss} \\ \text{miss} & \text{if } i_1(t, x) = \text{miss} \vee i_2(t, x) = \text{miss} \end{cases}$$

lt Less than

$$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i_1(t, x) < i_2(t, x) \wedge i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x) \neq \text{miss} \\ 0 & \text{if } i_1(t, x) \geq i_2(t, x) \wedge i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x) \neq \text{miss} \\ \text{miss} & \text{if } i_1(t, x) = \text{miss} \vee i_2(t, x) = \text{miss} \end{cases}$$

ge Greater equal

$$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i_1(t, x) \geq i_2(t, x) \wedge i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x) \neq \text{miss} \\ 0 & \text{if } i_1(t, x) < i_2(t, x) \wedge i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x) \neq \text{miss} \\ \text{miss} & \text{if } i_1(t, x) = \text{miss} \vee i_2(t, x) = \text{miss} \end{cases}$$

gt Greater than

$$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i_1(t, x) > i_2(t, x) \wedge i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x) \neq \text{miss} \\ 0 & \text{if } i_1(t, x) \leq i_2(t, x) \wedge i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x) \neq \text{miss} \\ \text{miss} & \text{if } i_1(t, x) = \text{miss} \vee i_2(t, x) = \text{miss} \end{cases}$$

Example

To create a mask containing 1 if the elements of two fields are the same and 0 if the elements are different use:

```
cdo eq infile1 infile2 outfile
```

2.5.2. COMPC - Comparison of a field with a constant

Synopsis

```
<operator>,c infile outfile
```

Description

This module compares all fields of a dataset with a constant. The resulting field is a mask containing 1 if the comparison is true and 0 if not. The type of comparison depends on the chosen operator.

Operators

eqc	Equal constant	
	$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i(t, x) = c & \wedge i(t, x), c \neq \text{miss} \\ 0 & \text{if } i(t, x) \neq c & \wedge i(t, x), c \neq \text{miss} \\ \text{miss} & \text{if } i(t, x) = \text{miss} & \vee c = \text{miss} \end{cases}$	
nec	Not equal constant	
	$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i(t, x) \neq c & \wedge i(t, x), c \neq \text{miss} \\ 0 & \text{if } i(t, x) = c & \wedge i(t, x), c \neq \text{miss} \\ \text{miss} & \text{if } i(t, x) = \text{miss} & \vee c = \text{miss} \end{cases}$	
lec	Less equal constant	
	$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i(t, x) \leq c & \wedge i(t, x), c \neq \text{miss} \\ 0 & \text{if } i(t, x) > c & \wedge i(t, x), c \neq \text{miss} \\ \text{miss} & \text{if } i(t, x) = \text{miss} & \vee c = \text{miss} \end{cases}$	
ltc	Less than constant	
	$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i(t, x) < c & \wedge i(t, x), c \neq \text{miss} \\ 0 & \text{if } i(t, x) \geq c & \wedge i(t, x), c \neq \text{miss} \\ \text{miss} & \text{if } i(t, x) = \text{miss} & \vee c = \text{miss} \end{cases}$	
gec	Greater equal constant	
	$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i(t, x) \geq c & \wedge i(t, x), c \neq \text{miss} \\ 0 & \text{if } i(t, x) < c & \wedge i(t, x), c \neq \text{miss} \\ \text{miss} & \text{if } i(t, x) = \text{miss} & \vee c = \text{miss} \end{cases}$	
gtc	Greater than constant	
	$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i(t, x) > c & \wedge i(t, x), c \neq \text{miss} \\ 0 & \text{if } i(t, x) \leq c & \wedge i(t, x), c \neq \text{miss} \\ \text{miss} & \text{if } i(t, x) = \text{miss} & \vee c = \text{miss} \end{cases}$	

Parameter

c FLOAT Constant

Example

To create a mask containing 1 if the field element is greater than 273.15 and 0 if not use:

```
cdo gtc,273.15 infile outfile
```

2.6. Modification

This section contains modules to modify the metadata, fields or part of a field in a dataset.

Here is a short overview of all operators in this section:

setattribute	Set attributes
setpartabp	Set parameter table
setpartabn	Set parameter table
setcodetab	Set parameter code table
setcode	Set code number
setparam	Set parameter identifier
setname	Set variable name
setunit	Set variable unit
setlevel	Set level
setltype	Set GRIB level type
setdate	Set date
settime	Set time of the day
setday	Set day
setmon	Set month
setyear	Set year
setunits	Set time units
settaxis	Set time axis
settbounds	Set time bounds
setreftime	Set reference time
setcalendar	Set calendar
shifttime	Shift timesteps
chcode	Change code number
chparam	Change parameter identifier
chname	Change variable or coordinate name
chunit	Change variable unit
chlevel	Change level
chlevelc	Change level of one code
chlevelv	Change level of one variable
setgrid	Set grid
setgridtype	Set grid type
setgridarea	Set grid cell area
setgridmask	Set grid mask
setzaxis	Set z-axis
genlevelbounds	Generate level bounds
invertlat	Invert latitudes
invertlev	Invert levels
shiftx	Shift x
shifty	Shift y
maskregion	Mask regions

masklonlatbox	Mask a longitude/latitude box
maskindexbox	Mask an index box
setclonlatbox	Set a longitude/latitude box to constant
setcindexbox	Set an index box to constant
enlarge	Enlarge fields
setmissval	Set a new missing value
setctomiss	Set constant to missing value
setmisstoc	Set missing value to constant
setrtomiss	Set range to missing value
setvrange	Set valid range
setmisstomn	Set missing value to nearest neighbor
setmisstodis	Set missing value to distance-weighted average
setgridcell	Set the value of a grid cell

2.6.1. SETATTRIBUTE - Set attributes

Synopsis

```
setattribute,attributes infile outfile
```

Description

This operator sets attributes of a dataset and writes the result to outfile. The new attributes are only available in outfile if the file format supports attributes.

Each attribute has the following structure:

```
[var_nm@]att_nm[:s|d|i]=[att_val]{{[var_nm@]att_nm}}
```

var_nm Variable name (optional). Example: pressure

att_nm Attribute name. Example: units

att_val Comma-separated list of attribute values. Example: pascal

The value of **var_nm** is the name of the variable containing the attribute (named **att_nm**) that you want to set. Use wildcards to set the attribute **att_nm** to more than one variable. A value of **var_nm** of '*' will set the attribute **att_nm** to all data variables. If **var_nm** is missing then **att_nm** refers to a global attribute.

The value of **att_nm** is the name of the attribute you want to set. For each attribute a string (att_nm:s), a double (att_nm:d) or an integer (att_nm:i) type can be defined. By default the native type is set.

The value of **att_val** is the contents of the attribute **att_nm**. **att_val** may be a single value or one-dimensional array of elements. The type and the number of elements of an attribute will be detected automatically from the contents of the values. An already existing attribute **att_nm** will be overwritten or it will be removed if **att_val** is omitted. Alternatively, the values of an existing attribute can be copied. This attribute must then be enclosed in curly brackets.

A special meaning has the attribute name **FILE**. If this is the 1st attribute then all attributes are read from a file specified in the value of **att_val**.

Parameter

attributes STRING Comma-separated list of attributes.

Note

Attributes are evaluated by **CDO** when opening infile. Therefore the result of this operator is not available for other operators when this operator is used in chaining operators.

Example

To set the units of the variable pressure to pascal use:

```
cdo setattribute,pressure@units=pascal infile outfile
```

To set the global text attribute "my_att" to "my contents", use:

```
cdo setattribute,my_att="my contents" infile outfile
```

Result of 'ncdump -h outfile':

```
netcdf outfile {  
dimensions: ...  
  
variables: ...  
  
// global attributes:  
           :my_att = "my contents" ;  
}
```

2.6.2. SETPARTAB - Set parameter table

Synopsis

```
<operator>,<table[,convert] infile outfile
```

Description

This module transforms data and metadata of infile via a parameter table and writes the result to outfile. A parameter table is an ASCII formatted file with a set of parameter entries for each variable. Each new set have to start with "¶meter" and to end with "/".

The following parameter table entries are supported:

Entry	Type	Description
name	WORD	Name of the variable
out_name	WORD	New name of the variable
param	WORD	Parameter identifier (GRIB1: code[.tabnum]; GRIB2: num[.cat[.dis]])
out_param	WORD	New parameter identifier
type	WORD	Data type (real or double)
standard_name	WORD	As defined in the CF standard name table
long_name	STRING	Describing the variable
units	STRING	Specifying the units for the variable
comment	STRING	Information concerning the variable
cell_methods	STRING	Information concerning calculation of means or climatologies
cell_measures	STRING	Indicates the names of the variables containing cell areas and volumes
missing_value	FLOAT	Specifying how missing data will be identified
valid_min	FLOAT	Minimum valid value
valid_max	FLOAT	Maximum valid value
ok_min_mean_abs	FLOAT	Minimum absolute mean
ok_max_mean_abs	FLOAT	Maximum absolute mean
factor	FLOAT	Scale factor
delete	INTEGER	Set to 1 to delete variable
convert	INTEGER	Set to 1 to convert the unit if necessary

Unsupported parameter table entries are stored as variable attributes. The search key for the variable depends on the operator. Use [setpartabn](#) to search variables by the name. This is typically used for NetCDF datasets. The operator [setpartabp](#) searches variables by the parameter ID.

Operators

setpartabp Set parameter table
Search variables by the parameter identifier.

setpartabn Set parameter table
Search variables by name.

Parameter

table STRING Parameter table file or name
convert STRING Converts the units if necessary

Example

Here is an example of a parameter table for one variable:

```
prompt> cat mypartab
&parameter
  name          = t
  out_name      = ta
  standard_name = air_temperature
  units         = "K"
  missing_value = 1.0e+20
  valid_min     = 157.1
  valid_max     = 336.3
/
```

To apply this parameter table to a dataset use:

```
cdo setpartabn,mypartab,convert infile outfile
```

This command renames the variable **t** to **ta**. The standard name of this variable is set to **air_temperature** and the unit is set to **[K]** (converts the unit if necessary). The missing value will be set to **1.0e+20**. In addition it will be checked whether the values of the variable are in the range of **157.1** to **336.3**.

2.6.3. SET - Set field info

Synopsis

```

setcodetab,table infile outfile
setcode,code infile outfile
setparam,param infile outfile
setname,name infile outfile
setunit,unit infile outfile
setlevel,level infile outfile
setltype,ltype infile outfile

```

Description

This module sets some field information. Depending on the chosen operator the parameter table, code number, parameter identifier, variable name or level is set.

Operators

setcodetab	Set parameter code table Sets the parameter code table for all variables.
setcode	Set code number Sets the code number for all variables to the same given value.
setparam	Set parameter identifier Sets the parameter identifier of the first variable.
setname	Set variable name Sets the name of the first variable.
setunit	Set variable unit Sets the unit of the first variable.
setlevel	Set level Sets the first level of all variables.
setltype	Set GRIB level type Sets the GRIB level type of all variables.

Parameter

<i>table</i>	STRING	Parameter table file or name
<i>code</i>	INTEGER	Code number
<i>param</i>	STRING	Parameter identifier (GRIB1: code[.tabnum]; GRIB2: num[.cat[.dis]])
<i>name</i>	STRING	Variable name
<i>level</i>	FLOAT	New level
<i>ltype</i>	INTEGER	GRIB level type

2.6.4. SETTIME - Set time

Synopsis

```

setdate,date infile outfile
settime,time infile outfile
setday,day infile outfile
setmon,month infile outfile
setyear,year infile outfile
settunits,units infile outfile
settaxis,date,time[,inc] infile outfile
settbounds,frequency infile outfile
setreftime,date,time[,units] infile outfile
setcalendar,calendar infile outfile
shifttime,sval infile outfile

```

Description

This module sets the time axis or part of the time axis. Which part of the time axis is overwritten/created depends on the chosen operator.

Operators

setdate	Set date Sets the date in every timestep to the same given value.
settime	Set time of the day Sets the time in every timestep to the same given value.
setday	Set day Sets the day in every timestep to the same given value.
setmon	Set month Sets the month in every timestep to the same given value.
setyear	Set year Sets the year in every timestep to the same given value.
settunits	Set time units Sets the base units of a relative time axis.
settaxis	Set time axis Sets the time axis.
settbounds	Set time bounds Sets the time bounds.
setreftime	Set reference time Sets the reference time of a relative time axis.
setcalendar	Set calendar Sets the calendar of a relative time axis.
shifttime	Shift timesteps Shifts all timesteps by the parameter sval.

Parameter

<i>day</i>	INTEGER	Value of the new day
<i>month</i>	INTEGER	Value of the new month
<i>year</i>	INTEGER	Value of the new year
<i>units</i>	STRING	Base units of the time axis (seconds, minutes, hours, days, months, years)
<i>date</i>	STRING	Date (format: YYYY-MM-DD)
<i>time</i>	STRING	Time (format: hh:mm:ss)
<i>inc</i>	STRING	Optional increment (seconds, minutes, hours, days, months, years) [default: 1hour]
<i>frequency</i>	STRING	Frequency of the time series (hour, day, month, year)
<i>calendar</i>	STRING	Calendar (standard, proleptic_gregorian, 360_day, 365_day, 366_day)
<i>sval</i>	STRING	Shift value (e.g. -3hour)

Example

To set the time axis to 1987-01-16 12:00:00 with an increment of one month for each timestep use:

```
cdo settaxis,1987-01-16,12:00:00,1mon infile outfile
```

Result of 'cdo showdate outfile' for a dataset with 12 timesteps:

```
1987-01-16 1987-02-16 1987-03-16 1987-04-16 1987-05-16 1987-06-16 \
1987-07-16 1987-08-16 1987-09-16 1987-10-16 1987-11-16 1987-12-16
```

To shift this time axis by -15 days use:

```
cdo shifttime,-15days infile outfile
```

Result of 'cdo showdate outfile':

```
1987-01-01 1987-02-01 1987-03-01 1987-04-01 1987-05-01 1987-06-01 \
1987-07-01 1987-08-01 1987-09-01 1987-10-01 1987-11-01 1987-12-01
```

2.6.5. CHANGE - Change field header

Synopsis

```

chcode,oldcode,newcode[,...] infile outfile
chparam,oldparam,newparam,... infile outfile
chname,oldname,newname,... infile outfile
chunit,oldunit,newunit,... infile outfile
chlevel,oldlev,newlev,... infile outfile
chlevelc,code,oldlev,newlev infile outfile
chlevelv,name,oldlev,newlev infile outfile

```

Description

This module reads fields from *infile*, changes some header values and writes the results to *outfile*. The kind of changes depends on the chosen operator.

Operators

chcode	Change code number Changes some user given code numbers to new user given values.
chparam	Change parameter identifier Changes some user given parameter identifiers to new user given values.
chname	Change variable or coordinate name Changes some user given variable or coordinate names to new user given names.
chunit	Change variable unit Changes some user given variable units to new user given units.
chlevel	Change level Changes some user given levels to new user given values.
chlevelc	Change level of one code Changes one level of a user given code number.
chlevelv	Change level of one variable Changes one level of a user given variable name.

Parameter

<i>code</i>	INTEGER	Code number
<i>oldcode</i> , <i>newcode</i> ,...	INTEGER	Pairs of old and new code numbers
<i>oldparam</i> , <i>newparam</i> ,...	STRING	Pairs of old and new parameter identifiers
<i>name</i>	STRING	Variable name
<i>oldname</i> , <i>newname</i> ,...	STRING	Pairs of old and new variable names
<i>oldlev</i>	FLOAT	Old level
<i>newlev</i>	FLOAT	New level
<i>oldlev</i> , <i>newlev</i> ,...	FLOAT	Pairs of old and new levels

Example

To change the code number 98 to 179 and 99 to 211 use:

```
cdo chcode,98,179,99,211 infile outfile
```

2.6.6. SETGRID - Set grid information

Synopsis

```

setgrid,grid infile outfile
setgridtype,gridtype infile outfile
setgridarea,gridarea infile outfile
setgridmask,gridmask infile outfile

```

Description

This module modifies the metadata of the horizontal grid. Depending on the chosen operator a new grid description is set, the coordinates are converted or the grid cell area is added.

Operators

setgrid	Set grid Sets a new grid description. The input fields need to have the same grid size as the size of the target grid description.
setgridtype	Set grid type Sets the grid type of all input fields. The following grid types are available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> curvilinear Converts a regular grid to a curvilinear grid unstructured Converts a regular or curvilinear grid to an unstructured grid dereference Dereference a reference to a grid regular Linear interpolation of a reduced Gaussian grid to a regular Gaussian grid regularnn Nearest neighbor interpolation of a reduced Gaussian grid to a regular Gaussian grid lonlat Converts a regular lonlat grid stored as a curvilinear grid back to a lonlat grid
setgridarea	Set grid cell area Sets the grid cell area. The parameter <i>gridarea</i> is the path to a data file, the first field is used as grid cell area. The input fields need to have the same grid size as the grid cell area. The grid cell area is used to compute the weights of each grid cell if needed by an operator, e.g. for fldmean .
setgridmask	Set grid mask Sets the grid mask. The parameter <i>gridmask</i> is the path to a data file, the first field is used as the grid mask. The input fields need to have the same grid size as the grid mask. The grid mask is used as the target grid mask for remapping, e.g. for remapbil .

Parameter

<i>grid</i>	STRING	Grid description file or name
<i>gridtype</i>	STRING	Grid type (curvilinear, unstructured, regular, lonlat or dereference)
<i>gridarea</i>	STRING	Data file, the first field is used as grid cell area
<i>gridmask</i>	STRING	Data file, the first field is used as grid mask

Example

Assuming a dataset has fields on a grid with 2048 elements without or with wrong grid description. To set the grid description of all input fields to a Gaussian N32 grid (8192 gridpoints) use:

```
cdo setgrid,n32 infile outfile
```

2.6.7. SETZAXIS - Set z-axis information

Synopsis

```
setzaxis,zaxis infile outfile  
genlevelbounds[,zbot[,ztop]] infile outfile
```

Description

This module modifies the metadata of the vertical grid.

Operators

setzaxis	Set z-axis This operator sets the z-axis description of all variables with the same number of level as the new z-axis.
genlevelbounds	Generate level bounds Generates the layer bounds of the z-axis.

Parameter

<i>zaxis</i>	STRING	Z-axis description file or name of the target z-axis
<i>zbot</i>	FLOAT z-axis.	Specifying the bottom of the vertical column. Must have the same units as z-axis.
<i>ztop</i>	FLOAT	Specifying the top of the vertical column. Must have the same units as z-axis.

2.6.8. INVERT - Invert latitudes

Synopsis

```
invertlat infile outfile
```

Description

This operator inverts the latitudes of all fields on a rectilinear grid.

Example

To invert the latitudes of a 2D field from N->S to S->N use:

```
cdo invertlat infile outfile
```

2.6.9. INVERTLEV - Invert levels

Synopsis

```
invertlev infile outfile
```

Description

This operator inverts the levels of all 3D variables.

2.6.10. SHIFTTY - Shift field

Synopsis

```
<operator>,<nshift>,<cyclic>,<coord> infile outfile
```

Description

This module contains operators to shift all fields in x or y direction. All fields need to have the same horizontal rectilinear or curvilinear grid.

Operators

shiftx	Shift x Shifts all fields in x direction.
shifty	Shift y Shifts all fields in y direction.

Parameter

<i>nshift</i>	INTEGER	Number of grid cells to shift (default: 1)
<i>cyclic</i>	STRING	If set, cells are filled up cyclic (default: missing value)
<i>coord</i>	STRING	If set, coordinates are also shifted

Example

To shift all input fields in the x direction by +1 cells and fill the new cells with missing value, use:

```
cdo shiftx infile outfile
```

To shift all input fields in the x direction by +1 cells and fill the new cells cyclic, use:

```
cdo shiftx,1,cyclic infile outfile
```

2.6.11. MASKREGION - Mask regions

Synopsis

```
maskregion,regions infile outfile
```

Description

Masks different regions of fields with a regular lon/lat grid. The elements inside a region are untouched, the elements outside are set to missing value. Considered are only those grid cells with the grid center inside the regions. All input fields must have the same horizontal grid. The user has to give ASCII formatted files with different regions. A region is defined by a polygon. Each line of a polygon description file contains the longitude and latitude of one point. Each polygon description file can contain one or more polygons separated by a line with the character &.

Parameter

regions STRING Comma-separated list of ASCII formatted files with different regions

Example

To mask the region with the longitudes from 120E to 90W and latitudes from 20N to 20S on all input fields use:

```
cdo maskregion,myregion infile outfile
```

For this example the polygon description file *myregion* should contain the following four coordinates:

```
120 20
120 -20
270 -20
270 20
```

2.6.12. MASKBOX - Mask a box

Synopsis

```
masklonlatbox,lon1,lon2,lat1,lat2 infile outfile
```

```
maskindexbox,idx1,idx2,idy1,idy2 infile outfile
```

Description

Masked a box of the rectangularly understood field. The elements inside the box are untouched, the elements outside are set to missing value. All input fields need to have the same horizontal grid. Use [selionlatbox](#) or [selindexbox](#) if only the data inside the box are needed.

Operators

masklonlatbox	Mask a longitude/latitude box Masked a regular longitude/latitude box. The user has to give the longitudes and latitudes of the edges of the box. Considered are only those grid cells with the grid center inside the lon/lat box.
maskindexbox	Mask an index box Masked an index box. The user has to give the indices of the edges of the box. The index of the left edge can be greater then the one of the right edge.

Parameter

<i>lon1</i>	FLOAT	Western longitude
<i>lon2</i>	FLOAT	Eastern longitude
<i>lat1</i>	FLOAT	Southern or northern latitude
<i>lat2</i>	FLOAT	Northern or southern latitude
<i>idx1</i>	INTEGER	Index of first longitude
<i>idx2</i>	INTEGER	Index of last longitude
<i>idy1</i>	INTEGER	Index of first latitude
<i>idy2</i>	INTEGER	Index of last latitude

Example

To mask the region with the longitudes from 120E to 90W and latitudes from 20N to 20S on all input fields use:

```
cdo masklonlatbox,120,-90,20,-20 infile outfile
```

If the input dataset has fields on a Gaussian N16 grid, the same box can be masked with [maskindexbox](#) by:

```
cdo maskindexbox,23,48,13,20 infile outfile
```

2.6.13. SETBOX - Set a box to constant

Synopsis

```
setclonlatbox,c,lon1,lon2,lat1,lat2 infile outfile
setcindexbox,c,idx1,idx2,idy1,idy2 infile outfile
```

Description

Sets a box of the rectangularly understood field to a constant value. The elements outside the box are untouched, the elements inside are set to the given constant. All input fields need to have the same horizontal grid.

Operators

setclonlatbox	Set a longitude/latitude box to constant Sets the values of a longitude/latitude box to a constant value. The user has to give the longitudes and latitudes of the edges of the box.
setcindexbox	Set an index box to constant Sets the values of an index box to a constant value. The user has to give the indices of the edges of the box. The index of the left edge can be greater than the one of the right edge.

Parameter

<i>c</i>	FLOAT	Constant
<i>lon1</i>	FLOAT	Western longitude
<i>lon2</i>	FLOAT	Eastern longitude
<i>lat1</i>	FLOAT	Southern or northern latitude
<i>lat2</i>	FLOAT	Northern or southern latitude
<i>idx1</i>	INTEGER	Index of first longitude
<i>idx2</i>	INTEGER	Index of last longitude
<i>idy1</i>	INTEGER	Index of first latitude
<i>idy2</i>	INTEGER	Index of last latitude

Example

To set all values in the region with the longitudes from 120E to 90W and latitudes from 20N to 20S to the constant value -1.23 use:

```
cdo setclonlatbox,-1.23,120,-90,20,-20 infile outfile
```

If the input dataset has fields on a Gaussian N16 grid, the same box can be set with [setcindexbox](#) by:

```
cdo setcindexbox,-1.23,23,48,13,20 infile outfile
```

2.6.14. ENLARGE - Enlarge fields

Synopsis

```
enlarge,grid infile outfile
```

Description

Enlarge all fields of *infile* to a user given horizontal grid. Normally only the last field element is used for the enlargement. If however the input and output grid are regular lon/lat grids, a zonal or meridional enlargement is possible. Zonal enlargement takes place, if the *xsize* of the input field is 1 and the *ysize* of both grids are the same. For meridional enlargement the *ysize* have to be 1 and the *xsize* of both grids should have the same size.

Parameter

grid STRING Target grid description file or name

Example

Assumed you want to add two datasets. The first dataset is a field on a global grid (*n* field elements) and the second dataset is a global mean (1 field element). Before you can add these two datasets the second dataset have to be enlarged to the grid size of the first dataset:

```
cdo enlarge,infile1 infile2 tmpfile
cdo add infile1 tmpfile outfile
```

Or shorter using operator piping:

```
cdo add infile1 -enlarge,infile1 infile2 outfile
```

2.6.15. SETMISS - Set missing value

Synopsis

```

setmissval,newmiss infile outfile
setctomiss,c infile outfile
setmisstoc,c infile outfile
setrtomiss,rmin,rmax infile outfile
setvrange,rmin,rmax infile outfile
setmisstonn infile outfile
setmisstodis[,neighbors] infile outfile

```

Description

This module sets part of a field to missing value or missing values to a constant value. Which part of the field is set depends on the chosen operator.

Operators

setmissval	Set a new missing value
	$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} \text{newmiss} & \text{if } i(t, x) = \text{miss} \\ i(t, x) & \text{if } i(t, x) \neq \text{miss} \end{cases}$
setctomiss	Set constant to missing value
	$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} \text{miss} & \text{if } i(t, x) = c \\ i(t, x) & \text{if } i(t, x) \neq c \end{cases}$
setmisstoc	Set missing value to constant
	$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} c & \text{if } i(t, x) = \text{miss} \\ i(t, x) & \text{if } i(t, x) \neq \text{miss} \end{cases}$
setrtomiss	Set range to missing value
	$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} \text{miss} & \text{if } i(t, x) \geq rmin \wedge i(t, x) \leq rmax \\ i(t, x) & \text{if } i(t, x) < rmin \vee i(t, x) > rmax \end{cases}$
setvrange	Set valid range
	$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} \text{miss} & \text{if } i(t, x) < rmin \vee i(t, x) > rmax \\ i(t, x) & \text{if } i(t, x) \geq rmin \wedge i(t, x) \leq rmax \end{cases}$
setmisstonn	Set missing value to nearest neighbor
	Set all missing values to the nearest non missing value.
	$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} i(t, y) & \text{if } i(t, x) = \text{miss} \wedge i(t, y) \neq \text{miss} \\ i(t, x) & \text{if } i(t, x) \neq \text{miss} \end{cases}$
setmisstodis	Set missing value to distance-weighted average
	Set all missing values to the distance-weighted average of the nearest non missing values. The default number of nearest neighbors is 4.

Parameter

<i>neighbors</i>	INTEGER	Number of nearest neighbors
<i>newmiss</i>	FLOAT	New missing value
<i>c</i>	FLOAT	Constant
<i>rmin</i>	FLOAT	Lower bound
<i>rmax</i>	FLOAT	Upper bound

Example

setrtomiss

Assume an input dataset has one field with temperatures in the range from 246 to 304 Kelvin. To set all values below 273.15 Kelvin to missing value use:

```
cdo setrtomiss,0,273.15 infile outfile
```

Result of 'cdo info infile':

-1 :	Date	Time	Code	Level	Size	Miss :	Minimum	Mean	Maximum
1 :	1987-12-31	12:00:00	139	0	2048	0 :	246.27	276.75	303.71

Result of 'cdo info outfile':

-1 :	Date	Time	Code	Level	Size	Miss :	Minimum	Mean	Maximum
1 :	1987-12-31	12:00:00	139	0	2048	871 :	273.16	287.08	303.71

setmisstonn

Set all missing values to the nearest non missing value:

```
cdo setmisstonn infile outfile
```

Below is a schematic illustration of this example:

On the left side is input data with missing values in grey and on the right side the result with the filled missing values.

2.6.16. SETGRIDCELL - Set the value of a grid cell

Synopsis

```
setgridcell,params infile outfile
```

Description

This operator sets the value of the selected grid cells. The grid cells can be selected by a comma-separated list of grid cell indices or a mask. The mask is read from a data file, which may contain only one field. If no grid cells are selected, all values are set.

Parameter

<i>value</i>	FLOAT	Value of the grid cell
<i>cell</i>	INTEGER	Comma-separated list of grid cell indices
<i>mask</i>	STRING	Name of the data file which contains the mask

2.7. Arithmetic

This section contains modules to arithmetically process datasets.

Here is a short overview of all operators in this section:

expr	Evaluate expressions
exprf	Evaluate expressions script
aexpr	Evaluate expressions and append results
aexprf	Evaluate expression script and append results
abs	Absolute value
int	Integer value
nint	Nearest integer value
pow	Power
sqr	Square
sqrt	Square root
exp	Exponential
ln	Natural logarithm
log10	Base 10 logarithm
sin	Sine
cos	Cosine
tan	Tangent
asin	Arc sine
acos	Arc cosine
atan	Arc tangent
reci	Reciprocal value
not	Logical NOT
addc	Add a constant
subc	Subtract a constant
mulc	Multiply with a constant
divc	Divide by a constant
minc	Minimum of a field and a constant
maxc	Maximum of a field and a constant
add	Add two fields
sub	Subtract two fields
mul	Multiply two fields
div	Divide two fields
min	Minimum of two fields
max	Maximum of two fields
atan2	Arc tangent of two fields
monadd	Add monthly time series
monsub	Subtract monthly time series
monmul	Multiply monthly time series
mondiv	Divide monthly time series
yearadd	Add yearly time series
yearsub	Subtract yearly time series
yearmul	Multiply yearly time series
yeardiv	Divide yearly time series

yhouradd	Add multi-year hourly time series
yhoursub	Subtract multi-year hourly time series
yhourmul	Multiply multi-year hourly time series
yhourdiv	Divide multi-year hourly time series
ydayadd	Add multi-year daily time series
ydaysub	Subtract multi-year daily time series
ydaymul	Multiply multi-year daily time series
ydaydiv	Divide multi-year daily time series
ymonadd	Add multi-year monthly time series
ymonsub	Subtract multi-year monthly time series
ymonmul	Multiply multi-year monthly time series
ymonddiv	Divide multi-year monthly time series
yseasadd	Add multi-year seasonal time series
yseasub	Subtract multi-year seasonal time series
yseasmul	Multiply multi-year seasonal time series
yseasdiv	Divide multi-year seasonal time series
muldpm	Multiply with days per month
divdpm	Divide by days per month
muldpy	Multiply with days per year
divdpy	Divide by days per year
mulcoslat	Multiply with the cosine of the latitude
divcoslat	Divide by cosine of the latitude

2.7.1. EXPR - Evaluate expressions

Synopsis

`expr, instr infile outfile`

`exprf, filename infile outfile`

`aexpr, instr infile outfile`

`aexprf, filename infile outfile`

Description

This module arithmetically processes every timestep of the input dataset. Each individual assignment statement have to end with a semi-colon. Unlike regular variables, temporary variables are never written to the output stream. To define a temporary variable simply prefix the variable name with an underscore (e.g. `_varname`) when the variable is declared.

The following operators are supported:

Operator	Meaning	Example	Result
<code>=</code>	assignment	<code>x = y</code>	Assigns y to x
<code>+</code>	addition	<code>x + y</code>	Sum of x and y
<code>-</code>	subtraction	<code>x - y</code>	Difference of x and y
<code>*</code>	multiplication	<code>x * y</code>	Product of x and y
<code>/</code>	division	<code>x / y</code>	Quotient of x and y
<code>^</code>	exponentiation	<code>x ^ y</code>	Exponentiates x with y
<code>==</code>	equal to	<code>x == y</code>	1, if x equal to y; else 0
<code>!=</code>	not equal to	<code>x != y</code>	1, if x not equal to y; else 0
<code>></code>	greater than	<code>x > y</code>	1, if x greater than y; else 0
<code><</code>	less than	<code>x < y</code>	1, if x less than y; else 0
<code>>=</code>	greater equal	<code>x >= y</code>	1, if x greater equal y; else 0
<code><=</code>	less equal	<code>x <= y</code>	1, if x less equal y; else 0
<code><=></code>	less equal greater	<code>x <=> y</code>	-1, if x less y; 1, if x greater y; else 0
<code>&&</code>	logical AND	<code>x && y</code>	1, if x and y not equal 0; else 0
<code> </code>	logical OR	<code>x y</code>	1, if x or y not equal 0; else 0
<code>!</code>	logical NOT	<code>!x</code>	1, if x equal 0; else 0
<code>?:</code>	ternary conditional	<code>x ? y : z</code>	y, if x not equal 0, else z

The following functions are supported:

Math intrinsics:

<code>abs(x)</code>	Absolute value of x
<code>floor(x)</code>	Round to largest integral value not greater than x
<code>ceil(x)</code>	Round to smallest integral value not less than x
<code>float(x)</code>	32-bit float value of x
<code>int(x)</code>	Integer value of x
<code>nint(x)</code>	Nearest integer value of x
<code>sqr(x)</code>	Square of x
<code>sqrt(x)</code>	Square Root of x
<code>exp(x)</code>	Exponential of x

<code>ln(x)</code>	Natural logarithm of x
<code>log10(x)</code>	Base 10 logarithm of x
<code>sin(x)</code>	Sine of x, where x is specified in radians
<code>cos(x)</code>	Cosine of x, where x is specified in radians
<code>tan(x)</code>	Tangent of x, where x is specified in radians
<code>asin(x)</code>	Arc-sine of x, where x is specified in radians
<code>acos(x)</code>	Arc-cosine of x, where x is specified in radians
<code>atan(x)</code>	Arc-tangent of x, where x is specified in radians
<code>rad(x)</code>	Convert x from degrees to radians
<code>deg(x)</code>	Convert x from radians to degrees
<code>rand(x)</code>	Replace x by pseudo-random numbers in the range of 0 to 1
<code>isMissval(x)</code>	Returns 1 where x is missing
Coordinates:	
<code>clon(x)</code>	Longitude coordinate of x (available only if x has geographical coordinates)
<code>clat(x)</code>	Latitude coordinate of x (available only if x has geographical coordinates)
<code>gridarea(x)</code>	Grid cell area of x (available only if x has geographical coordinates)
<code>clev(x)</code>	Level coordinate of x (0, if x is a 2D surface variable)
<code>cdeltaz(x)</code>	Upper minus lower level bound of x (1, if level bounds are missing)
<code>ctimestep()</code>	Timestep number (1 to N)
<code>cdate()</code>	Verification date as YYYYMMDD
<code>ctime()</code>	Verification time as HHMMSS.millisecond
<code>cdeltat()</code>	Difference between current and last timestep in seconds
<code>cday()</code>	Day as DD
<code>cmonth()</code>	Month as MM
<code>cyear()</code>	Year as YYYY
<code>csecond()</code>	Second as SS.millisecond
<code>cminute()</code>	Minute as MM
<code>chour()</code>	Hour as HH
Constants:	
<code>ngp(x)</code>	Number of horizontal grid points
<code>nlev(x)</code>	Number of vertical levels
<code>size(x)</code>	Total number of elements (<code>ngp(x)*nlev(x)</code>)
<code>missval(x)</code>	Returns the missing value of variable x
Statistical values over a field:	
<code>fldmin(x)</code> , <code>fldmax(x)</code> , <code>fldsum(x)</code> , <code>fldmean(x)</code> , <code>fldavg(x)</code> , <code>fldstd(x)</code> , <code>fldstd1(x)</code> , <code>fldvar(x)</code> , <code>fldvar1(x)</code>	
Zonal statistical values for regular 2D grids:	
<code>zonmin(x)</code> , <code>zonmax(x)</code> , <code>zonsum(x)</code> , <code>zonmean(x)</code> , <code>zonavg(x)</code> , <code>zonstd(x)</code> , <code>zonstd1(x)</code> , <code>zonvar(x)</code> , <code>zonvar1(x)</code>	
Vertical statistical values:	
<code>vertmin(x)</code> , <code>vertmax(x)</code> , <code>vertsum(x)</code> , <code>vertmean(x)</code> , <code>vertavg(x)</code> , <code>vertstd(x)</code> , <code>vertstd1(x)</code> , <code>vertvar(x)</code> , <code>vertvar1(x)</code>	
Miscellaneous:	

<code>sellevel(x,k)</code>	Select level k of variable x
<code>sellevidx(x,k)</code>	Select level index k of variable x
<code>sellevelrange(x,k1,k2)</code>	Select all levels of variable x in the range k1 to k2
<code>sellevidxrange(x,k1,k2)</code>	Select all level indices of variable x in the range k1 to k2
<code>remove(x)</code>	Remove variable x from output stream

Operators

expr	Evaluate expressions The processing instructions are read from the parameter.
exprf	Evaluate expressions script Contrary to expr the processing instructions are read from a file.
aexpr	Evaluate expressions and append results Same as expr , but keep input variables and append results
aexprf	Evaluate expression script and append results Same as exprf , but keep input variables and append results

Parameter

<i>instr</i>	STRING	Processing instructions (need to be 'quoted' in most cases)
<i>filename</i>	STRING	File with processing instructions

Note

The `expr` commands `sellevel(x,k)` and `sellevidx(x,k)` are only available with [exprf/aexprf](#). If the input stream contains duplicate entries of the same variable name then the last one is used.

Example

Assume an input dataset contains at least the variables 'aprl', 'aprc' and 'ts'. To create a new variable 'var1' with the sum of 'aprl' and 'aprc' and a variable 'var2' which convert the temperature 'ts' from Kelvin to Celsius use:

```
cdo expr,'var1=aprl+aprc;var2=ts-273.15;' infile outfile
```

The same example, but the instructions are read from a file:

```
cdo exprf,myexpr infile outfile
```

The file `myexpr` contains:

```
var1 = aprl + aprc;
var2 = ts - 273.15;
```

2.7.2. MATH - Mathematical functions

Synopsis

`<operator> infile outfile`

Description

This module contains some standard mathematical functions. All trigonometric functions calculate with radians.

Operators

abs	Absolute value $o(t, x) = \text{abs}(i(t, x))$
int	Integer value $o(t, x) = \text{int}(i(t, x))$
nint	Nearest integer value $o(t, x) = \text{nint}(i(t, x))$
pow	Power $o(t, x) = i(t, x)^y$
sqr	Square $o(t, x) = i(t, x)^2$
sqrt	Square root $o(t, x) = \sqrt{i(t, x)}$
exp	Exponential $o(t, x) = e^{i(t, x)}$
ln	Natural logarithm $o(t, x) = \ln(i(t, x))$
log10	Base 10 logarithm $o(t, x) = \log_{10}(i(t, x))$
sin	Sine $o(t, x) = \sin(i(t, x))$
cos	Cosine $o(t, x) = \cos(i(t, x))$
tan	Tangent $o(t, x) = \tan(i(t, x))$
asin	Arc sine $o(t, x) = \arcsin(i(t, x))$
acos	Arc cosine $o(t, x) = \arccos(i(t, x))$
atan	Arc tangent $o(t, x) = \arctan(i(t, x))$
reci	Reciprocal value $o(t, x) = 1/i(t, x)$
not	Logical NOT $o(t, x) = 1, \text{if } x \text{ equal } 0; \text{ else } 0$

Example

To calculate the square root for all field elements use:

```
cdo sqrt infile outfile
```

2.7.3. ARITHC - Arithmetic with a constant

Synopsis

```
<operator>,c infile outfile
```

Description

This module performs simple arithmetic with all field elements of a dataset and a constant. The fields in outfile inherit the meta data from infile.

Operators

addc	Add a constant $o(t, x) = i(t, x) + c$
subc	Subtract a constant $o(t, x) = i(t, x) - c$
mulc	Multiply with a constant $o(t, x) = i(t, x) * c$
divc	Divide by a constant $o(t, x) = i(t, x) / c$
minc	Minimum of a field and a constant $o(t, x) = \min(i(t, x), c)$
maxc	Maximum of a field and a constant $o(t, x) = \max(i(t, x), c)$

Parameter

c FLOAT Constant

Example

To sum all input fields with the constant -273.15 use:

```
cdo addc,-273.15 infile outfile
```

2.7.4. ARITH - Arithmetic on two datasets

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

This module performs simple arithmetic of two datasets. The number of fields in `infile1` should be the same as in `infile2`. The fields in `outfile` inherit the meta data from `infile1`. All operators in this module simply process one field after the other from the two input files. Neither the order of the variables nor the date is checked. One of the input files can contain only one timestep or one variable.

Operators

add	Add two fields $o(t, x) = i_1(t, x) + i_2(t, x)$
sub	Subtract two fields $o(t, x) = i_1(t, x) - i_2(t, x)$
mul	Multiply two fields $o(t, x) = i_1(t, x) * i_2(t, x)$
div	Divide two fields $o(t, x) = i_1(t, x) / i_2(t, x)$
min	Minimum of two fields $o(t, x) = \min(i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x))$
max	Maximum of two fields $o(t, x) = \max(i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x))$
atan2	Arc tangent of two fields The <code>atan2</code> operator calculates the arc tangent of two fields. The result is in radians, which is between -PI and PI (inclusive). $o(t, x) = \text{atan2}(i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x))$

Example

To sum all fields of the first input file with the corresponding fields of the second input file use:

```
cdo add infile1 infile2 outfile
```

2.7.5. MONARITH - Monthly arithmetic

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

This module performs simple arithmetic of a time series and one timestep with the same month and year. For each field in `infile1` the corresponding field of the timestep in `infile2` with the same month and year is used. The header information in `infile1` have to be the same as in `infile2`. Usually `infile2` is generated by an operator of the module [MONSTAT](#).

Operators

monadd	Add monthly time series Adds a time series and a monthly time series.
monsub	Subtract monthly time series Subtracts a time series and a monthly time series.
monmul	Multiply monthly time series Multiplies a time series and a monthly time series.
monddiv	Divide monthly time series Divides a time series and a monthly time series.

Example

To subtract a monthly time average from a time series use:

```
cdo monsub infile -monavg infile outfile
```

2.7.6. YEARARITH - Yearly arithmetic

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

This module performs simple arithmetic of a time series and one timestep with the same year. For each field in `infile1` the corresponding field of the timestep in `infile2` with the same year is used. The header information in `infile1` have to be the same as in `infile2`. Usually `infile2` is generated by an operator of the module [YEARSTAT](#).

Operators

yearadd	Add yearly time series Adds a time series and a yearly time series.
yearsab	Subtract yearly time series Subtracts a time series and a yearly time series.
yearmul	Multiply yearly time series Multiplies a time series and a yearly time series.
yeardiv	Divide yearly time series Divides a time series and a yearly time series.

Example

To subtract a yearly time average from a time series use:

```
cdo yearsub infile -yearavg infile outfile
```

2.7.7. YHOURARITH - Multi-year hourly arithmetic

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

This module performs simple arithmetic of a time series and one timestep with the same hour and day of year. For each field in `infile1` the corresponding field of the timestep in `infile2` with the same hour and day of year is used. The header information in `infile1` have to be the same as in `infile2`. Usually `infile2` is generated by an operator of the module [YHOURSTAT](#).

Operators

yhouradd	Add multi-year hourly time series Adds a time series and a multi-year hourly time series.
yhoursub	Subtract multi-year hourly time series Subtracts a time series and a multi-year hourly time series.
yhourmul	Multiply multi-year hourly time series Multiplies a time series and a multi-year hourly time series.
yhourdiv	Divide multi-year hourly time series Divides a time series and a multi-year hourly time series.

Example

To subtract a multi-year hourly time average from a time series use:

```
cdo yhoursub infile -yhouravg infile outfile
```

2.7.8. YDAYARITH - Multi-year daily arithmetic

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

This module performs simple arithmetic of a time series and one timestep with the same day of year. For each field in `infile1` the corresponding field of the timestep in `infile2` with the same day of year is used. The header information in `infile1` have to be the same as in `infile2`. Usually `infile2` is generated by an operator of the module [YDAYSTAT](#).

Operators

ydayadd	Add multi-year daily time series Adds a time series and a multi-year daily time series.
ydaysub	Subtract multi-year daily time series Subtracts a time series and a multi-year daily time series.
ydaymul	Multiply multi-year daily time series Multiplies a time series and a multi-year daily time series.
ydaydiv	Divide multi-year daily time series Divides a time series and a multi-year daily time series.

Example

To subtract a multi-year daily time average from a time series use:

```
cdo ydaysub infile -ydayavg infile outfile
```

2.7.9. YMONARITH - Multi-year monthly arithmetic

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

This module performs simple arithmetic of a time series and one timestep with the same month of year. For each field in `infile1` the corresponding field of the timestep in `infile2` with the same month of year is used. The header information in `infile1` have to be the same as in `infile2`. Usually `infile2` is generated by an operator of the module [YMONSTAT](#).

Operators

ymonadd	Add multi-year monthly time series Adds a time series and a multi-year monthly time series.
ymonsub	Subtract multi-year monthly time series Subtracts a time series and a multi-year monthly time series.
ymonmul	Multiply multi-year monthly time series Multiplies a time series and a multi-year monthly time series.
ymonddiv	Divide multi-year monthly time series Divides a time series and a multi-year monthly time series.

Example

To subtract a multi-year monthly time average from a time series use:

```
cdo ymonsub infile -ymonavg infile outfile
```

2.7.10. YSEASARITH - Multi-year seasonal arithmetic

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

This module performs simple arithmetic of a time series and one timestep with the same season. For each field in `infile1` the corresponding field of the timestep in `infile2` with the same season is used. The header information in `infile1` have to be the same as in `infile2`. Usually `infile2` is generated by an operator of the module [YSEASSTAT](#).

Operators

yseasadd	Add multi-year seasonal time series Adds a time series and a multi-year seasonal time series.
yseassub	Subtract multi-year seasonal time series Subtracts a time series and a multi-year seasonal time series.
yseasmul	Multiply multi-year seasonal time series Multiplies a time series and a multi-year seasonal time series.
yseasdiv	Divide multi-year seasonal time series Divides a time series and a multi-year seasonal time series.

Example

To subtract a multi-year seasonal time average from a time series use:

```
cdo yseassub infile -yseasavg infile outfile
```

2.7.11. ARITHDAYS - Arithmetic with days

Synopsis

`<operator> infile outfile`

Description

This module multiplies or divides each timestep of a dataset with the corresponding days per month or days per year. The result of these functions depends on the used calendar of the input data.

Operators

muldpm	Multiply with days per month $o(t, x) = i(t, x) * days_per_month$
divdpm	Divide by days per month $o(t, x) = i(t, x) / days_per_month$
muldpy	Multiply with days per year $o(t, x) = i(t, x) * days_per_year$
divdpy	Divide by days per year $o(t, x) = i(t, x) / days_per_year$

2.7.12. ARITHLAT - Arithmetic with latitude

Synopsis

`<operator> infile outfile`

Description

This module multiplies or divides each field element with the cosine of the latitude.

Operators

mulcoslat	Multiply with the cosine of the latitude $o(t, x) = i(t, x) * cos(latitude(x))$
divcoslat	Divide by cosine of the latitude $o(t, x) = i(t, x) / cos(latitude(x))$

2.8. Statistical values

This section contains modules to compute statistical values of datasets. In this program there is the different notion of "mean" and "average" to distinguish two different kinds of treatment of missing values. While computing the mean, only the not missing values are considered to belong to the sample with the side effect of a probably reduced sample size. Computing the average is just adding the sample members and divide the result by the sample size. For example, the mean of 1, 2, miss and 3 is $(1+2+3)/3 = 2$, whereas the average is $(1+2+miss+3)/4 = miss/4 = miss$. If there are no missing values in the sample, the average and the mean are identical.

CDO is using the verification time to identify the time range for temporal statistics. The time bounds are never used!

In this section the abbreviations as in the following table are used:

sum	$\sum_{i=1}^n x_i$
mean resp. avg \bar{x}	$n^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i$
mean resp. avg weighted by $\{w_i, i = 1, \dots, n\}$	$\left(\sum_{j=1}^n w_j \right)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i$
Variance var	$n^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2$
var1	$(n-1)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2$
var weighted by $\{w_i, i = 1, \dots, n\}$	$\left(\sum_{j=1}^n w_j \right)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \left(x_i - \left(\sum_{j=1}^n w_j \right)^{-1} \sum_{j=1}^n w_j x_j \right)^2$
Standard deviation std s	$\sqrt{n^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}$
std1	$\sqrt{(n-1)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}$
std weighted by $\{w_i, i = 1, \dots, n\}$	$\sqrt{\left(\sum_{j=1}^n w_j \right)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \left(x_i - \left(\sum_{j=1}^n w_j \right)^{-1} \sum_{j=1}^n w_j x_j \right)^2}$
median	$\begin{cases} x_{\frac{n+1}{2}} & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \\ \frac{1}{2} (x_{\frac{n}{2}} + x_{\frac{n}{2}+1}) & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \end{cases}$

Skewness skew	$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})/n}{s^3}$
Kurtosis kurt	$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^4/n}{s^4}$
Cumulative Ranked Probability Score crps	$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} [H(x_1) - \text{cdf}(\{x_2 \dots x_n\}) _r]^2 dr$

with $\text{cdf}(X)|_r$ being the cumulative distribution function of $\{x_i, i = 2 \dots n\}$ at r
and $H(x)$ the Heavyside function jumping at x .

Here is a short overview of all operators in this section:

timcumsum	Cumulative sum over all timesteps
consecsum	Consecutive Sum
consects	Consecutive Timesteps
varsmin	Variables minimum
varsmax	Variables maximum
varsrange	Variables range
varssum	Variables sum
varsmean	Variables mean
varsavg	Variables average
varsstd	Variables standard deviation
varsstd1	Variables standard deviation (n-1)
varsvar	Variables variance
varsvar1	Variables variance (n-1)
ensmin	Ensemble minimum
ensmax	Ensemble maximum
ensrange	Ensemble range
enssum	Ensemble sum
ensmean	Ensemble mean
ensavg	Ensemble average
ensstd	Ensemble standard deviation
ensstd1	Ensemble standard deviation (n-1)
ensvar	Ensemble variance
ensvar1	Ensemble variance (n-1)
ensskew	Ensemble skewness
enskurt	Ensemble kurtosis
ensmedian	Ensemble median
enspctl	Ensemble percentiles
ensrkhistspace	Ranked Histogram averaged over time
ensrkhisttime	Ranked Histogram averaged over space
ensroc	Ensemble Receiver Operating characteristics
enscrps	Ensemble CRPS and decomposition
ensbrs	Ensemble Brier score

fldmin	Field minimum
fldmax	Field maximum
fldrange	Field range
fldsum	Field sum
fldint	Field integral
fldmean	Field mean
fldavg	Field average
fldstd	Field standard deviation
fldstd1	Field standard deviation (n-1)
fldvar	Field variance
fldvar1	Field variance (n-1)
fldskew	Field skewness
fldkurt	Field kurtosis
fldmedian	Field median
fldpctl	Field percentiles
zonmin	Zonal minimum
zonmax	Zonal maximum
zonrange	Zonal range
zonsum	Zonal sum
zonmean	Zonal mean
zonavg	Zonal average
zonstd	Zonal standard deviation
zonstd1	Zonal standard deviation (n-1)
zonvar	Zonal variance
zonvar1	Zonal variance (n-1)
zonskew	Zonal skewness
zonkurt	Zonal kurtosis
zonmedian	Zonal median
zonpctl	Zonal percentiles
mermin	Meridional minimum
mermax	Meridional maximum
merrange	Meridional range
mersum	Meridional sum
mermean	Meridional mean
meravg	Meridional average
merstd	Meridional standard deviation
merstd1	Meridional standard deviation (n-1)
mervar	Meridional variance
mervar1	Meridional variance (n-1)
merskew	Meridional skewness
merkurt	Meridional kurtosis
mermedian	Meridional median
merpctl	Meridional percentiles

gridboxmin	Gridbox minimum
gridboxmax	Gridbox maximum
gridboxrange	Gridbox range
gridboxsum	Gridbox sum
gridboxmean	Gridbox mean
gridboxavg	Gridbox average
gridboxstd	Gridbox standard deviation
gridboxstd1	Gridbox standard deviation (n-1)
gridboxvar	Gridbox variance
gridboxvar1	Gridbox variance (n-1)
gridboxskew	Gridbox skewness
gridboxkurt	Gridbox kurtosis
gridboxmedian	Gridbox median
vertmin	Vertical minimum
vertmax	Vertical maximum
vertrange	Vertical range
vertsum	Vertical sum
vertmean	Vertical mean
vertavg	Vertical average
vertstd	Vertical standard deviation
vertstd1	Vertical standard deviation (n-1)
vertvar	Vertical variance
vertvar1	Vertical variance (n-1)
timselmin	Time selection minimum
timselmax	Time selection maximum
timselrange	Time selection range
timselsum	Time selection sum
timselmean	Time selection mean
timselavg	Time selection average
timselstd	Time selection standard deviation
timselstd1	Time selection standard deviation (n-1)
timselvar	Time selection variance
timselvar1	Time selection variance (n-1)
timselpctl	Time range percentiles
runmin	Running minimum
runmax	Running maximum
runrange	Running range
runsum	Running sum
runmean	Running mean
runavg	Running average
runstd	Running standard deviation
runstd1	Running standard deviation (n-1)
runvar	Running variance
runvar1	Running variance (n-1)
runpctl	Running percentiles

timmin	Time minimum
timmax	Time maximum
timrange	Time range
timsun	Time sum
timmean	Time mean
timavg	Time average
timstd	Time standard deviation
timstd1	Time standard deviation (n-1)
timvar	Time variance
timvar1	Time variance (n-1)
timepctl	Time percentiles
hourmin	Hourly minimum
hourmax	Hourly maximum
hourrange	Hourly range
hoursum	Hourly sum
hourmean	Hourly mean
houravg	Hourly average
hourstd	Hourly standard deviation
hourstd1	Hourly standard deviation (n-1)
hourvar	Hourly variance
hourvar1	Hourly variance (n-1)
hourpctl	Hourly percentiles
daymin	Daily minimum
daymax	Daily maximum
dayrange	Daily range
daysum	Daily sum
daymean	Daily mean
dayavg	Daily average
daystd	Daily standard deviation
daystd1	Daily standard deviation (n-1)
dayvar	Daily variance
dayvar1	Daily variance (n-1)
daypctl	Daily percentiles
monmin	Monthly minimum
monmax	Monthly maximum
monrange	Monthly range
monsum	Monthly sum
monmean	Monthly mean
monavg	Monthly average
monstd	Monthly standard deviation
monstd1	Monthly standard deviation (n-1)
monvar	Monthly variance
monvar1	Monthly variance (n-1)
monpctl	Monthly percentiles
yearmonmean	Yearly mean from monthly data

yearmin	Yearly minimum
yearmax	Yearly maximum
yearminidx	Yearly minimum indices
yearmaxidx	Yearly maximum indices
yearrange	Yearly range
yearsum	Yearly sum
yearmean	Yearly mean
yearavg	Yearly average
yearstd	Yearly standard deviation
yearstd1	Yearly standard deviation (n-1)
yearvar	Yearly variance
yearvar1	Yearly variance (n-1)
yearpctl	Yearly percentiles
seasmin	Seasonal minimum
seasmax	Seasonal maximum
seasrange	Seasonal range
seassum	Seasonal sum
seasmean	Seasonal mean
seasavg	Seasonal average
seasstd	Seasonal standard deviation
seasstd1	Seasonal standard deviation (n-1)
seasvar	Seasonal variance
seasvar1	Seasonal variance (n-1)
seaspctl	Seasonal percentiles
yhourmin	Multi-year hourly minimum
yhourmax	Multi-year hourly maximum
yhourrange	Multi-year hourly range
yhoursum	Multi-year hourly sum
yhourmean	Multi-year hourly mean
yhouravg	Multi-year hourly average
yhourstd	Multi-year hourly standard deviation
yhourstd1	Multi-year hourly standard deviation (n-1)
yhourvar	Multi-year hourly variance
yhourvar1	Multi-year hourly variance (n-1)
dhourmin	Multi-day hourly minimum
dhourmax	Multi-day hourly maximum
dhourrange	Multi-day hourly range
dhoursum	Multi-day hourly sum
dhourmean	Multi-day hourly mean
dhouravg	Multi-day hourly average
dhourstd	Multi-day hourly standard deviation
dhourstd1	Multi-day hourly standard deviation (n-1)
dhourvar	Multi-day hourly variance
dhourvar1	Multi-day hourly variance (n-1)

ydaymin	Multi-year daily minimum
ydaymax	Multi-year daily maximum
ydayrange	Multi-year daily range
ydaysum	Multi-year daily sum
ydaymean	Multi-year daily mean
ydayavg	Multi-year daily average
ydaystd	Multi-year daily standard deviation
ydaystd1	Multi-year daily standard deviation (n-1)
ydayvar	Multi-year daily variance
ydayvar1	Multi-year daily variance (n-1)
ydaypctl	Multi-year daily percentiles
ymonmin	Multi-year monthly minimum
ymonmax	Multi-year monthly maximum
ymonrange	Multi-year monthly range
ymonsum	Multi-year monthly sum
ymonmean	Multi-year monthly mean
ymonavg	Multi-year monthly average
ymonstd	Multi-year monthly standard deviation
ymonstd1	Multi-year monthly standard deviation (n-1)
ymonvar	Multi-year monthly variance
ymonvar1	Multi-year monthly variance (n-1)
ymonpctl	Multi-year monthly percentiles
yseasmin	Multi-year seasonal minimum
yseasmax	Multi-year seasonal maximum
yseasrange	Multi-year seasonal range
yseassum	Multi-year seasonal sum
yseasmean	Multi-year seasonal mean
yseasavg	Multi-year seasonal average
yseasstd	Multi-year seasonal standard deviation
yseasstd1	Multi-year seasonal standard deviation (n-1)
yseasvar	Multi-year seasonal variance
yseasvar1	Multi-year seasonal variance (n-1)
yseaspctl	Multi-year seasonal percentiles
ydrunmin	Multi-year daily running minimum
ydrunmax	Multi-year daily running maximum
ydrunsum	Multi-year daily running sum
ydrunmean	Multi-year daily running mean
ydrunavg	Multi-year daily running average
ydrunstd	Multi-year daily running standard deviation
ydrunstd1	Multi-year daily running standard deviation (n-1)
ydrunvar	Multi-year daily running variance
ydrunvar1	Multi-year daily running variance (n-1)
ydrunpctl	Multi-year daily running percentiles

2.8.1. TIMCUMSUM - Cumulative sum over all timesteps

Synopsis

```
timcumsum infile outfile
```

Description

The timcumsum operator calculates the cumulative sum over all timesteps. Missing values are treated as numeric zero when summing.

$$o(t, x) = \text{sum}\{i(t', x), 0 < t' \leq t\}$$

2.8.2. CONSECTAT - Consecutive timestep periods

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile outfile
```

Description

This module computes periods over all timesteps in `infile` where a certain property is valid. The property can be chosen by creating a mask from the original data, which is the expected input format for operators of this module. Depending on the operator full information about each period or just its length and ending date are computed.

Operators

consecsum	Consecutive Sum This operator computes periods of consecutive timesteps similar to a runsum , but periods are finished, when the mask value is 0. That way multiple periods can be found. Timesteps from the input are preserved. Missing values are handled like 0, i.e. finish periods of consecutive timesteps.
consects	Consecutive Timesteps In contrast to the operator above <code>consects</code> only computes the length of each period together with its last timestep. To be able to perform statistical analysis like min, max or mean, everything else is set to missing value.

Example

For a given time series of daily temperatures, the periods of summer days can be calculated with inplace masking the input field:

```
cdo consects -gtc,20.0 infile1 outfile
```

2.8.3. VARSSTAT - Statistical values over all variables

Synopsis

`<operator> infile outfile`

Description

This module computes statistical values over all variables for each timestep. Depending on the chosen operator the minimum, maximum, range, sum, average, variance or standard deviation is written to outfile. All input variables need to have the same gridsize and the same number of levels.

Operators

varsmin	Variables minimum For every timestep the minimum over all variables is computed.
varsmax	Variables maximum For every timestep the maximum over all variables is computed.
varsrange	Variables range For every timestep the range over all variables is computed.
varssum	Variables sum For every timestep the sum over all variables is computed.
varsmean	Variables mean For every timestep the mean over all variables is computed.
varsavg	Variables average For every timestep the average over all variables is computed.
varsstd	Variables standard deviation For every timestep the standard deviation over all variables is computed. Normalize by n.
varsstd1	Variables standard deviation (n-1) For every timestep the standard deviation over all variables is computed. Normalize by (n-1).
varsvar	Variables variance For every timestep the variance over all variables is computed. Normalize by n.
varsvar1	Variables variance (n-1) For every timestep the variance over all variables is computed. Normalize by (n-1).

2.8.4. ENSSTAT - Statistical values over an ensemble

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile outfile
enspctl,p infile outfile
```

Description

This module computes statistical values over an ensemble of input files. Depending on the chosen operator, the minimum, maximum, range, sum, average, standard deviation, variance, skewness, kurtosis, median or a certain percentile over all input files is written to outfile. All input files need to have the same structure with the same variables. The date information of a timestep in outfile is the date of the first input file.

Operators

ensmin	Ensemble minimum $o(t, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x), \dots, i_n(t, x)\}$
ensmax	Ensemble maximum $o(t, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x), \dots, i_n(t, x)\}$
ensrange	Ensemble range $o(t, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x), \dots, i_n(t, x)\}$
enssum	Ensemble sum $o(t, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x), \dots, i_n(t, x)\}$
ensmean	Ensemble mean $o(t, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x), \dots, i_n(t, x)\}$
ensavg	Ensemble average $o(t, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x), \dots, i_n(t, x)\}$
ensstd	Ensemble standard deviation Normalize by n. $o(t, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x), \dots, i_n(t, x)\}$
ensstd1	Ensemble standard deviation (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). $o(t, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x), \dots, i_n(t, x)\}$
ensvar	Ensemble variance Normalize by n. $o(t, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x), \dots, i_n(t, x)\}$
ensvar1	Ensemble variance (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). $o(t, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x), \dots, i_n(t, x)\}$
ensskew	Ensemble skewness $o(t, x) = \mathbf{skew}\{i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x), \dots, i_n(t, x)\}$
enskurt	Ensemble kurtosis $o(t, x) = \mathbf{kurt}\{i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x), \dots, i_n(t, x)\}$
ensmedian	Ensemble median $o(t, x) = \mathbf{median}\{i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x), \dots, i_n(t, x)\}$
enspctl	Ensemble percentiles $o(t, x) = \mathbf{pth\ percentile}\{i_1(t, x), i_2(t, x), \dots, i_n(t, x)\}$

Parameter

p FLOAT Percentile number in 0, ..., 100

Note

This operator needs to open all input files simultaneously. The maximum number of open files depends on the operating system!

Example

To compute the ensemble mean over 6 input files use:

```
cdo ensmean infile1 infile2 infile3 infile4 infile5 infile6 outfile
```

Or shorter with filename substitution:

```
cdo ensmean infile[1-6] outfile
```

To compute the 50th percentile (median) over 6 input files use:

```
cdo enspctl,50 infile1 infile2 infile3 infile4 infile5 infile6 outfile
```

2.8.5. ENSSTAT2 - Statistical values over an ensemble

Synopsis

```
<operator> obsfile ensfiles outfile
```

Description

This module computes statistical values over the ensemble of `ensfiles` using `obsfile` as a reference. Depending on the operator a ranked Histogram or a roc-curve over all Ensembles `ensfiles` with reference to `obsfile` is written to `outfile`. The date and grid information of a timestep in `outfile` is the date of the first input file. Thus all input files are required to have the same structure in terms of the gridsize, variable definitions and number of timesteps.

All Operators in this module use `obsfile` as the reference (for instance an observation) whereas `ensfiles` are understood as an ensemble consisting of `n` (where `n` is the number of `ensfiles`) members.

The operators `ensrkhistspace` and `ensrkhisttime` compute Ranked Histograms. Therefore the vertical axis is utilized as the Histogram axis, which prohibits the use of files containing more than one level. The histogram axis has `nensfiles+1` bins with level 0 containing for each grid point the number of observations being smaller as all ensembles and level `nensfiles+1` indicating the number of observations being larger than all ensembles.

`ensrkhistspace` computes a ranked histogram at each timestep reducing each horizontal grid to a 1x1 grid and keeping the time axis as in `obsfile`. Contrary `ensrkhisttime` computes a histogram at each grid point keeping the horizontal grid for each variable and reducing the time-axis. The time information is that from the last timestep in `obsfile`.

Operators

ensrkhistspace	Ranked Histogram averaged over time
ensrkhisttime	Ranked Histogram averaged over space
ensroc	Ensemble Receiver Operating characteristics

Example

To compute a rank histogram over 5 input files `ensfile1-ensfile5` given an observation in `obsfile` use:

```
cdo ensrkhisttime obsfile ensfile1 ensfile2 ensfile3 ensfile4 ensfile5 outfile
```

Or shorter with filename substitution:

```
cdo ensrkhisttime obsfile ensfile[1-5] outfile
```

2.8.6. ENSVAL - Ensemble validation tools

Synopsis

```
enscrps rfile infiles outfilebase
ensbrs,x rfile infiles outfilebase
```

Description

This module computes ensemble validation scores and their decomposition such as the Brier and cumulative ranked probability score (CRPS). The first file is used as a reference it can be a climatology, observation or reanalysis against which the skill of the ensembles given in infiles is measured. Depending on the operator a number of output files is generated each containing the skill score and its decomposition corresponding to the operator. The output is averaged over horizontal fields using appropriate weights for each level and timestep in rfile.

All input files need to have the same structure with the same variables. The date information of a timestep in outfile is the date of the first input file. The output files are named as <outfilebase>.<type>.<filesuffix> where <type> depends on the operator and <filesuffix> is determined from the output file type. There are three output files for operator enscrps and four output files for operator ensbrs.

The CRPS and its decomposition into Reliability and the potential CRPS are calculated by an appropriate averaging over the field members (note, that the CRPS does **not** average linearly). In the three output files <type> has the following meaning: crps for the CRPS, reli for the reliability and crpspot for the potential crps. The relation $CRPS = CRPS_{pot} + RELI$

holds.

The Brier score of the Ensemble given by infiles with respect to the reference given in rfile and the threshold x is calculated. In the four output files <type> has the following meaning: brs for the Brier score wrt threshold x; brsreli for the Brier score reliability wrt threshold x; brsreso for the Brier score resolution wrt threshold x; brsunct for the Brier score uncertainty wrt threshold x. In analogy to the CRPS the following relation holds: $BRS(x) = RELI(x) - RESO(x) + UNCT(x)$.

The implementation of the decomposition of the CRPS and Brier Score follows Hans Hersbach (2000): Decomposition of the Continuous Ranked Probability Score for Ensemble Prediction Systems, in: Weather and Forecasting (15) pp. 559-570.

The CRPS code decomposition has been verified against the CRAN - ensemble validation package from R. Differences occur when grid-cell area is not uniform as the implementation in R does not account for that.

Operators

enscrps	Ensemble CRPS and decomposition
ensbrs	Ensemble Brier score Ensemble Brier Score and Decomposition

Example

To compute the field averaged Brier score at x=5 over an ensemble with 5 members ensfile1-5 w.r.t. the reference rfile and write the results to files obase.brs.<stuff>, obase.brsreli<stuff>, obase.brsreso<stuff>, obase.brsunct<stuff> where <stuff> is determined from the output file type, use

```
cdo ensbrs,5 rfile ensfile1 ensfile2 ensfile3 ensfile4 ensfile5 obase
```

or shorter using file name substitution:

```
cdo ensbrs,5 rfile ensfile[1-5] obase
```

2.8.7. FLDSTAT - Statistical values over a field

Synopsis

`<operator>,weights infile outfile`

`fldpctl,p infile outfile`

Description

This module computes statistical values of all input fields. A field is a horizontal layer of a data variable. Depending on the chosen operator, the minimum, maximum, range, sum, integral, average, standard deviation, variance, skewness, kurtosis, median or a certain percentile of the field is written to outfile.

Operators

fldmin	Field minimum For every gridpoint x_1, \dots, x_n of the same field it is: $o(t, 1) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t, x'), x_1 < x' \leq x_n\}$
fldmax	Field maximum For every gridpoint x_1, \dots, x_n of the same field it is: $o(t, 1) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t, x'), x_1 < x' \leq x_n\}$
fldrange	Field range For every gridpoint x_1, \dots, x_n of the same field it is: $o(t, 1) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t, x'), x_1 < x' \leq x_n\}$
fldsum	Field sum For every gridpoint x_1, \dots, x_n of the same field it is: $o(t, 1) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t, x'), x_1 < x' \leq x_n\}$
fldint	Field integral For every gridpoint x_1, \dots, x_n of the same field it is: $o(t, 1) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t, x') * cellarea(x'), x_1 < x' \leq x_n\}$
fldmean	Field mean For every gridpoint x_1, \dots, x_n of the same field it is: $o(t, 1) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t, x'), x_1 < x' \leq x_n\}$ weighted by area weights obtained by the input field.
fldavg	Field average For every gridpoint x_1, \dots, x_n of the same field it is: $o(t, 1) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t, x'), x_1 < x' \leq x_n\}$ weighted by area weights obtained by the input field.
fldstd	Field standard deviation Normalize by n. For every gridpoint x_1, \dots, x_n of the same field it is: $o(t, 1) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t, x'), x_1 < x' \leq x_n\}$ weighted by area weights obtained by the input field.
fldstd1	Field standard deviation (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). For every gridpoint x_1, \dots, x_n of the same field it is: $o(t, 1) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t, x'), x_1 < x' \leq x_n\}$ weighted by area weights obtained by the input field.

fldvar	Field variance Normalize by n. For every gridpoint x_1, \dots, x_n of the same field it is: $o(t, 1) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t, x'), x_1 < x' \leq x_n\}$ weighted by area weights obtained by the input field.
fldvar1	Field variance (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). For every gridpoint x_1, \dots, x_n of the same field it is: $o(t, 1) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t, x'), x_1 < x' \leq x_n\}$ weighted by area weights obtained by the input field.
fldskew	Field skewness For every gridpoint x_1, \dots, x_n of the same field it is: $o(t, 1) = \mathbf{skew}\{i(t, x'), x_1 < x' \leq x_n\}$
fldkurt	Field kurtosis For every gridpoint x_1, \dots, x_n of the same field it is: $o(t, 1) = \mathbf{kurt}\{i(t, x'), x_1 < x' \leq x_n\}$
fldmedian	Field median For every gridpoint x_1, \dots, x_n of the same field it is: $o(t, 1) = \mathbf{median}\{i(t, x'), x_1 < x' \leq x_n\}$
fldpctl	Field percentiles For every gridpoint x_1, \dots, x_n of the same field it is: $o(t, 1) = \mathbf{pth\ percentile}\{i(t, x'), x_1 < x' \leq x_n\}$

Parameter

<i>weights</i>	BOOL	weights=FALSE disables weighting by grid cell area [default: weights=TRUE]
<i>p</i>	FLOAT	Percentile number in 0, ..., 100

Example

To compute the field mean of all input fields use:

```
cdo fldmean infile outfile
```

To compute the 90th percentile of all input fields use:

```
cdo fldpctl,90 infile outfile
```

2.8.8. ZONSTAT - Zonal statistical values

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile outfile
zonpctl,p infile outfile
```

Description

This module computes zonal statistical values of the input fields. Depending on the chosen operator, the zonal minimum, maximum, range, sum, average, standard deviation, variance, skewness, kurtosis, median or a certain percentile of the field is written to outfile. This operator requires all variables on the same regular lon/lat grid.

Operators

zonmin	Zonal minimum For every latitude the minimum over all longitudes is computed.
zonmax	Zonal maximum For every latitude the maximum over all longitudes is computed.
zonrange	Zonal range For every latitude the range over all longitudes is computed.
zonsum	Zonal sum For every latitude the sum over all longitudes is computed.
zonmean	Zonal mean For every latitude the mean over all longitudes is computed.
zonavg	Zonal average For every latitude the average over all longitudes is computed.
zonstd	Zonal standard deviation For every latitude the standard deviation over all longitudes is computed. Normalize by n.
zonstd1	Zonal standard deviation (n-1) For every latitude the standard deviation over all longitudes is computed. Normalize by (n-1).
zonvar	Zonal variance For every latitude the variance over all longitudes is computed. Normalize by n.
zonvar1	Zonal variance (n-1) For every latitude the variance over all longitudes is computed. Normalize by (n-1).
zonskew	Zonal skewness For every latitude the skewness over all longitudes is computed.
zonkurt	Zonal kurtosis For every latitude the kurtosis over all longitudes is computed.
zonmedian	Zonal median For every latitude the median over all longitudes is computed.
zonpctl	Zonal percentiles For every latitude the pth percentile over all longitudes is computed.

Parameter

p FLOAT Percentile number in 0, ..., 100

Example

To compute the zonal mean of all input fields use:

```
cdo zonmean infile outfile
```

To compute the 50th meridional percentile (median) of all input fields use:

```
cdo zonpctl,50 infile outfile
```

2.8.9. MERSTAT - Meridional statistical values

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile outfile
merpctl,p infile outfile
```

Description

This module computes meridional statistical values of the input fields. Depending on the chosen operator, the meridional minimum, maximum, range, sum, average, standard deviation, variance, skewness, kurtosis, median or a certain percentile of the field is written to outfile. This operator requires all variables on the same regular lon/lat grid.

Operators

mermin	Meridional minimum For every longitude the minimum over all latitudes is computed.
mermax	Meridional maximum For every longitude the maximum over all latitudes is computed.
merrange	Meridional range For every longitude the range over all latitudes is computed.
mersum	Meridional sum For every longitude the sum over all latitudes is computed.
mermean	Meridional mean For every longitude the area weighted mean over all latitudes is computed.
meravg	Meridional average For every longitude the area weighted average over all latitudes is computed.
merstd	Meridional standard deviation For every longitude the standard deviation over all latitudes is computed. Normalize by n.
merstd1	Meridional standard deviation (n-1) For every longitude the standard deviation over all latitudes is computed. Normalize by (n-1).
mervar	Meridional variance For every longitude the variance over all latitudes is computed. Normalize by n.
mervar1	Meridional variance (n-1) For every longitude the variance over all latitudes is computed. Normalize by (n-1).
merskew	Meridional skewness For every longitude the skewness over all latitudes is computed.
merkurt	Meridional kurtosis For every longitude the kurtosis over all latitudes is computed.
mermedian	Meridional median For every longitude the median over all latitudes is computed.
merpctl	Meridional percentiles For every longitude the pth percentile over all latitudes is computed.

Parameter

p FLOAT Percentile number in 0, ..., 100

Example

To compute the meridional mean of all input fields use:

```
cdo mermean infile outfile
```

To compute the 50th meridional percentile (median) of all input fields use:

```
cdo merpctl,50 infile outfile
```

2.8.10. GRIDBOXSTAT - Statistical values over grid boxes

Synopsis

```
<operator>,nx,ny infile outfile
```

Description

This module computes statistical values over surrounding grid boxes. Depending on the chosen operator, the minimum, maximum, range, sum, average, standard deviation, variance, skewness, kurtosis or median of the neighboring grid boxes is written to outfile. All gridbox operators only work on quadrilateral curvilinear grids.

Operators

gridboxmin	Gridbox minimum Minimum value of the selected grid boxes.
gridboxmax	Gridbox maximum Maximum value of the selected grid boxes.
gridboxrange	Gridbox range Range (max-min value) of the selected grid boxes.
gridboxsum	Gridbox sum Sum of the selected grid boxes.
gridboxmean	Gridbox mean Mean of the selected grid boxes.
gridboxavg	Gridbox average Average of the selected grid boxes.
gridboxstd	Gridbox standard deviation Standard deviation of the selected grid boxes. Normalize by n.
gridboxstd1	Gridbox standard deviation (n-1) Standard deviation of the selected grid boxes. Normalize by (n-1).
gridboxvar	Gridbox variance Variance of the selected grid boxes. Normalize by n.
gridboxvar1	Gridbox variance (n-1) Variance of the selected grid boxes. Normalize by (n-1).
gridboxskew	Gridbox skewness Skewness of the selected grid boxes.
gridboxkurt	Gridbox kurtosis Kurtosis of the selected grid boxes.
gridboxmedian	Gridbox median Median of the selected grid boxes.

Parameter

<i>nx</i>	INTEGER	Number of grid boxes in x direction
<i>ny</i>	INTEGER	Number of grid boxes in y direction

Example

To compute the mean over 10x10 grid boxes of the input field use:

```
cdo gridboxmean,10,10 infile outfile
```

2.8.11. VERTSTAT - Vertical statistical values

Synopsis

```
<operator>,weights infile outfile
```

Description

This module computes statistical values over all levels of the input variables. According to chosen operator the vertical minimum, maximum, range, sum, average, variance or standard deviation is written to outfile.

Operators

vertmin	Vertical minimum For every gridpoint the minimum over all levels is computed.
vertmax	Vertical maximum For every gridpoint the maximum over all levels is computed.
vertrange	Vertical range For every gridpoint the range over all levels is computed.
vertsum	Vertical sum For every gridpoint the sum over all levels is computed.
vertmean	Vertical mean For every gridpoint the layer weighted mean over all levels is computed.
vertavg	Vertical average For every gridpoint the layer weighted average over all levels is computed.
vertstd	Vertical standard deviation For every gridpoint the standard deviation over all levels is computed. Normalize by n.
vertstd1	Vertical standard deviation (n-1) For every gridpoint the standard deviation over all levels is computed. Normalize by (n-1).
vertvar	Vertical variance For every gridpoint the variance over all levels is computed. Normalize by n.
vertvar1	Vertical variance (n-1) For every gridpoint the variance over all levels is computed. Normalize by (n-1).

Parameter

weights BOOL weights=FALSE disables weighting by layer thickness [default: weights=TRUE]

Example

To compute the vertical sum of all input variables use:

```
cdo vertsum infile outfile
```

2.8.12. TIMSELSTAT - Time range statistical values

Synopsis

```
<operator> ,nsets[,noffset[,nskip]] infile outfile
```

Description

This module computes statistical values for a selected number of timesteps. According to the chosen operator the minimum, maximum, range, sum, average, variance or standard deviation of the selected timesteps is written to outfile. The time of outfile is determined by the time in the middle of all contributing timesteps of infile. This can be change with the **CDO** option `--timestat_date <first|middle|last>`.

Operators

tinselmin	Time selection minimum For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same selected time range it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
tinselmax	Time selection maximum For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same selected time range it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
tinselrange	Time selection range For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same selected time range it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
tinselsum	Time selection sum For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same selected time range it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
tinselmean	Time selection mean For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same selected time range it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
tinselavg	Time selection average For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same selected time range it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
tinselstd	Time selection standard deviation Normalize by n. For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same selected time range it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
tinselstd1	Time selection standard deviation (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same selected time range it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
tinselvar	Time selection variance Normalize by n. For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same selected time range it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$

timselvar1 Time selection variance (n-1)
 Normalize by (n-1). For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same selected time range it is:

$$o(t, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$$

Parameter

<i>nsets</i>	INTEGER	Number of input timesteps for each output timestep
<i>noffset</i>	INTEGER	Number of input timesteps skipped before the first timestep range (optional)
<i>nskip</i>	INTEGER	Number of input timesteps skipped between timestep ranges (optional)

Example

Assume an input dataset has monthly means over several years. To compute seasonal means from monthly means the first two month have to be skipped:

```
cdo timselmean,3,2 infile outfile
```

2.8.13. TIMSELPCTL - Time range percentile values

Synopsis

```
timselpctl,p,nsets[,noffset[,nskip]] infile1 infile2 infile3 outfile
```

Description

This operator computes percentile values over a selected number of timesteps in *infile1*. The algorithm uses histograms with minimum and maximum bounds given in *infile2* and *infile3*, respectively. The default number of histogram bins is 101. The default can be overridden by setting the environment variable `CDO_PCTL_NBINS` to a different value. The files *infile2* and *infile3* should be the result of corresponding [timselmin](#) and [timselmax](#) operations, respectively. The time of *outfile* is determined by the time in the middle of all contributing timesteps of *infile1*. This can be change with the **CDO** option `--timestat_date <first|middle|last>`.

For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same selected time range it is:

$$o(t, x) = \mathbf{pth\ percentile}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$$

Parameter

<i>p</i>	FLOAT	Percentile number in 0, ..., 100
<i>nsets</i>	INTEGER	Number of input timesteps for each output timestep
<i>noffset</i>	INTEGER	Number of input timesteps skipped before the first timestep range (optional)
<i>nskip</i>	INTEGER	Number of input timesteps skipped between timestep ranges (optional)

Environment

<code>CDO_PCTL_NBINS</code>	Sets the number of histogram bins. The default number is 101.
-----------------------------	---

2.8.14. RUNSTAT - Running statistical values

Synopsis

`<operator>,nts infile outfile`

Description

This module computes running statistical values over a selected number of timesteps. Depending on the chosen operator the minimum, maximum, range, sum, average, variance or standard deviation of a selected number of consecutive timesteps read from `infile` is written to `outfile`. The time of `outfile` is determined by the time in the middle of all contributing timesteps of `infile`. This can be change with the **CDO** option `--timestat_date <first|middle|last>`.

Operators

runmin	Running minimum $o(t + (nts - 1)/2, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x)\}$
runmax	Running maximum $o(t + (nts - 1)/2, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x)\}$
runrange	Running range $o(t + (nts - 1)/2, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x)\}$
runsum	Running sum $o(t + (nts - 1)/2, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x)\}$
runmean	Running mean $o(t + (nts - 1)/2, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x)\}$
runavg	Running average $o(t + (nts - 1)/2, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x)\}$
runstd	Running standard deviation Normalize by n. $o(t + (nts - 1)/2, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x)\}$
runstd1	Running standard deviation (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). $o(t + (nts - 1)/2, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x)\}$
runvar	Running variance Normalize by n. $o(t + (nts - 1)/2, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x)\}$
runvar1	Running variance (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). $o(t + (nts - 1)/2, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x)\}$

Parameter

`nts` **INTEGER** Number of timesteps

Environment

`CDO_TIMESTAT_DATE` Sets the time stamp in `outfile` to the "first", "middle" or "last" contributing timestep of `infile`.

Example

To compute the running mean over 9 timesteps use:

```
cdo runmean,9 infile outfile
```

2.8.15. RUNPCTL - Running percentile values

Synopsis

```
runpctl,p,nts infile outfile
```

Description

This module computes running percentiles over a selected number of timesteps in `infile`. The time of `outfile` is determined by the time in the middle of all contributing timesteps of `infile`. This can be change with the **CDO** option `--timestat_date <first|middle|last>`.

$$o(t + (nts - 1)/2, x) = \mathbf{pth\ percentile}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x)\}$$

Parameter

<code>p</code>	FLOAT	Percentile number in 0, ..., 100
<code>nts</code>	INTEGER	Number of timesteps

Example

To compute the running 50th percentile (median) over 9 timesteps use:

```
cdo runpctl,50,9 infile outfile
```

2.8.16. TIMSTAT - Statistical values over all timesteps

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile outfile
```

Description

This module computes statistical values over all timesteps in `infile`. Depending on the chosen operator the minimum, maximum, range, sum, average, variance or standard deviation of all timesteps read from `infile` is written to `outfile`. The time of `outfile` is determined by the time in the middle of all contributing timesteps of `infile`. This can be change with the **CDO** option `--timestat_date <first|middle|last>`.

Operators

timmin	Time minimum $o(1, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
timmax	Time maximum $o(1, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
timrange	Time range $o(1, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
timsun	Time sum $o(1, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
timmean	Time mean $o(1, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
timavg	Time average $o(1, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
timstd	Time standard deviation Normalize by n. $o(1, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
timstd1	Time standard deviation (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). $o(1, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
timvar	Time variance Normalize by n. $o(1, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
timvar1	Time variance (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). $o(1, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$

Example

To compute the mean over all input timesteps use:

```
cdo timmean infile outfile
```

2.8.17. TIMPCTL - Percentile values over all timesteps

Synopsis

```
timpctl,p infile1 infile2 infile3 outfile
```

Description

This operator computes percentiles over all timesteps in `infile1`. The algorithm uses histograms with minimum and maximum bounds given in `infile2` and `infile3`, respectively. The default number of histogram bins is 101. The default can be overridden by defining the environment variable `CDO_PCTL_NBINS`. The files `infile2` and `infile3` should be the result of corresponding `timmin` and `timax` operations, respectively. The time of `outfile` is determined by the time in the middle of all contributing timesteps of `infile1`. This can be change with the **CDO** option `--timestat_date <first|middle|last>`.

$$o(1,x) = \text{pth percentile}\{i(t',x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$$

Parameter

`p` FLOAT Percentile number in 0, ..., 100

Environment

`CDO_PCTL_NBINS` Sets the number of histogram bins. The default number is 101.

Example

To compute the 90th percentile over all input timesteps use:

```
cdo timmin infile minfile
cdo timmax infile maxfile
cdo timpctl,90 infile minfile maxfile outfile
```

Or shorter using operator piping:

```
cdo timpctl,90 infile -timmin infile -timmax infile outfile
```

2.8.18. HOURSTAT - Hourly statistical values

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile outfile
```

Description

This module computes statistical values over timesteps of the same hour. Depending on the chosen operator the minimum, maximum, range, sum, average, variance or standard deviation of timesteps of the same hour is written to outfile. The time of outfile is determined by the time in the middle of all contributing timesteps of infile. This can be change with the **CDO** option `--timestat_date <first|middle|last>`.

Operators

hourmin	Hourly minimum For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same hour it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
hourmax	Hourly maximum For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same hour it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
hourrange	Hourly range For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same hour it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
hoursum	Hourly sum For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same hour it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
hourmean	Hourly mean For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same hour it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
houravg	Hourly average For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same hour it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
hourstd	Hourly standard deviation Normalize by n. For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same hour it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
hourstd1	Hourly standard deviation (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same hour it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
hourvar	Hourly variance Normalize by n. For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same hour it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
hourvar1	Hourly variance (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same hour it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$

Example

To compute the hourly mean of a time series use:

```
cdo hourmean infile outfile
```

2.8.19. HOURPCTL - Hourly percentile values

Synopsis

```
hourpctl,p infile1 infile2 infile3 outfile
```

Description

This operator computes percentiles over all timesteps of the same hour in `infile1`. The algorithm uses histograms with minimum and maximum bounds given in `infile2` and `infile3`, respectively. The default number of histogram bins is 101. The default can be overridden by defining the environment variable `CDO_PCTL_NBINS`. The files `infile2` and `infile3` should be the result of corresponding [hourmin](#) and [hourmax](#) operations, respectively. The time of `outfile` is determined by the time in the middle of all contributing timesteps of `infile1`. This can be change with the **CDO** option `--timestat_date <first|middle|last>`.

For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same hour it is:

$$o(t, x) = \text{pth percentile}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$$

Parameter

`p` FLOAT Percentile number in 0, ..., 100

Environment

`CDO_PCTL_NBINS` Sets the number of histogram bins. The default number is 101.

Example

To compute the hourly 90th percentile of a time series use:

```
cdo hourmin infile minfile
cdo hourmax infile maxfile
cdo hourpctl,90 infile minfile maxfile outfile
```

Or shorter using operator piping:

```
cdo hourpctl,90 infile -hourmin infile -hourmax infile outfile
```

2.8.20. DAYSTAT - Daily statistical values

Synopsis

<operator> infile outfile

Description

This module computes statistical values over timesteps of the same day. Depending on the chosen operator the minimum, maximum, range, sum, average, variance or standard deviation of timesteps of the same day is written to outfile. The time of outfile is determined by the time in the middle of all contributing timesteps of infile. This can be change with the **CDO** option --timestat_date <first|middle|last>.

Operators

daymin	Daily minimum For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same day it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
daymax	Daily maximum For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same day it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
dayrange	Daily range For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same day it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
daysum	Daily sum For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same day it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
daymean	Daily mean For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same day it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
dayavg	Daily average For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same day it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
daystd	Daily standard deviation Normalize by n. For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same day it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
daystd1	Daily standard deviation (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same day it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
dayvar	Daily variance Normalize by n. For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same day it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
dayvar1	Daily variance (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same day it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$

Example

To compute the daily mean of a time series use:

```
cdo daymean infile outfile
```

2.8.21. DAYPCTL - Daily percentile values

Synopsis

```
daypctl,p infile1 infile2 infile3 outfile
```

Description

This operator computes percentiles over all timesteps of the same day in `infile1`. The algorithm uses histograms with minimum and maximum bounds given in `infile2` and `infile3`, respectively. The default number of histogram bins is 101. The default can be overridden by defining the environment variable `CDO_PCTL_NBINS`. The files `infile2` and `infile3` should be the result of corresponding `daymin` and `daymax` operations, respectively. The time of `outfile` is determined by the time in the middle of all contributing timesteps of `infile1`. This can be change with the **CDO** option `--timestat_date <first|middle|last>`.

For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same day it is:

$$o(t, x) = \text{pth percentile}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$$

Parameter

`p` FLOAT Percentile number in 0, ..., 100

Environment

`CDO_PCTL_NBINS` Sets the number of histogram bins. The default number is 101.

Example

To compute the daily 90th percentile of a time series use:

```
cdo daymin infile minfile
cdo daymax infile maxfile
cdo daypctl,90 infile minfile maxfile outfile
```

Or shorter using operator piping:

```
cdo daypctl,90 infile -daymin infile -daymax infile outfile
```

2.8.22. MONSTAT - Monthly statistical values

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile outfile
```

Description

This module computes statistical values over timesteps of the same month. Depending on the chosen operator the minimum, maximum, range, sum, average, variance or standard deviation of timesteps of the same month is written to outfile. The time of outfile is determined by the time in the middle of all contributing timesteps of infile. This can be change with the **CDO** option `--timestat_date <first|middle|last>`.

Operators

monmin	Monthly minimum For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same month it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
monmax	Monthly maximum For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same month it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
monrange	Monthly range For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same month it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
monsum	Monthly sum For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same month it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
monmean	Monthly mean For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same month it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
monavg	Monthly average For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same month it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
monstd	Monthly standard deviation Normalize by n. For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same month it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
monstd1	Monthly standard deviation (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same month it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
monvar	Monthly variance Normalize by n. For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same month it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
monvar1	Monthly variance (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same month it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$

Example

To compute the monthly mean of a time series use:

```
cdo monmean infile outfile
```

2.8.23. MONPCTL - Monthly percentile values

Synopsis

```
monpctl,p infile1 infile2 infile3 outfile
```

Description

This operator computes percentiles over all timesteps of the same month in `infile1`. The algorithm uses histograms with minimum and maximum bounds given in `infile2` and `infile3`, respectively. The default number of histogram bins is 101. The default can be overridden by defining the environment variable `CDO_PCTL_NBINS`. The files `infile2` and `infile3` should be the result of corresponding `monmin` and `monmax` operations, respectively. The time of `outfile` is determined by the time in the middle of all contributing timesteps of `infile1`. This can be change with the **CDO** option `--timestat_date <first|middle|last>`.

For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same month it is:

$$o(t, x) = \text{pth percentile}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$$

Parameter

`p` FLOAT Percentile number in 0, ..., 100

Environment

`CDO_PCTL_NBINS` Sets the number of histogram bins. The default number is 101.

Example

To compute the monthly 90th percentile of a time series use:

```
cdo monmin infile minfile
cdo monmax infile maxfile
cdo monpctl,90 infile minfile maxfile outfile
```

Or shorter using operator piping:

```
cdo monpctl,90 infile -monmin infile -monmax infile outfile
```

2.8.24. YEARMONSTAT - Yearly mean from monthly data

Synopsis

```
yearmonmean infile outfile
```

Description

This operator computes the yearly mean of a monthly time series. Each month is weighted with the number of days per month. The time of outfile is determined by the time in the middle of all contributing timesteps of infile.

For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same year it is:
 $o(t, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$

Environment

CDO_TIMESTAT_DATE Sets the date information in outfile to the "first", "middle" or "last" contributing timestep of infile.

Example

To compute the yearly mean of a monthly time series use:

```
cdo yearmonmean infile outfile
```

2.8.25. YEARSTAT - Yearly statistical values

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile outfile
```

Description

This module computes statistical values over timesteps of the same year. Depending on the chosen operator the minimum, maximum, range, sum, average, variance or standard deviation of timesteps of the same year is written to outfile. The time of outfile is determined by the time in the middle of all contributing timesteps of infile. This can be change with the **CDO** option `--timestat_date <first|middle|last>`.

Operators

yearmin	Yearly minimum For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same year it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
yearmax	Yearly maximum For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same year it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
yearminidx	Yearly minimum indices For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same year it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{minidx}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
yearmaxidx	Yearly maximum indices For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same year it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{maxidx}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
yearrange	Yearly range For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same year it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
yearsum	Yearly sum For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same year it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
yearmean	Yearly mean For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same year it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
yearavg	Yearly average For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same year it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
yearstd	Yearly standard deviation Normalize by n. For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same year it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
yearstd1	Yearly standard deviation (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same year it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
yearvar	Yearly variance Normalize by n. For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same year it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$

yearvar1 Yearly variance (n-1)
 Normalize by (n-1). For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same year it is:

$$o(t, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$$

Note

The operators `yearmean` and `yearavg` compute only arithmetical means!

Example

To compute the yearly mean of a time series use:

```
cdo yearmean infile outfile
```

To compute the yearly mean from the correct weighted monthly mean use:

```
cdo yearmonmean infile outfile
```

2.8.26. YEARPCTL - Yearly percentile values

Synopsis

```
yearpctl,p infile1 infile2 infile3 outfile
```

Description

This operator computes percentiles over all timesteps of the same year in `infile1`. The algorithm uses histograms with minimum and maximum bounds given in `infile2` and `infile3`, respectively. The default number of histogram bins is 101. The default can be overridden by defining the environment variable `CDO_PCTL_NBINS`. The files `infile2` and `infile3` should be the result of corresponding `yearmin` and `yearmax` operations, respectively. The time of `outfile` is determined by the time in the middle of all contributing timesteps of `infile1`. This can be change with the **CDO** option `--timestat_date <first|middle|last>`.

For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same year it is:

$$o(t, x) = \mathbf{pth\ percentile}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$$

Parameter

p FLOAT Percentile number in 0, ..., 100

Environment

`CDO_PCTL_NBINS` Sets the number of histogram bins. The default number is 101.

Example

To compute the yearly 90th percentile of a time series use:

```
cdo yearmin infile minfile
cdo yearmax infile maxfile
cdo yearpctl,90 infile minfile maxfile outfile
```

Or shorter using operator piping:

```
cdo yearpctl,90 infile -yearmin infile -yearmax infile outfile
```

2.8.27. SEASSTAT - Seasonal statistical values

Synopsis

<operator> infile outfile

Description

This module computes statistical values over timesteps of the same season. Depending on the chosen operator the minimum, maximum, range, sum, average, variance or standard deviation of timesteps of the same season is written to outfile. The time of outfile is determined by the time in the middle of all contributing timesteps of infile. This can be change with the **CDO** option `--timestat_date` <first|middle|last>. Be careful about the first and the last output timestep, they may be incorrect values if the seasons have incomplete timesteps.

Operators

seasmin	Seasonal minimum For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same season it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
seasmax	Seasonal maximum For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same season it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
seasrange	Seasonal range For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same season it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
seasum	Seasonal sum For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same season it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
seasmean	Seasonal mean For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same season it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
seasavg	Seasonal average For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same season it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
seasstd	Seasonal standard deviation Normalize by n. For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same season it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
seasstd1	Seasonal standard deviation (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same season it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
seasvar	Seasonal variance Normalize by n. For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same season it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$
seasvar1	Seasonal variance (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). For every adjacent sequence t_{-1}, \dots, t_{-n} of timesteps of the same season it is: $o(t, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$

Example

To compute the seasonal mean of a time series use:

```
cdo seasmean infile outfile
```

2.8.28. SEASPCTL - Seasonal percentile values

Synopsis

```
seaspctl,p infile1 infile2 infile3 outfile
```

Description

This operator computes percentiles over all timesteps in `infile1` of the same season. The algorithm uses histograms with minimum and maximum bounds given in `infile2` and `infile3`, respectively. The default number of histogram bins is 101. The default can be overridden by defining the environment variable `CDO_PCTL_NBINS`. The files `infile2` and `infile3` should be the result of corresponding `seasmin` and `seasmax` operations, respectively. The time of `outfile` is determined by the time in the middle of all contributing timesteps of `infile1`. This can be change with the **CDO** option `--timestat_date <first|middle|last>`. Be careful about the first and the last output timestep, they may be incorrect values if the seasons have incomplete timesteps.

For every adjacent sequence t_1, \dots, t_n of timesteps of the same season it is:

$$o(t, x) = \text{pth percentile}\{i(t', x), t_1 < t' \leq t_n\}$$

Parameter

`p` `FLOAT` Percentile number in 0, ..., 100

Environment

`CDO_PCTL_NBINS` Sets the number of histogram bins. The default number is 101.

Example

To compute the seasonal 90th percentile of a time series use:

```
cdo seasmin infile minfile
cdo seasmax infile maxfile
cdo seaspctl,90 infile minfile maxfile outfile
```

Or shorter using operator piping:

```
cdo seaspctl,90 infile -seasmin infile -seasmax infile outfile
```

2.8.29. YHOURSTAT - Multi-year hourly statistical values

Synopsis

<operator> infile outfile

Description

This module computes statistical values of each hour and day of year. Depending on the chosen operator the minimum, maximum, range, sum, average, variance or standard deviation of each hour and day of year in infile is written to outfile. The date information in an output field is the date of the last contributing input field.

Operators

yhourmin	Multi-year hourly minimum $o(0001, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 0001\}$ \vdots $o(8784, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 8784\}$
yhourmax	Multi-year hourly maximum $o(0001, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 0001\}$ \vdots $o(8784, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 8784\}$
yhourrange	Multi-year hourly range $o(0001, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 0001\}$ \vdots $o(8784, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 8784\}$
yhoursum	Multi-year hourly sum $o(0001, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 0001\}$ \vdots $o(8784, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 8784\}$
yhourmean	Multi-year hourly mean $o(0001, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 0001\}$ \vdots $o(8784, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 8784\}$
yhouravg	Multi-year hourly average $o(0001, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 0001\}$ \vdots $o(8784, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 8784\}$
yhourstd	Multi-year hourly standard deviation Normalize by n. $o(0001, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 0001\}$ \vdots $o(8784, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 8784\}$
yhourstd1	Multi-year hourly standard deviation (n-1) Normalize by (n-1).

	$o(0001, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 0001\}$
	\vdots
	$o(8784, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 8784\}$
yhourvar	Multi-year hourly variance Normalize by n.
	$o(0001, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 0001\}$
	\vdots
	$o(8784, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 8784\}$
yhourvar1	Multi-year hourly variance (n-1) Normalize by (n-1).
	$o(0001, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 0001\}$
	\vdots
	$o(8784, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 8784\}$

2.8.30. DHOURLYSTAT - Multi-day hourly statistical values

Synopsis

`<operator> infile outfile`

Description

This module computes statistical values of each hour of day. Depending on the chosen operator the minimum, maximum, range, sum, average, variance or standard deviation of each hour of day in `infile` is written to `outfile`. The date information in an output field is the date of the last contributing input field.

Operators

dhourmin	Multi-day hourly minimum $o(01, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 01\}$ \vdots $o(24, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 24\}$
dhourmax	Multi-day hourly maximum $o(01, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 01\}$ \vdots $o(24, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 24\}$
dhourrange	Multi-day hourly range $o(01, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 01\}$ \vdots $o(24, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 24\}$
dhoursum	Multi-day hourly sum $o(01, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 01\}$ \vdots $o(24, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 24\}$
dhourmean	Multi-day hourly mean $o(01, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 01\}$ \vdots $o(24, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 24\}$
dhouravg	Multi-day hourly average $o(01, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 01\}$ \vdots $o(24, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 24\}$
dhourstd	Multi-day hourly standard deviation Normalize by n. $o(01, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 01\}$ \vdots $o(24, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 24\}$
dhourstd1	Multi-day hourly standard deviation (n-1) Normalize by (n-1).

	$o(01, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 01\}$
	\vdots
	$o(24, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 24\}$
dhourvar	Multi-day hourly variance Normalize by n.
	$o(01, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 01\}$
	\vdots
	$o(24, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 24\}$
dhourvar1	Multi-day hourly variance (n-1) Normalize by (n-1).
	$o(01, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 01\}$
	\vdots
	$o(24, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 24\}$

2.8.31. YDAYSTAT - Multi-year daily statistical values

Synopsis

`<operator> infile outfile`

Description

This module computes statistical values of each day of year. Depending on the chosen operator the minimum, maximum, range, sum, average, variance or standard deviation of each day of year in `infile` is written to `outfile`. The date information in an output field is the date of the last contributing input field.

Operators

ydaymin	Multi-year daily minimum $o(001, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 001\}$ \vdots $o(366, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 366\}$
ydaymax	Multi-year daily maximum $o(001, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 001\}$ \vdots $o(366, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 366\}$
ydayrange	Multi-year daily range $o(001, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 001\}$ \vdots $o(366, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 366\}$
ydaysum	Multi-year daily sum $o(001, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 001\}$ \vdots $o(366, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 366\}$
ydaymean	Multi-year daily mean $o(001, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 001\}$ \vdots $o(366, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 366\}$
ydayavg	Multi-year daily average $o(001, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 001\}$ \vdots $o(366, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 366\}$
ydaystd	Multi-year daily standard deviation Normalize by n. $o(001, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 001\}$ \vdots $o(366, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 366\}$
ydaystd1	Multi-year daily standard deviation (n-1) Normalize by (n-1).

	$o(001, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 001\}$
	⋮
	$o(366, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 366\}$
ydayvar	Multi-year daily variance Normalize by n.
	$o(001, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 001\}$
	⋮
	$o(366, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 366\}$
ydayvar1	Multi-year daily variance (n-1) Normalize by (n-1).
	$o(001, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 001\}$
	⋮
	$o(366, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 366\}$

Example

To compute the daily mean over all input years use:

```
cdo ydaymean infile outfile
```

2.8.32. YDAYPCTL - Multi-year daily percentile values

Synopsis

```
ydaypctl,p infile1 infile2 infile3 outfile
```

Description

This operator writes a certain percentile of each day of year in `infile1` to `outfile`. The algorithm uses histograms with minimum and maximum bounds given in `infile2` and `infile3`, respectively. The default number of histogram bins is 101. The default can be overridden by setting the environment variable `CDO_PCTL_NBINS` to a different value. The files `infile2` and `infile3` should be the result of corresponding `ydaymin` and `ydaymax` operations, respectively. The date information in an output field is the date of the last contributing input field.

$$o(001, x) = \text{pth percentile}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 001\}$$

$$\vdots$$

$$o(366, x) = \text{pth percentile}\{i(t, x), \text{day}(i(t)) = 366\}$$

Parameter

`p` FLOAT Percentile number in 0, ..., 100

Environment

`CDO_PCTL_NBINS` Sets the number of histogram bins. The default number is 101.

Example

To compute the daily 90th percentile over all input years use:

```
cdo ydaymin infile minfile
cdo ydaymax infile maxfile
cdo ydaypctl,90 infile minfile maxfile outfile
```

Or shorter using operator piping:

```
cdo ydaypctl,90 infile -ydaymin infile -ydaymax infile outfile
```

2.8.33. YMONSTAT - Multi-year monthly statistical values

Synopsis

<operator> infile outfile

Description

This module computes statistical values of each month of year. Depending on the chosen operator the minimum, maximum, range, sum, average, variance or standard deviation of each month of year in `infile` is written to `outfile`. The date information in an output field is the date of the last contributing input field. This can be change with the **CDO** option `--timestat_date <first|middle|last>`.

Operators

ymonmin	Multi-year monthly minimum $o(01, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 01\}$ \vdots $o(12, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12\}$
ymonmax	Multi-year monthly maximum $o(01, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 01\}$ \vdots $o(12, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12\}$
ymonrange	Multi-year monthly range $o(01, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 01\}$ \vdots $o(12, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12\}$
ymonsum	Multi-year monthly sum $o(01, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 01\}$ \vdots $o(12, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12\}$
ymonmean	Multi-year monthly mean $o(01, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 01\}$ \vdots $o(12, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12\}$
ymonavg	Multi-year monthly average $o(01, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 01\}$ \vdots $o(12, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12\}$
ymonstd	Multi-year monthly standard deviation Normalize by n. $o(01, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 01\}$ \vdots $o(12, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12\}$
ymonstd1	Multi-year monthly standard deviation (n-1) Normalize by (n-1).

	$o(01, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 01\}$
	\vdots
	$o(12, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12\}$
ymonvar	Multi-year monthly variance Normalize by n.
	$o(01, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 01\}$
	\vdots
	$o(12, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12\}$
ymonvar1	Multi-year monthly variance (n-1) Normalize by (n-1).
	$o(01, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 01\}$
	\vdots
	$o(12, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12\}$

Example

To compute the monthly mean over all input years use:

```
cdo ymonmean infile outfile
```

2.8.34. YMONPCTL - Multi-year monthly percentile values

Synopsis

```
ymonpctl,p infile1 infile2 infile3 outfile
```

Description

This operator writes a certain percentile of each month of year in `infile1` to `outfile`. The algorithm uses histograms with minimum and maximum bounds given in `infile2` and `infile3`, respectively. The default number of histogram bins is 101. The default can be overridden by setting the environment variable `CDO_PCTL_NBINS` to a different value. The files `infile2` and `infile3` should be the result of corresponding `ymonmin` and `ymonmax` operations, respectively. The date information in an output field is the date of the last contributing input field.

$$\begin{aligned}
 o(01, x) &= \text{pth percentile}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 01\} \\
 &\quad \vdots \\
 o(12, x) &= \text{pth percentile}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Parameter

`p` FLOAT Percentile number in 0, ..., 100

Environment

`CDO_PCTL_NBINS` Sets the number of histogram bins. The default number is 101.

Example

To compute the monthly 90th percentile over all input years use:

```
cdo ymonmin infile minfile
cdo ymonmax infile maxfile
cdo ymonpctl,90 infile minfile maxfile outfile
```

Or shorter using operator piping:

```
cdo ymonpctl,90 infile -ymonmin infile -ymonmax infile outfile
```

2.8.35. YSEASSTAT - Multi-year seasonal statistical values

Synopsis

<operator> infile outfile

Description

This module computes statistical values of each season. Depending on the chosen operator the minimum, maximum, range, sum, average, variance or standard deviation of each season in infile is written to outfile. The date information in an output field is the date of the last contributing input field.

Operators

yseasmin	Multi-year seasonal minimum $o(1, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12, 01, 02\}$ $o(2, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 03, 04, 05\}$ $o(3, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 06, 07, 08\}$ $o(4, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 09, 10, 11\}$
yseasmax	Multi-year seasonal maximum $o(1, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12, 01, 02\}$ $o(2, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 03, 04, 05\}$ $o(3, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 06, 07, 08\}$ $o(4, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 09, 10, 11\}$
yseasrange	Multi-year seasonal range $o(1, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12, 01, 02\}$ $o(2, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 03, 04, 05\}$ $o(3, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 06, 07, 08\}$ $o(4, x) = \mathbf{range}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 09, 10, 11\}$
yseassum	Multi-year seasonal sum $o(1, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12, 01, 02\}$ $o(2, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 03, 04, 05\}$ $o(3, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 06, 07, 08\}$ $o(4, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 09, 10, 11\}$
yseasmean	Multi-year seasonal mean $o(1, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12, 01, 02\}$ $o(2, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 03, 04, 05\}$ $o(3, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 06, 07, 08\}$ $o(4, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 09, 10, 11\}$
yseasavg	Multi-year seasonal average $o(1, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12, 01, 02\}$ $o(2, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 03, 04, 05\}$ $o(3, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 06, 07, 08\}$ $o(4, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 09, 10, 11\}$
yseasstd	Multi-year seasonal standard deviation $o(1, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12, 01, 02\}$ $o(2, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 03, 04, 05\}$ $o(3, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 06, 07, 08\}$ $o(4, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 09, 10, 11\}$

yseasstd1	Multi-year seasonal standard deviation (n-1) $o(1, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12, 01, 02\}$ $o(2, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 03, 04, 05\}$ $o(3, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 06, 07, 08\}$ $o(4, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 09, 10, 11\}$
yseasvar	Multi-year seasonal variance $o(1, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12, 01, 02\}$ $o(2, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 03, 04, 05\}$ $o(3, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 06, 07, 08\}$ $o(4, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 09, 10, 11\}$
yseasvar1	Multi-year seasonal variance (n-1) $o(1, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12, 01, 02\}$ $o(2, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 03, 04, 05\}$ $o(3, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 06, 07, 08\}$ $o(4, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 09, 10, 11\}$

Example

To compute the seasonal mean over all input years use:

```
cdo yseasmean infile outfile
```

2.8.36. YSEASPCTL - Multi-year seasonal percentile values

Synopsis

```
yseaspctl,p infile1 infile2 infile3 outfile
```

Description

This operator writes a certain percentile of each season in `infile1` to `outfile`. The algorithm uses histograms with minimum and maximum bounds given in `infile2` and `infile3`, respectively. The default number of histogram bins is 101. The default can be overridden by setting the environment variable `CDO_PCTL_NBINS` to a different value. The files `infile2` and `infile3` should be the result of corresponding `yseasmin` and `yseasmax` operations, respectively. The date information in an output field is the date of the last contributing input field.

$$o(1, x) = \text{pth percentile}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 12, 01, 02\}$$

$$o(2, x) = \text{pth percentile}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 03, 04, 05\}$$

$$o(3, x) = \text{pth percentile}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 06, 07, 08\}$$

$$o(4, x) = \text{pth percentile}\{i(t, x), \text{month}(i(t)) = 09, 10, 11\}$$

Parameter

`p` FLOAT Percentile number in 0, ..., 100

Environment

`CDO_PCTL_NBINS` Sets the number of histogram bins. The default number is 101.

Example

To compute the seasonal 90th percentile over all input years use:

```
cdo yseasmin infile minfile
cdo yseasmax infile maxfile
cdo yseaspctl,90 infile minfile maxfile outfile
```

Or shorter using operator piping:

```
cdo yseaspctl,90 infile -yseasmin infile -yseasmax infile outfile
```

2.8.37. YDRUNSTAT - Multi-year daily running statistical values

Synopsis

`<operator>,nts infile outfile`

Description

This module writes running statistical values for each day of year in infile to outfile. Depending on the chosen operator, the minimum, maximum, sum, average, variance or standard deviation of all timesteps in running windows of which the medium timestep corresponds to a certain day of year is computed. The date information in an output field is the date of the timestep in the middle of the last contributing running window. Note that the operator have to be applied to a continuous time series of daily measurements in order to yield physically meaningful results. Also note that the output time series begins $(nts-1)/2$ timesteps after the first timestep of the input time series and ends $(nts-1)/2$ timesteps before the last one. For input data which are complete but not continuous, such as time series of daily measurements for the same month or season within different years, the operator yields physically meaningful results only if the input time series does include the $(nts-1)/2$ days before and after each period of interest.

Operators

ydrunmin	Multi-year daily running minimum $o(001, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 001\}$ \vdots $o(366, x) = \mathbf{min}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 366\}$
ydrunmax	Multi-year daily running maximum $o(001, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 001\}$ \vdots $o(366, x) = \mathbf{max}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 366\}$
ydrunsum	Multi-year daily running sum $o(001, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 001\}$ \vdots $o(366, x) = \mathbf{sum}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 366\}$
ydrunmean	Multi-year daily running mean $o(001, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 001\}$ \vdots $o(366, x) = \mathbf{mean}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 366\}$
ydrunavg	Multi-year daily running average $o(001, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 001\}$ \vdots $o(366, x) = \mathbf{avg}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 366\}$
ydrunstd	Multi-year daily running standard deviation Normalize by n. $o(001, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 001\}$ \vdots $o(366, x) = \mathbf{std}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 366\}$

ydrunstd1	Multi-year daily running standard deviation (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). $o(001, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 001\}$ \vdots $o(366, x) = \mathbf{std1}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 366\}$
ydrunvar	Multi-year daily running variance Normalize by n. $o(001, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 001\}$ \vdots $o(366, x) = \mathbf{var}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 366\}$
ydrunvar1	Multi-year daily running variance (n-1) Normalize by (n-1). $o(001, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 001\}$ \vdots $o(366, x) = \mathbf{var1}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 366\}$

Parameter

nts INTEGER Number of timesteps

Example

Assume the input data provide a continuous time series of daily measurements. To compute the running multi-year daily mean over all input timesteps for a running window of five days use:

```
cdo ydrunmean,5 infile outfile
```

Note that except for the standard deviation the results of the operators in this module are equivalent to a composition of corresponding operators from the [YDAYSTAT](#) and [RUNSTAT](#) modules. For instance, the above command yields the same result as:

```
cdo ydaymean -runmean,5 infile outfile
```

2.8.38. YDRUNPCTL - Multi-year daily running percentile values

Synopsis

```
ydrunpctl,p,nts infile1 infile2 infile3 outfile
```

Description

This operator writes running percentile values for each day of year in `infile1` to `outfile`. A certain percentile is computed for all timesteps in running windows of which the medium timestep corresponds to a certain day of year. The algorithm uses histograms with minimum and maximum bounds given in `infile2` and `infile3`, respectively. The default number of histogram bins is 101. The default can be overridden by setting the environment variable `CDO_PCTL_NBINS` to a different value. The files `infile2` and `infile3` should be the result of corresponding `ydrunmin` and `ydrunmax` operations, respectively. The date information in an output field is the date of the timestep in the middle of the last contributing running window. Note that the operator have to be applied to a continuous time series of daily measurements in order to yield physically meaningful results. Also note that the output time series begins $(nts-1)/2$ timesteps after the first timestep of the input time series and ends $(nts-1)/2$ timesteps before the last. For input data which are complete but not continuous, such as time series of daily measurements for the same month or season within different years, the operator only yields physically meaningful results if the input time series does include the $(nts-1)/2$ days before and after each period of interest.

$$\begin{aligned}
 o(001, x) &= \text{pth percentile}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 001\} \\
 &\quad \vdots \\
 o(366, x) &= \text{pth percentile}\{i(t, x), i(t + 1, x), \dots, i(t + nts - 1, x); \text{day}[(i(t + (nts - 1)/2)] = 366\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Parameter

<code>p</code>	FLOAT	Percentile number in 0, ..., 100
<code>nts</code>	INTEGER	Number of timesteps

Environment

<code>CDO_PCTL_NBINS</code>	Sets the number of histogram bins. The default number is 101.
-----------------------------	---

Example

Assume the input data provide a continuous time series of daily measurements. To compute the running multi-year daily 90th percentile over all input timesteps for a running window of five days use:

```
cdo ydrunmin,5 infile minfile
cdo ydrunmax,5 infile maxfile
cdo ydrunpctl,90,5 infile minfile maxfile outfile
```

Or shorter using operator piping:

```
cdo ydrunpctl,90,5 infile -ydrunmin infile -ydrunmax infile outfile
```

2.9. Correlation and co.

This sections contains modules for correlation and co. in grid space and over time.
In this section the abbreviations as in the following table are used:

Covariance covar	$n^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})$
covar weighted by $\{w_i, i = 1, \dots, n\}$	$\left(\sum_{j=1}^n w_j \right)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \left(x_i - \left(\sum_{j=1}^n w_j \right)^{-1} \sum_{j=1}^n w_j x_j \right) \left(y_i - \left(\sum_{j=1}^n w_j \right)^{-1} \sum_{j=1}^n w_j y_j \right)$

Here is a short overview of all operators in this section:

fldcor	Correlation in grid space
timcor	Correlation over time
fldcovar	Covariance in grid space
timcovar	Covariance over time

2.9.1. FLDCOR - Correlation in grid space

Synopsis

```
fldcor infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

The correlation coefficient is a quantity that gives the quality of a least squares fitting to the original data. This operator correlates all gridpoints of two fields for each timestep. With

$$S(t) = \{x, i_1(t, x) \neq \text{missval} \wedge i_2(t, x) \neq \text{missval}\}$$

it is

$$o(t, 1) = \frac{\sum_{x \in S(t)} i_1(t, x) i_2(t, x) w(x) - \overline{i_1(t, x)} \overline{i_2(t, x)} \sum_{x \in S(t)} w(x)}{\sqrt{\left(\sum_{x \in S(t)} i_1(t, x)^2 w(x) - \overline{i_1(t, x)}^2 \sum_{x \in S(t)} w(x) \right) \left(\sum_{x \in S(t)} i_2(t, x)^2 w(x) - \overline{i_2(t, x)}^2 \sum_{x \in S(t)} w(x) \right)}}$$

where $w(x)$ are the area weights obtained by the input streams. For every timestep t only those field elements x belong to the sample, which have $i_1(t, x) \neq \text{missval}$ and $i_2(t, x) \neq \text{missval}$.

2.9.2. TIMCOR - Correlation over time

Synopsis

```
timcor infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

The correlation coefficient is a quantity that gives the quality of a least squares fitting to the original data. This operator correlates each gridpoint of two fields over all timesteps. With

$$S(x) = \{t, i_1(t, x) \neq \text{missval} \wedge i_2(t, x) \neq \text{missval}\}$$

it is

$$o(1, x) = \frac{\sum_{t \in S(x)} i_1(t, x) i_2(t, x) - n \overline{i_1(t, x)} \overline{i_2(t, x)}}{\sqrt{\left(\sum_{t \in S(x)} i_1(t, x)^2 - n \overline{i_1(t, x)}^2 \right) \left(\sum_{t \in S(x)} i_2(t, x)^2 - n \overline{i_2(t, x)}^2 \right)}}$$

For every gridpoint x only those timesteps t belong to the sample, which have $i_1(t, x) \neq \text{missval}$ and $i_2(t, x) \neq \text{missval}$.

2.9.3. FLDCOVAR - Covariance in grid space

Synopsis

```
fldcovar infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

This operator calculates the covariance of two fields over all gridpoints for each timestep. With

$$S(t) = \{x, i_1(t, x) \neq \text{missval} \wedge i_2(t, x) \neq \text{missval}\}$$

it is

$$o(t, 1) = \left(\sum_{x \in S(t)} w(x) \right)^{-1} \sum_{x \in S(t)} w(x) \left(i_1(t, x) - \frac{\sum_{x \in S(t)} w(x) i_1(t, x)}{\sum_{x \in S(t)} w(x)} \right) \left(i_2(t, x) - \frac{\sum_{x \in S(t)} w(x) i_2(t, x)}{\sum_{x \in S(t)} w(x)} \right)$$

where $w(x)$ are the area weights obtained by the input streams. For every timestep t only those field elements x belong to the sample, which have $i_1(t, x) \neq \text{missval}$ and $i_2(t, x) \neq \text{missval}$.

2.9.4. TIMCOVAR - Covariance over time

Synopsis

```
timcovar infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

This operator calculates the covariance of two fields at each gridpoint over all timesteps. With

$$S(x) = \{t, i_1(t, x) \neq \text{missval} \wedge i_2(t, x) \neq \text{missval}\}$$

it is

$$o(1, x) = n^{-1} \sum_{t \in S(x)} \left(i_1(t, x) - \overline{i_1(t, x)} \right) \left(i_2(t, x) - \overline{i_2(t, x)} \right)$$

For every gridpoint x only those timesteps t belong to the sample, which have $i_1(t, x) \neq \text{missval}$ and $i_2(t, x) \neq \text{missval}$.

2.10. Regression

This sections contains modules for linear regression of time series.

Here is a short overview of all operators in this section:

regres	Regression
detrend	Detrend
trend	Trend
addtrend	Add trend
subtrend	Subtract trend

2.10.1. REGRES - Regression

Synopsis

```
regres[,equal] infile outfile
```

Description

The values of the input file `infile` are assumed to be distributed as $N(a + bt, \sigma^2)$ with unknown a , b and σ^2 . This operator estimates the parameter b . For every field element x only those timesteps t belong to the sample $S(x)$, which have $i(t, x) \neq \text{miss}$. It is

$$o(1, x) = \frac{\sum_{t \in S(x)} \left(i(t, x) - \frac{1}{\#S(x)} \sum_{t' \in S(x)} i(t', x) \right) \left(t - \frac{1}{\#S(x)} \sum_{t' \in S(x)} t' \right)}{\sum_{t \in S(x)} \left(t - \frac{1}{\#S(x)} \sum_{t' \in S(x)} t' \right)^2}$$

It is assumed that all timesteps are equidistant, if this is not the case set the parameter `equal=false`.

Parameter

`equal` **BOOL** Set to false for unequal distributed timesteps (default: true)

2.10.2. DETREND - Detrend time series

Synopsis

```
detrend[,equal] infile outfile
```

Description

Every time series in `infile` is linearly detrended. For every field element x only those timesteps t belong to the sample $S(x)$, which have $i(t, x) \neq \text{miss}$. It is assumed that all timesteps are equidistant, if this is not the case set the parameter `equal=false`. With

$$a(x) = \frac{1}{\#S(x)} \sum_{t \in S(x)} i(t, x) - b(x) \left(\frac{1}{\#S(x)} \sum_{t \in S(x)} t \right)$$

and

$$b(x) = \frac{\sum_{t \in S(x)} \left(i(t, x) - \frac{1}{\#S(x)} \sum_{t' \in S(x)} i(t', x) \right) \left(t - \frac{1}{\#S(x)} \sum_{t' \in S(x)} t' \right)}{\sum_{t \in S(x)} \left(t - \frac{1}{\#S(x)} \sum_{t' \in S(x)} t' \right)^2}$$

it is

$$o(t, x) = i(t, x) - (a(x) + b(x)t)$$

Parameter

`equal` **BOOL** Set to false for unequal distributed timesteps (default: true)

Note

This operator has to keep the fields of all timesteps concurrently in the memory. If not enough memory is available use the operators [trend](#) and [subtrend](#).

Example

To detrend the data in infile and to store the detrended data in outfile use:

```
cdo detrend infile outfile
```

2.10.3. TREND - Trend of time series**Synopsis**

```
trend[,equal] infile outfile1 outfile2
```

Description

The values of the input file `infile` are assumed to be distributed as $N(a + bt, \sigma^2)$ with unknown a , b and σ^2 . This operator estimates the parameter a and b . For every field element x only those timesteps t belong to the sample $S(x)$, which have $i(t, x) \neq \text{miss}$. It is

$$o_1(1, x) = \frac{1}{\#S(x)} \sum_{t \in S(x)} i(t, x) - b(x) \left(\frac{1}{\#S(x)} \sum_{t \in S(x)} t \right)$$

and

$$o_2(1, x) = \frac{\sum_{t \in S(x)} \left(i(t, x) - \frac{1}{\#S(x)} \sum_{t' \in S(x)} i(t', x) \right) \left(t - \frac{1}{\#S(x)} \sum_{t' \in S(x)} t' \right)}{\sum_{t \in S(x)} \left(t - \frac{1}{\#S(x)} \sum_{t' \in S(x)} t' \right)^2}$$

Thus the estimation for a is stored in `outfile1` and that for b is stored in `outfile2`. To subtract the trend from the data see operator [subtrend](#). It is assumed that all timesteps are equidistant, if this is not the case set the parameter `equal=false`.

Parameter

`equal` `BOOL` Set to false for unequal distributed timesteps (default: true)

2.10.4. TRENDARITH - Add or subtract a trend

Synopsis

```
<operator>[,equal] infile1 infile2 infile3 outfile
```

Description

This module is for adding or subtracting a trend computed by the operator [trend](#).

Operators

addtrend Add trend
It is

$$o(t, x) = i_1(t, x) + (i_2(1, x) + i_3(1, x) \cdot t)$$

where t is the timesteps.

subtrend Subtract trend
It is

$$o(t, x) = i_1(t, x) - (i_2(1, x) + i_3(1, x) \cdot t)$$

where t is the timesteps.

Parameter

equal BOOL Set to false for unequal distributed timesteps (default: true)

Example

The typical call for detrending the data in infile and storing the detrended data in outfile is:

```
cdo trend infile afile bfile
cdo subtrend infile afile bfile outfile
```

The result is identical to a call of the operator [detrend](#):

```
cdo detrend infile outfile
```

2.11. EOFs

This section contains modules to compute Empirical Orthogonal Functions and - once they are computed - their principal coefficients.

An introduction to the theory of principal component analysis as applied here can be found in:

Principal Component Analysis in Meteorology and Oceanography [Preisendorfer]

Details about calculation in the time- and spatial spaces are found in:

Statistical Analysis in Climate Research [vonStorch]

EOFs are defined as the eigen values of the scatter matrix (covariance matrix) of the data. For the sake of simplicity, samples are regarded as **time series of anomalies**

$$(z(t)), t \in \{1, \dots, n\}$$

of (column-) vectors $z(t)$ with p entries (where p is the gridsize). Thus, using the fact, that $z_j(t)$ are anomalies, i.e.

$$\langle z_j \rangle = n^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n z_j(i) = 0 \quad \forall 1 \leq j \leq p$$

the scatter matrix \mathbf{S} can be written as

$$\mathbf{S} = \sum_{t=1}^n \left[\sqrt{\mathbf{W}} z(t) \right] \left[\sqrt{\mathbf{W}} z(t) \right]^T$$

where \mathbf{W} is the diagonal matrix containing the area weight of cell p_0 in z at $\mathbf{W}(x, x)$.

The matrix \mathbf{S} has a set of orthonormal eigenvectors $e_j, j = 1, \dots, p$, which are called *empirical orthogonal functions (EOFs) of the sample z* . (Please note, that e_j is the eigenvector of \mathbf{S} and not the weighted eigen-vector which would be $\mathbf{W}e_j$.) Let the corresponding eigenvalues be denoted λ_j . The vectors e_j are spatial patterns which explain a certain amount of variance of the time series $z(t)$ that is related linearly to λ_j . Thus, the spatial pattern defined by the first eigenvector (the one with the largest eigenvalue) is the pattern which explains a maximum possible amount of variance of the sample $z(t)$. The orthonormality of eigenvectors reads as

$$\sum_{x=1}^p \left[\sqrt{\mathbf{W}(x, x)} e_j(x) \right] \left[\sqrt{\mathbf{W}(x, x)} e_k(x) \right] = \sum_{x=1}^p \mathbf{W}(x, x) e_j(x) e_k(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j \neq k \\ 1 & \text{if } j = k \end{cases}$$

If all EOFs e_j with $\lambda_j \neq 0$ are calculated, the data can be reconstructed from

$$z(t, x) = \sum_{j=1}^p \mathbf{W}(x, x) a_j(t) e_j(x)$$

where a_j are called the *principal components* or *principal coefficients* or *EOF coefficients* of z . These coefficients - as readily seen from above - are calculated as the projection of an EOF e_j onto a time step of the data sample $z(t_0)$ as

$$a_j(t_0) = \sum_{x=1}^p \left[\sqrt{\mathbf{W}(x, x)} e_j(x) \right] \left[\sqrt{\mathbf{W}(x, x)} z(t_0, x) \right] = \left[\sqrt{\mathbf{W}} z(t_0) \right]^T \left[\sqrt{\mathbf{W}} e_j \right].$$

Here is a short overview of all operators in this section:

eof	Calculate EOFs in spatial or time space
eoftime	Calculate EOFs in time space
eofspatial	Calculate EOFs in spatial space
eof3d	Calculate 3-Dimensional EOFs in time space
eofcoeff	Calculate principal coefficients of EOFs

2.11.1. EOFs - Empirical Orthogonal Functions

Synopsis

```
<operator>,neof infile outfile1 outfile2
```

Description

This module calculates empirical orthogonal functions of the data in `infile` as the eigen values of the scatter matrix (covariance matrix) S of the data sample $z(t)$. A more detailed description can be found above.

Please note, that the input data are assumed to be anomalies.

If operator `eof` is chosen, the EOFs are computed in either time or spatial space, whichever is the fastest. If the user already knows, which computation is faster, the module can be forced to perform a computation in time- or gridspace by using the operators `eoftime` or `eofspatial`, respectively. This can enhance performance, especially for very long time series, where the number of timesteps is larger than the number of grid-points. Data in `infile` are assumed to be anomalies. If they are not, the behavior of this module is **not well defined**. After execution `outfile1` will contain all eigen-values and `outfile2` the eigenvectors e_j . All EOFs and eigen-values are computed. However, only the first `neof` EOFs are written to `outfile2`. Nonetheless, `outfile1` contains all eigen-values.

Missing values are not fully supported. Support is only checked for non-changing masks of missing values in time. Although there still will be results, they are not trustworthy, and a warning will occur. In the latter case we suggest to replace missing values by 0 in `infile`.

Operators

<code>eof</code>	Calculate EOFs in spatial or time space
<code>eoftime</code>	Calculate EOFs in time space
<code>eofspatial</code>	Calculate EOFs in spatial space
<code>eof3d</code>	Calculate 3-Dimensional EOFs in time space

Parameter

<code>neof</code>	INTEGER	Number of eigen functions
-------------------	---------	---------------------------

Environment

<code>CDO_SVD_MODE</code>	Is used to choose the algorithm for eigenvalue calculation. Options are 'jacobi' for a one-sided parallel jacobi-algorithm (only executed in parallel if -P flag is set) and 'danielson_lanczos' for a non-parallel d/l algorithm. The default setting is 'jacobi'.
<code>CDO_WEIGHT_MODE</code>	It is used to set the weight mode. The default is 'off'. Set it to 'on' for a weighted version.
<code>MAX_JACOBI_ITER</code>	Is the maximum integer number of annihilation sweeps that is executed if the jacobi-algorithm is used to compute the eigen values. The default value is 12.
<code>FNORM_PRECISION</code>	Is the Frobenius norm of the matrix consisting of an annihilation pair of eigenvectors that is used to determine if the eigenvectors have reached a sufficient level of convergence. If all annihilation-pairs of vectors have a norm below this value, the computation is considered to have converged properly. Otherwise, a warning will occur. The default value 1e-12.

Example

To calculate the first 40 EOFs of a data-set containing anomalies use:

```
cdo eof,40 infile outfile1 outfile2
```

If the dataset does not contain anomalies, process them first, and use:

```
cdo sub infile1 -timmean infile1 anom_file  
cdo eof,40 anom_file outfile1 outfile2
```

2.11.2. EOFCOEFF - Principal coefficients of EOFs

Synopsis

```
eofcoeff infile1 infile2 obase
```

Description

This module calculates the time series of the principal coefficients for given EOF (empirical orthogonal functions) and data. Time steps in `infile1` are assumed to be the EOFs, time steps in `infile2` are assumed to be the time series. Note, that this operator calculates a non weighted dot product of the fields in `infile1` and `infile2`. For consistency set the environment variable `CDO_WEIGHT_MODE=off` when using `eof` or `eof3d`. Given a set of EOFs e_{-j} and a time series of data $z(t)$ with p entries for each timestep from which e_{-j} have been calculated, this operator calculates the time series of the projections of data onto each EOF

$$o_j(t) = \sum_{x=1}^p z(t,x)e_j(x)$$

There will be a separate file o_{-j} for the principal coefficients of each EOF.

As the EOFs e_{-j} are uncorrelated, so are their principal coefficients, i.e.

$$\sum_{t=1}^n o_j(t)o_k(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } j \neq k \\ \lambda_j & \text{if } j = k \end{cases} \quad \text{with } \sum_{t=1}^n o_j(t) = 0 \forall j \in \{1, \dots, p\}.$$

There will be a separate file containing a time series of principal coefficients with time information from `infile2` for each EOF in `infile1`. Output files will be numbered as `<obase><neof><suffix>` where `neof+1` is the number of the EOF (timestep) in `infile1` and `suffix` is the filename extension derived from the file format.

Environment

`CDO_FILE_SUFFIX` Set the default file suffix. This suffix will be added to the output file names instead of the filename extension derived from the file format. Set this variable to `NULL` to disable the adding of a file suffix.

Example

To calculate principal coefficients of the first 40 EOFs of `anom_file`, and write them to files beginning with `obase`, use:

```
export CDO_WEIGHT_MODE=off
cdo eof,40 anom_file eval_file eof_file
cdo eofcoeff eof_file anom_file obase
```

The principal coefficients of the first EOF will be in the file `obase000000.nc` (and so forth for higher EOFs, n th EOF will be in `obase<n-1>`).

If the dataset `infile` does not contain anomalies, process them first, and use:

```
export CDO_WEIGHT_MODE=off
cdo sub infile -timmean infile anom_file
cdo eof,40 anom_file eval_file eof_file
cdo eofcoeff eof_file anom_file obase
```

2.12. Interpolation

This section contains modules to interpolate datasets. There are several operators to interpolate horizontal fields to a new grid. Some of those operators can handle only 2D fields on a regular rectangular grid. Vertical interpolation of 3D variables is possible from hybrid model levels to height or pressure levels. Interpolation in time is possible between time steps and years.

Here is a short overview of all operators in this section:

remapbil	Bilinear interpolation
genbil	Generate bilinear interpolation weights
remapbic	Bicubic interpolation
genbic	Generate bicubic interpolation weights
remapnn	Nearest neighbor remapping
gennn	Generate nearest neighbor remap weights
remapdis	Distance weighted average remapping
gendis	Generate distance weighted average remap weights
remapcon	First order conservative remapping
gencon	Generate 1st order conservative remap weights
remapcon2	Second order conservative remapping
gencon2	Generate 2nd order conservative remap weights
remaplaf	Largest area fraction remapping
genlaf	Generate largest area fraction remap weights
remap	Grid remapping
remapeta	Remap vertical hybrid level
ml2pl	Model to pressure level interpolation
ml2hl	Model to height level interpolation
ap2pl	Air pressure to pressure level interpolation
gh2hl	Geometric height to height level interpolation
intlevel	Linear level interpolation
intlevel3d	Linear level interpolation onto a 3D vertical coordinate
intlevelx3d	like intlevel3d but with extrapolation
inttime	Interpolation between timesteps
intntime	Interpolation between timesteps
intyear	Interpolation between two years

2.12.1. REMAPBIL - Bilinear interpolation

Synopsis

```
<operator>,grid infile outfile
```

Description

This module contains operators for a bilinear remapping of fields between grids in spherical coordinates. The interpolation is based on an adapted SCRIP library version. For a detailed description of the interpolation method see [SCRIP]. This interpolation method only works on quadrilateral curvilinear source grids. Below is a schematic illustration of the bilinear remapping:

The figure on the left side shows the input data on a regular lon/lat source grid and on the right side the remapped result on an unstructured triangular target grid. The figure in the middle shows the input data with the target grid. Grid cells with missing value are grey colored.

Operators

- remapbil** Bilinear interpolation
Performs a bilinear interpolation on all input fields.
- genbil** Generate bilinear interpolation weights
Generates bilinear interpolation weights for the first input field and writes the result to a file. The format of this file is NetCDF following the SCRIP convention. Use the operator [remap](#) to apply this remapping weights to a data file with the same source grid.

Parameter

grid STRING Target grid description file or name

Environment

REMAP_EXTRAPOLATE This variable is used to switch the extrapolation feature 'on' or 'off'. By default the extrapolation is enabled for circular grids.

Example

Say *infile* contains fields on a quadrilateral curvilinear grid. To remap all fields bilinear to a Gaussian N32 grid, type:

```
cdo remapbil,n32 infile outfile
```

2.12.2. REMAPBIC - Bicubic interpolation

Synopsis

```
<operator> .grid infile outfile
```

Description

This module contains operators for a bicubic remapping of fields between grids in spherical coordinates. The interpolation is based on an adapted SCRIP library version. For a detailed description of the interpolation method see [SCRIP]. This interpolation method only works on quadrilateral curvilinear source grids. Below is a schematic illustration of the bicubic remapping:

The figure on the left side shows the input data on a regular lon/lat source grid and on the right side the remapped result on an unstructured triangular target grid. The figure in the middle shows the input data with the target grid. Grid cells with missing value are grey colored.

Operators

remapbic	Bicubic interpolation Performs a bicubic interpolation on all input fields.
genbic	Generate bicubic interpolation weights Generates bicubic interpolation weights for the first input field and writes the result to a file. The format of this file is NetCDF following the SCRIP convention. Use the operator remap to apply this remapping weights to a data file with the same source grid.

Parameter

grid STRING Target grid description file or name

Environment

REMAP_EXTRAPOLATE This variable is used to switch the extrapolation feature 'on' or 'off'. By default the extrapolation is enabled for circular grids.

Example

Say *infile* contains fields on a quadrilateral curvilinear grid. To remap all fields bicubic to a Gaussian N32 grid, type:

```
cdo remapbic,n32 infile outfile
```

2.12.3. REMAPNN - Nearest neighbor remapping

Synopsis

```
<operator>,grid infile outfile
```

Description

This module contains operators for a nearest neighbor remapping of fields between grids in spherical coordinates. Below is a schematic illustration of the nearest neighbor remapping:

The figure on the left side shows the input data on a regular lon/lat source grid and on the right side the remapped result on an unstructured triangular target grid. The figure in the middle shows the input data with the target grid. Grid cells with missing value are grey colored.

Operators

- remapnn** Nearest neighbor remapping
Performs a nearest neighbor remapping on all input fields.
- gennn** Generate nearest neighbor remap weights
Generates nearest neighbor remapping weights for the first input field and writes the result to a file. The format of this file is NetCDF following the SCRIP convention. Use the operator [remap](#) to apply this remapping weights to a data file with the same source grid.

Parameter

grid STRING Target grid description file or name

Environment

- REMAP_EXTRAPOLATE This variable is used to switch the extrapolation feature 'on' or 'off'. By default the extrapolation is enabled for this remapping method.
- CDO_GRIDSEARCH_RADIUS Grid search radius in degree, default 180 degree.

2.12.4. REMAPDIS - Distance weighted average remapping

Synopsis

```
remapdis,grid[,neighbors] infile outfile
```

```
gendis,grid infile outfile
```

Description

This module contains operators for an inverse distance weighted average remapping of the four nearest neighbor values of fields between grids in spherical coordinates. The interpolation is based on an adapted SCRIP library version. For a detailed description of the interpolation method see [SCRIP]. Below is a schematic illustration of the distance weighted average remapping:

The figure on the left side shows the input data on a regular lon/lat source grid and on the right side the remapped result on an unstructured triangular target grid. The figure in the middle shows the input data with the target grid. Grid cells with missing value are grey colored.

Operators

- remapdis** Distance weighted average remapping
Performs an inverse distance weighted average remapping of the nearest neighbors value on all input fields. The default number of nearest neighbors is 4.
- gendis** Generate distance weighted average remap weights
Generates distance weighted average remapping weights of the four nearest neighbor values for the first input field and writes the result to a file. The format of this file is NetCDF following the SCRIP convention. Use the operator [remap](#) to apply this remapping weights to a data file with the same source grid.

Parameter

- | | | |
|------------------|---------|--------------------------------------|
| <i>grid</i> | STRING | Target grid description file or name |
| <i>neighbors</i> | INTEGER | Number of nearest neighbors |

Environment

- | | |
|-----------------------|---|
| REMAP_EXTRAPOLATE | This variable is used to switch the extrapolation feature 'on' or 'off'. By default the extrapolation is enabled for this remapping method. |
| CDO_GRIDSEARCH_RADIUS | Grid search radius in degree, default 180 degree. |

2.12.5. REMAPCON - First order conservative remapping

Synopsis

```
<operator>,>grid infile outfile
```

Description

This module contains operators for a first order conservative remapping of fields between grids in spherical coordinates. The operators in this module uses code from the YAC software package to compute the conservative remapping weights. For a detailed description of the interpolation method see [YAC]. The interpolation method is completely general and can be used for any grid on a sphere. The search algorithm for the conservative remapping requires that no grid cell occurs more than once. Below is a schematic illustration of the 1st order conservative remapping:

The figure on the left side shows the input data on a regular lon/lat source grid and on the right side the remapped result on an unstructured triangular target grid. The figure in the middle shows the input data with the target grid. Grid cells with missing value are grey colored.

Operators

- remapcon** First order conservative remapping
Performs a first order conservative remapping on all input fields.
- gencon** Generate 1st order conservative remap weights
Generates first order conservative remapping weights for the first input field and writes the result to a file. The format of this file is NetCDF following the SCRIP convention. Use the operator [remap](#) to apply this remapping weights to a data file with the same source grid.

Parameter

grid STRING Target grid description file or name

Environment

CDO_REMAP_NORM This variable is used to choose the normalization of the conservative interpolation. By default CDO_REMAP_NORM is set to 'fracarea'. 'fracarea' uses the sum of the non-masked source cell intersected areas to normalize each target cell field value. This results in a reasonable flux value but the flux is not locally conserved. The option 'destarea' uses the total target cell area to normalize each target cell field value. Local flux conservation is ensured, but unreasonable flux values may result.

REMAP_AREA_MIN This variable is used to set the minimum destination area fraction. The default of this variable is 0.0.

Example

Say infile contains fields on a quadrilateral curvilinear grid. To remap all fields conservative to a Gaussian N32 grid, type:

```
cdo remapcon,n32 infile outfile
```

2.12.6. REMAPCON2 - Second order conservative remapping

Synopsis

```
<operator> ,grid infile outfile
```

Description

This module contains operators for a second order conservative remapping of fields between grids in spherical coordinates. The interpolation is based on an adapted SCRIP library version. For a detailed description of the interpolation method see [SCRIP]. The interpolation method is completely general and can be used for any grid on a sphere. The search algorithm for the conservative remapping requires that no grid cell occurs more than once. Below is a schematic illustration of the 2nd order conservative remapping:

The figure on the left side shows the input data on a regular lon/lat source grid and on the right side the remapped result on an unstructured triangular target grid. The figure in the middle shows the input data with the target grid. Grid cells with missing value are grey colored.

Operators

- remapcon2** Second order conservative remapping
Performs a second order conservative remapping on all input fields.
- gencon2** Generate 2nd order conservative remap weights
Generates second order conservative remapping weights for the first input field and writes the result to a file. The format of this file is NetCDF following the SCRIP convention. Use the operator [remap](#) to apply this remapping weights to a data file with the same source grid.

Parameter

grid STRING Target grid description file or name

Environment

CDO_REMAP_NORM This variable is used to choose the normalization of the conservative interpolation. By default CDO_REMAP_NORM is set to 'fracarea'. 'fracarea' uses the sum of the non-masked source cell intersected areas to normalize each target cell field value. This results in a reasonable flux value but the flux is not locally conserved. The option 'destarea' uses the total target cell area to normalize each target cell field value. Local flux conservation is ensured, but unreasonable flux values may result.

REMAP_AREA_MIN This variable is used to set the minimum destination area fraction. The default of this variable is 0.0.

Note

The SCRIP conservative remapping method doesn't work correctly for some grid combinations.

Example

Say `infile` contains fields on a quadrilateral curvilinear grid. To remap all fields conservative (2nd order) to a Gaussian N32 grid, type:

```
cdo remapcon2,n32 infile outfile
```

2.12.7. REMAPLAF - Largest area fraction remapping

Synopsis

```
<operator>,grid infile outfile
```

Description

This module contains operators for a largest area fraction remapping of fields between grids in spherical coordinates. The operators in this module uses code from the YAC software package to compute the largest area fraction. For a detailed description of the interpolation method see [YAC]. The interpolation method is completely general and can be used for any grid on a sphere. The search algorithm for this remapping method requires that no grid cell occurs more than once. Below is a schematic illustration of the largest area fraction conservative remapping:

The figure on the left side shows the input data on a regular lon/lat source grid and on the right side the remapped result on an unstructured triangular target grid. The figure in the middle shows the input data with the target grid. Grid cells with missing value are grey colored.

Operators

- remaplaf** Largest area fraction remapping
Performs a largest area fraction remapping on all input fields.
- genlaf** Generate largest area fraction remap weights
Generates largest area fraction remapping weights for the first input field and writes the result to a file. The format of this file is NetCDF following the SCRIP convention. Use the operator [remap](#) to apply this remapping weights to a data file with the same source grid.

Parameter

grid STRING Target grid description file or name

Environment

REMAP_AREA_MIN This variable is used to set the minimum destination area fraction. The default of this variable is 0.0.

2.12.8. REMAP - Grid remapping

Synopsis

```
remap,grid,weights infile outfile
```

Description

Interpolation between different horizontal grids can be a very time-consuming process. Especially if the data are on an unstructured and/or a large grid. In this case the interpolation process can be split into two parts. Firstly the generation of the interpolation weights, which is the most time-consuming part. These interpolation weights can be reused for every remapping process with the operator `remap`. This operator remaps all input fields to a new horizontal grid. The remap type and the interpolation weights of one input grid are read from a NetCDF file. More weights are computed if the input fields are on different grids. The NetCDF file with the weights should follow the [SCRIP] convention. Normally these weights come from a previous call to one of the genXXX operators (e.g. `genbil`) or were created by the original SCRIP package.

Parameter

<code>grid</code>	STRING	Target grid description file or name
<code>weights</code>	STRING	Interpolation weights (SCRIP NetCDF file)

Environment

<code>CDO_REMAP_NORM</code>	This variable is used to choose the normalization of the conservative interpolation. By default <code>CDO_REMAP_NORM</code> is set to 'fracarea'. 'fracarea' uses the sum of the non-masked source cell intersected areas to normalize each target cell field value. This results in a reasonable flux value but the flux is not locally conserved. The option 'destarea' uses the total target cell area to normalize each target cell field value. Local flux conservation is ensured, but unreasonable flux values may result.
<code>REMAP_EXTRAPOLATE</code>	This variable is used to switch the extrapolation feature 'on' or 'off'. By default the extrapolation is enabled for <code>remapdis</code> , <code>remapnn</code> and for circular grids.
<code>REMAP_AREA_MIN</code>	This variable is used to set the minimum destination area fraction. The default of this variable is 0.0.
<code>CDO_GRIDSEARCH_RADIUS</code>	Grid search radius in degree, default 180 degree.

Example

Say `infile` contains fields on a quadrilateral curvilinear grid. To remap all fields bilinear to a Gaussian N32 grid use:

```
cdo genbil,n32 infile remapweights.nc
cdo remap,n32,remapweights.nc infile outfile
```

The result will be the same as:

```
cdo remapbil,n32 infile outfile
```

2.12.9. REMAPETA - Remap vertical hybrid level

Synopsis

```
remapeta,vct[,oro] infile outfile
```

Description

This operator interpolates between different vertical hybrid levels. This include the preparation of consistent data for the free atmosphere. The procedure for the vertical interpolation is based on the HIRLAM scheme and was adapted from [INTERA]. The vertical interpolation is based on the vertical integration of the hydrostatic equation with few adjustments. The basic tasks are the following one:

- at first integration of hydrostatic equation
- extrapolation of surface pressure
- Planetary Boundary-Layer (PBL) proutfile interpolation
- interpolation in free atmosphere
- merging of both proutfiles
- final surface pressure correction

The vertical interpolation corrects the surface pressure. This is simply a cut-off or an addition of air mass. This mass correction should not influence the geostrophic velocity field in the middle troposphere. Therefore the total mass above a given reference level is conserved. As reference level the geopotential height of the 400 hPa level is used. Near the surface the correction can affect the vertical structure of the PBL. Therefore the interpolation is done using the potential temperature. But in the free atmosphere above a certain n ($n=0.8$ defining the top of the PBL) the interpolation is done linearly. After the interpolation both proutfiles are merged. With the resulting temperature/pressure correction the hydrostatic equation is integrated again and adjusted to the reference level finding the final surface pressure correction. A more detailed description of the interpolation can be found in [INTERA]. This operator requires all variables on the same horizontal grid.

Parameter

<code>vct</code>	STRING	File name of an ASCII dataset with the vertical coordinate table
<code>oro</code>	STRING	File name with the orography (surf. geopotential) of the target dataset (optional)

Environment

<code>REMAPETA_PTOP</code>	Sets the minimum pressure level for condensation. Above this level the humidity is set to the constant 1.E-6. The default value is 0 Pa.
----------------------------	--

Note

The code numbers or the variable names of the required parameter have to follow the [ECHAM] convention.

Use the `sinfo` command to test if your vertical coordinate system is recognized as hybrid system.

In case `remapeta` complains about not finding any data on hybrid model levels you may wish to use the `setzaxis` command to generate a zaxis description which conforms to the ECHAM convention. See section "1.4 Z-axis description" for an example how to define a hybrid Z-axis.

Example

To remap between different hybrid model level data use:

```
cdo remapeta,vct infile outfile
```

Here is an example vct file with 19 hybrid model level:

0	0.0000000000000000	0.0000000000000000
1	2000.0000000000000000	0.0000000000000000
2	4000.0000000000000000	0.0000000000000000
3	6046.1093750000000000	0.00033899326808751
4	8267.9296875000000000	0.00335718691349030
5	10609.5117187500000000	0.01307003945112228
6	12851.1015625000000000	0.03407714888453484
7	14698.5000000000000000	0.07064980268478394
8	15861.1289062500000000	0.12591671943664551
9	16116.2382812500000000	0.20119541883468628
10	15356.9218750000000000	0.29551959037780762
11	13621.4609375000000000	0.40540921688079834
12	11101.5585937500000000	0.52493220567703247
13	8127.1445312500000000	0.64610791206359863
14	5125.1406250000000000	0.75969839096069336
15	2549.9689941406250000	0.85643762350082397
16	783.1950683593750000	0.92874687910079956
17	0.0000000000000000	0.97298520803451538
18	0.0000000000000000	0.99228149652481079
19	0.0000000000000000	1.0000000000000000

2.12.10. VERTINTML - Vertical interpolation

Synopsis

```
ml2pl,plevels infile outfile
```

```
ml2hl,hlevels infile outfile
```

Description

Interpolates 3D variables on hybrid sigma pressure level to pressure or height levels. The input file should contain the log. surface pressure or the surface pressure. To extrapolate the temperature, the surface geopotential is also needed. It is assumed that the geopotential heights are located on the hybrid layer interfaces. For the lowest layer of geopotential heights the surface geopotential is required. The pressure, temperature, geopotential height, and surface geopotential are identified by their GRIB1 code number or NetCDF CF standard name. Supported parameter tables are: WMO standard table number 2 and ECMWF local table number 128.

CF standard name	Units	GRIB 1 code
surface_air_pressure	Pa	134
air_temperature	K	130
surface_geopotential	m2 s-2	129
geopotential_height	m	156

Use the alias **ml2plx/ml2hlx** or the environment variable EXTRAPOLATE to extrapolate missing values. This operator requires all variables on the same horizontal grid. Missing values in the input data are not supported.

Operators

ml2pl Model to pressure level interpolation
Interpolates 3D variables on hybrid sigma pressure level to pressure level.

ml2hl Model to height level interpolation
Interpolates 3D variables on hybrid sigma pressure level to height level. The procedure is the same as for the operator [ml2pl](#) except for the pressure levels being calculated from the heights by: $p_{level} = 101325 * \exp(h_{level} / -7000)$

Parameter

<i>plevels</i>	FLOAT	Pressure levels in pascal
<i>hlevels</i>	FLOAT	Height levels in meter

Environment

EXTRAPOLATE If set to 1 extrapolate missing values.

Example

To interpolate hybrid model level data to pressure levels of 925, 850, 500 and 200 hPa use:

```
cdo ml2pl,92500,85000,50000,20000 infile outfile
```

2.12.11. VERTINTAP - Vertical pressure interpolation

Synopsis

```
ap2pl,plevels infile outfile
```

Description

Interpolate 3D variables on hybrid sigma height coordinates to pressure levels. The input file must contain the 3D air pressure in pascal. The air pressure is identified by the NetCDF CF standard name `air_pressure`. Use the alias `ap2plx` or the environment variable `EXTRAPOLATE` to extrapolate missing values. This operator requires all variables on the same horizontal grid.

Parameter

<code>plevels</code>	FLOAT	Comma-separated list of pressure levels in pascal
----------------------	-------	---

Environment

<code>EXTRAPOLATE</code>	If set to 1 extrapolate missing values.
--------------------------	---

Note

This is a specific implementation for NetCDF files from the ICON model, it may not work with data from other sources.

Example

To interpolate 3D variables on hybrid sigma height level to pressure levels of 925, 850, 500 and 200 hPa use:

```
cdo ap2pl,92500,85000,50000,20000 infile outfile
```

2.12.12. VERTINTGH - Vertical height interpolation

Synopsis

```
gh2hl,hlevels infile outfile
```

Description

Interpolate 3D variables on hybrid sigma height coordinates to height levels. The input file must contain the 3D geometric height in meter. The geometric height is identified by the NetCDF CF standard name `geometric_height_at_full_level_center`. Use the alias `gh2hlx` or the environment variable `EXTRAPOLATE` to extrapolate missing values. This operator requires all variables on the same horizontal grid.

Parameter

`hlevels` FLOAT Comma-separated list of height levels in meter

Environment

`EXTRAPOLATE` If set to 1 extrapolate missing values.

Note

This is a specific implementation for NetCDF files from the ICON model, it may not work with data from other sources.

Example

To interpolate 3D variables on hybrid sigma height level to height levels of 20, 100, 500, 1000, 5000, 10000 and 20000 meter use:

```
cdo gh2hl,20,100,500,1000,5000,10000,20000 infile outfile
```

2.12.13. INTLEVEL - Linear level interpolation

Synopsis

```
intlevel,levels infile outfile
```

Description

This operator performs a linear vertical interpolation of 3D variables.

Parameter

levels FLOAT Comma-separated list of target levels

Example

To interpolate 3D variables on height levels to a new set of height levels use:

```
cdo intlevel,10,50,100,500,1000 infile outfile
```

2.12.14. INTLEVEL3D - Linear level interpolation from/to 3D vertical coordinates

Synopsis

```
<operator>,tgtcoordinate infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

This operator performs a linear vertical interpolation of 3D variables fields with given 3D vertical coordinates. *infile1* contains the 3D data variables and *infile2* the 3D vertical source coordinate. The parameter *tgtcoordinate* is a datafile with the 3D vertical target coordinate.

Operators

intlevel3d Linear level interpolation onto a 3D vertical coordinate

intlevelx3d like intlevel3d but with extrapolation

Parameter

tgtcoordinate STRING filename for 3D vertical target coordinates

Example

To interpolate 3D variables from one set of 3D height levels into another one where

- *infile2* contains a single 3D variable, which represents the source 3D vertical coordinate
- *infile1* contains the source data, which the vertical coordinate from *infile2* belongs to
- *tgtcoordinate* only contains the target 3D height levels

```
cdo intlevel3d,tgtcoordinate infile1 infile2 outfile
```

2.12.15. INTTIME - Time interpolation

Synopsis

```
inttime,date,time[,inc] infile outfile
```

```
intntime,n infile outfile
```

Description

This module performs linear interpolation between timesteps. Interpolation is only performed if both values exist. If both values are missing values, the result is also a missing value. If only one value exists, it is taken if the time weighting is greater than or equal to 0.5. So no new value will be created at existing time steps, if the value is missing there.

Operators

inttime Interpolation between timesteps
This operator creates a new dataset by linear interpolation between timesteps. The user has to define the start date/time with an optional increment.

intntime Interpolation between timesteps
This operator performs linear interpolation between timesteps. The user has to define the number of timesteps from one timestep to the next.

Parameter

<i>date</i>	STRING	Start date (format YYYY-MM-DD)
<i>time</i>	STRING	Start time (format hh:mm:ss)
<i>inc</i>	STRING	Optional increment (seconds, minutes, hours, days, months, years) [default: 0hour]
<i>n</i>	INTEGER	Number of timesteps from one timestep to the next

Example

Assumed a 6 hourly dataset starts at 1987-01-01 12:00:00. To interpolate this time series to a one hourly dataset use:

```
cdo inttime,1987-01-01,12:00:00,1hour infile outfile
```

2.12.16. INTYEAR - Year interpolation

Synopsis

```
intyear,years infile1 infile2 obase
```

Description

This operator performs linear interpolation between two years, timestep by timestep. The input files need to have the same structure with the same variables. The output files will be named `<obase><yyyy><suffix>` where `yyyy` will be the year and `suffix` is the filename extension derived from the file format.

Parameter

`years` INTEGER Comma-separated list or first/last[/inc] range of years

Environment

`CDO_FILE_SUFFIX` Set the default file suffix. This suffix will be added to the output file names instead of the filename extension derived from the file format. Set this variable to NULL to disable the adding of a file suffix.

Note

This operator needs to open all output files simultaneously. The maximum number of open files depends on the operating system!

Example

Assume there are two monthly mean datasets over a year. The first dataset has 12 timesteps for the year 1985 and the second one for the year 1990. To interpolate the years between 1985 and 1990 month by month use:

```
cdo intyear,1986,1987,1988,1989 infile1 infile2 year
```

Example result of `'dir year*'` for NetCDF datasets:

```
year1986.nc year1987.nc year1988.nc year1989.nc
```

2.13. Transformation

This section contains modules to perform spectral transformations.

Here is a short overview of all operators in this section:

sp2gp	Spectral to gridpoint
gp2sp	Gridpoint to spectral
sp2sp	Spectral to spectral
dv2ps	D and V to velocity potential and stream function
dv2uv	Divergence and vorticity to U and V wind
uv2dv	U and V wind to divergence and vorticity
fourier	Fourier transformation

2.13.1. SPECTRAL - Spectral transformation

Synopsis

```
<operator>[,gridtype] infile outfile
```

Description

This module transforms fields on a global regular Gaussian grid to spectral coefficients and vice versa. The transformation is achieved by applying Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT) first and direct Legendre Transformation afterwards in gp2sp. In sp2gp the inverse Legendre Transformation and inverse FFT are used. Missing values are not supported.

The relationship between the spectral resolution, governed by the truncation number T, and the grid resolution depends on the number of grid points at which the shortest wavelength field is represented. For a grid with 2N points between the poles (so 4N grid points in total around the globe) the relationship is:

linear grid: the shortest wavelength is represented by 2 grid points $\rightarrow 4N \simeq 2(TL + 1)$

quadratic grid: the shortest wavelength is represented by 3 grid points $\rightarrow 4N \simeq 3(TQ + 1)$

cubic grid: the shortest wavelength is represented by 4 grid points $\rightarrow 4N \simeq 4(TC + 1)$

The quadratic grid is used by ECHAM and ERA15. ERA40 is using a linear Gaussian grid reflected by the TL notation.

The following table shows the calculation of the number of latitudes and the triangular truncation for the different grid types:

Gridtype	Number of latitudes: nlat	Triangular truncation: ntr
linear	$NINT((ntr*2 + 1)/2)$	$(nlat*2 - 1) / 2$
quadratic	$NINT((ntr*3 + 1)/2)$	$(nlat*2 - 1) / 3$
cubic	$NINT((ntr*4 + 1)/2)$	$(nlat*2 - 1) / 4$

Operators

- sp2gp** Spectral to gridpoint
Convert all spectral fields to a global regular Gaussian grid.
- gp2sp** Gridpoint to spectral
Convert all Gaussian gridpoint fields to spectral fields.

Parameter

gridtype STRING Type of the grid: quadratic, linear, cubic (default: quadratic)

Example

To transform spectral coefficients from T106 to N80 Gaussian grid use:

```
cdo sp2gp infile outfile
```

To transform spectral coefficients from TL159 to N80 Gaussian grid use:

```
cdo sp2gp,linear infile outfile
```

2.13.2. SPECCONV - Spectral conversion

Synopsis

```
sp2sp, trunc infile outfile
```

Description

Changed the triangular truncation of all spectral fields. This operator performs downward conversion by cutting the resolution. Upward conversions are achieved by filling in zeros.

Parameter

```
trunc    INTEGER    New spectral resolution
```

2.13.3. WIND2 - D and V to velocity potential and stream function

Synopsis

```
dv2ps infile outfile
```

Description

Calculate spherical harmonic coefficients of velocity potential and stream function from spherical harmonic coefficients of relative divergence and vorticity. The divergence and vorticity need to have the names *sd* and *svo* or code numbers 155 and 138.

2.13.4. WIND - Wind transformation

Synopsis

```
<operator>[,gridtype] infile outfile
```

Description

This module converts relative divergence and vorticity to U and V wind and vice versa. Divergence and vorticity are spherical harmonic coefficients in spectral space and U and V are on a global regular Gaussian grid. The Gaussian latitudes need to be ordered from north to south. The maximum number of supported spectral coefficients is 4002000. Missing values are not supported.

The relationship between the spectral resolution, governed by the truncation number T, and the grid resolution depends on the number of grid points at which the shortest wavelength field is represented. For a grid with 2N points between the poles (so 4N grid points in total around the globe) the relationship is:

linear grid: the shortest wavelength is represented by 2 grid points $\rightarrow 4N \simeq 2(TL + 1)$

quadratic grid: the shortest wavelength is represented by 3 grid points $\rightarrow 4N \simeq 3(TQ + 1)$

cubic grid: the shortest wavelength is represented by 4 grid points $\rightarrow 4N \simeq 4(TC + 1)$

The quadratic grid is used by ECHAM and ERA15. ERA40 is using a linear Gaussian grid reflected by the TL notation.

The following table shows the calculation of the number of latitudes and the triangular truncation for the different grid types:

Gridtype	Number of latitudes: nlat	Triangular truncation: ntr
linear	$NINT((ntr*2 + 1)/2)$	$(nlat*2 - 1) / 2$
quadratic	$NINT((ntr*3 + 1)/2)$	$(nlat*2 - 1) / 3$
cubic	$NINT((ntr*4 + 1)/2)$	$(nlat*2 - 1) / 4$

Operators

dv2uv Divergence and vorticity to U and V wind
Calculate U and V wind on a Gaussian grid from spherical harmonic coefficients of relative divergence and vorticity. The divergence and vorticity need to have the names sd and svo or code numbers 155 and 138.

uv2dv U and V wind to divergence and vorticity
Calculate spherical harmonic coefficients of relative divergence and vorticity from U and V wind. The U and V wind need to be on a Gaussian grid and need to have the names u and v or the code numbers 131 and 132.

Parameter

gridtype STRING Type of the grid: quadratic, linear (default: quadratic)

Example

Assume a dataset has at least spherical harmonic coefficients of divergence and vorticity. To transform the spectral divergence and vorticity to U and V wind on a Gaussian grid use:

```
cdo dv2uv infile outfile
```

2.13.5. FOURIER - Fourier transformation

Synopsis

```
fourier,epsilon infile outfile
```

Description

The fourier operator performs the fourier transformation or the inverse fourier transformation of all input fields. If the number of timesteps is a power of 2 then the algorithm of the Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT) is used.

It is

$$o(t, x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} i(t, x) e^{\epsilon 2\pi i j}$$

where a user given *epsilon* = -1 leads to the forward transformation and a user given *epsilon* = 1 leads to the backward transformation.

If the input stream *infile* consists only of complex fields, then the fields of *outfile*, computed by

```
cdo -f ext fourier,1 -fourier,-1 infile outfile
```

are the same than that of *infile*. For real input files see function *retocomplex*.

Parameter

epsilon INTEGER -1: forward transformation; 1: backward transformation

Note

Currently only the EXTRA format supports fields with complex numbers.

2.14. Import/Export

This section contains modules to import and export data files which can not read or write directly with CDO.

Here is a short overview of all operators in this section:

import_binary	Import binary data sets
import_cmsaf	Import CM-SAF HDF5 files
import_amr	Import AMSR binary files
input	ASCII input
inputsrv	SERVICE ASCII input
inputtext	EXTRA ASCII input
output	ASCII output
outputf	Formatted output
outputint	Integer output
outputsrv	SERVICE ASCII output
outputtext	EXTRA ASCII output
outputtab	Table output
gmtxyz	GMT xyz format
gmtcells	GMT multiple segment format

2.14.1. IMPORTBINARY - Import binary data sets

Synopsis

```
import_binary infile outfile
```

Description

This operator imports gridded binary data sets via a GrADS data descriptor file. The GrADS data descriptor file contains a complete description of the binary data as well as instructions on where to find the data and how to read it. The descriptor file is an ASCII file that can be created easily with a text editor. The general contents of a gridded data descriptor file are as follows:

- Filename for the binary data
- Missing or undefined data value
- Mapping between grid coordinates and world coordinates
- Description of variables in the binary data set

A detailed description of the components of a GrADS data descriptor file can be found in [GrADS]. Here is a list of the supported components: BYTESWAPPED, CHSUB, DSET, ENDVARS, FILE-HEADER, HEADERBYTES, OPTIONS, TDEF, TITLE, TRAILERBYTES, UNDEF, VARS, XDEF, XYHEADER, YDEF, ZDEF

Note

Only 32-bit IEEE floats are supported for standard binary files!

Example

To convert a binary data file to NetCDF use:

```
cdo -f nc import_binary infile.ctl outfile.nc
```

Here is an example of a GrADS data descriptor file:

```
DSET ^infile.bin
OPTIONS sequential
UNDEF -9e+33
XDEF 360 LINEAR -179.5 1
YDEF 180 LINEAR -89.5 1
ZDEF 1 LINEAR 1 1
TDEF 1 LINEAR 00:00Z15jun1989 12hr
VARS 1
  param 1 99 description of the variable
ENDVARS
```

The binary data file infile.bin contains one parameter on a global 1 degree lon/lat grid written with FORTRAN record length headers (sequential).

2.14.2. IMPORTCMSAF - Import CM-SAF HDF5 files

Synopsis

```
import_cmsaf infile outfile
```

Description

This operator imports gridded CM-SAF (Satellite Application Facility on Climate Monitoring) HDF5 files. CM-SAF exploits data from polar-orbiting and geostationary satellites in order to provide climate monitoring products of the following parameters:

Cloud parameters: cloud fraction (CFC), cloud type (CTY), cloud phase (CPH), cloud top height, pressure and temperature (CTH,CTP,CTT), cloud optical thickness (COT), cloud water path (CWP).

Surface radiation components: Surface albedo (SAL); surface incoming (SIS) and net (SNS) shortwave radiation; surface downward (SDL) and outgoing (SOL) longwave radiation, surface net longwave radiation (SNL) and surface radiation budget (SRB).

Top-of-atmosphere radiation components: Incoming (TIS) and reflected (TRS) solar radiative flux at top-of-atmosphere. Emitted thermal radiative flux at top-of-atmosphere (TET).

Water vapour: Vertically integrated water vapour (HTW), layered vertically integrated water vapour and layer mean temperature and relative humidity for 5 layers (HLW), temperature and mixing ratio at 6 pressure levels.

Daily and monthly mean products can be ordered via the CM-SAF web page (www.cmsaf.eu). Products with higher spatial and temporal resolution, i.e. instantaneous swath-based products, are available on request (contact.cmsaf@dwd.de). All products are distributed free-of-charge. More information on the data is available on the CM-SAF homepage (www.cmsaf.eu).

Daily and monthly mean products are provided in equal-area projections. **CDO** reads the projection parameters from the metadata in the HDF5-headers in order to allow spatial operations like remapping. For spatial operations with instantaneous products on original satellite projection, additional files with arrays of latitudes and longitudes are needed. These can be obtained from CM-SAF together with the data.

Note

To use this operator, it is necessary to build **CDO** with HDF5 support (version 1.6 or higher). The PROJ library (version 5.0 or higher) is needed for full support of the remapping functionality.

Example

A typical sequence of commands with this operator could look like this:

```
cdo -f nc remapbil,r360x180 -import_cmsaf cmsaf_product.hdf output.nc
```

(bilinear remapping to a predefined global grid with 1 deg resolution and conversion to NetCDF).

If you work with CM-SAF data on original satellite project, an additional file with information on geolocation is required, to perform such spatial operations:

```
cdo -f nc remapbil,r720x360 -setgrid,cmsaf_latlon.h5 -import_cmsaf cmsaf.hdf out.nc
```

Some CM-SAF data are stored as scaled integer values. For some operations, it could be desirable (or necessary) to increase the accuracy of the converted products:

```
cdo -b f32 -f nc fldmean -sellonlatbox,0,10,0,10 -remapbil,r720x360 \  
-import_cmsaf cmsaf_product.hdf output.nc
```

2.14.3. IMPORTAMSR - Import AMSR binary files

Synopsis

```
import_amsr infile outfile
```

Description

This operator imports gridded binary AMSR (Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer) data. The binary data files are available from the AMSR ftp site (<ftp://ftp.ssmi.com/amsre>). Each file consists of twelve (daily) or five (averaged) 0.25 x 0.25 degree grid (1440,720) byte maps. For daily files, six daytime maps in the following order, Time (UTC), Sea Surface Temperature (SST), 10 meter Surface Wind Speed (WSPD), Atmospheric Water Vapor (VAPOR), Cloud Liquid Water (CLOUD), and Rain Rate (RAIN), are followed by six nighttime maps in the same order. Time-Averaged files contain just the geophysical layers in the same order [SST, WSPD, VAPOR, CLOUD, RAIN]. More information to the data is available on the AMSR homepage <http://www.remss.com/amsr>.

Example

To convert monthly binary AMSR files to NetCDF use:

```
cdo -f nc amsre_yyyymm5 amsre_yyyymm5.nc
```

2.14.4. INPUT - Formatted input

Synopsis

```
input,grid[,zaxis] outfile
inputsrv outfile
inputtext outfile
```

Description

This module reads time series of one 2D variable from standard input. All input fields need to have the same horizontal grid. The format of the input depends on the chosen operator.

Operators

input	ASCII input Reads fields with ASCII numbers from standard input and stores them in <code>outfile</code> . The numbers read are exactly that ones which are written out by the output operator.
inputsrv	SERVICE ASCII input Reads fields with ASCII numbers from standard input and stores them in <code>outfile</code> . Each field should have a header of 8 integers (SERVICE likely). The numbers that are read are exactly that ones which are written out by the outputsrv operator.
inputtext	EXTRA ASCII input Read fields with ASCII numbers from standard input and stores them in <code>outfile</code> . Each field should have header of 4 integers (EXTRA likely). The numbers read are exactly that ones which are written out by the outputtext operator.

Parameter

<i>grid</i>	STRING	Grid description file or name
<i>zaxis</i>	STRING	Z-axis description file

Example

Assume an ASCII dataset contains a field on a global regular grid with 32 longitudes and 16 latitudes (512 elements). To create a GRIB1 dataset from the ASCII dataset use:

```
cdo -f grb input,r32x16 outfile.grb < my_ascii_data
```

2.14.5. OUTPUT - Formatted output

Synopsis

```

output infiles
outputf,format[,nelem] infiles
outputint infiles
outputsrv infiles
outputtext infiles

```

Description

This module prints all values of all input datasets to standard output. All input fields need to have the same horizontal grid. All input files need to have the same structure with the same variables. The format of the output depends on the chosen operator.

Operators

output	ASCII output Prints all values to standard output. Each row has 6 elements with the C-style format "%13.6g".
outputf	Formatted output Prints all values to standard output. The format and number of elements for each row have to be specified by the parameters <i>format</i> and <i>nelem</i> . The default for <i>nelem</i> is 1.
outputint	Integer output Prints all values rounded to the nearest integer to standard output.
outputsrv	SERVICE ASCII output Prints all values to standard output. Each field with a header of 8 integers (SERVICE likely).
outputtext	EXTRA ASCII output Prints all values to standard output. Each field with a header of 4 integers (EXTRA likely).

Parameter

<i>format</i>	STRING	C-style format for one element (e.g. %13.6g)
<i>nelem</i>	INTEGER	Number of elements for each row (default: <i>nelem</i> = 1)

Example

To print all field elements of a dataset formatted with "%8.4g" and 8 values per line use:

```
cdo outputf,%8.4g,8 infile
```

Example result of a dataset with one field on 64 grid points:

261.7	262	257.8	252.5	248.8	247.7	246.3	246.1
250.6	252.6	253.9	254.8	252	246.6	249.7	257.9
273.4	266.2	259.8	261.6	257.2	253.4	251	263.7
267.5	267.4	272.2	266.7	259.6	255.2	272.9	277.1
275.3	275.5	276.4	278.4	282	269.6	278.7	279.5
282.3	284.5	280.3	280.3	280	281.5	284.7	283.6
292.9	290.5	293.9	292.6	292.7	292.8	294.1	293.6
293.8	292.6	291.2	292.6	293.2	292.8	291	291.2

2.14.6. OUTPUTTAB - Table output

Synopsis

```
outputtab, params infile outfile
```

Description

This operator prints a table of all input datasets to standard output. `infile` is an arbitrary number of input files. All input files need to have the same structure with the same variables on different timesteps. All input fields need to have the same horizontal grid.

The contents of the table depends on the chosen paramters. The format of each table parameter is `keyname[:len]`. `len` is the optional length of a table entry. Here is a list of all valid keynames:

Keyname	Type	Description
value	FLOAT	Value of the variable [len:8]
name	STRING	Name of the variable [len:8]
param	STRING	Parameter ID (GRIB1: code[.tabnum]; GRIB2: num[.cat[.dis]]) [len:11]
code	INTEGER	Code number [len:4]
x	FLOAT	X coordinate of the original grid [len:6]
y	FLOAT	Y coordinate of the original grid [len:6]
lon	FLOAT	Longitude coordinate in degrees [len:6]
lat	FLOAT	Latitude coordinate in degrees [len:6]
lev	FLOAT	Vertical level [len:6]
xind	INTEGER	Grid x index [len:4]
yind	INTEGER	Grid y index [len:4]
timestep	INTEGER	Timestep number [len:6]
date	STRING	Date (format YYYY-MM-DD) [len:10]
time	STRING	Time (format hh:mm:ss) [len:8]
year	INTEGER	Year [len:5]
month	INTEGER	Month [len:2]
day	INTEGER	Day [len:2]
nohead	INTEGER	Disable output of header line

Parameter

`params` STRING Comma-separated list of keynames, one for each column of the table

Example

To print a table with name, date, lon, lat and value information use:

```
cdo outputtab,name,date,lon,lat,value infile
```

Here is an example output of a time series with the yearly mean temperatur at lon=10/lat=53.5:

#	name	date	lon	lat	value
	tsurf	1991-12-31	10	53.5	8.83903
	tsurf	1992-12-31	10	53.5	8.17439
	tsurf	1993-12-31	10	53.5	7.90489
	tsurf	1994-12-31	10	53.5	10.0216
	tsurf	1995-12-31	10	53.5	9.07798

2.14.7. OUTPUTGMT - GMT output

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile
```

Description

This module prints the first field of the input dataset to standard output. The output can be used to generate 2D Lon/Lat plots with [GMT]. The format of the output depends on the chosen operator.

Operators

- gmtxyz** GMT xyz format
The operator exports the first field to the GMT xyz ASCII format. The output can be used to create contour plots with the GMT module pscontour.
- gmtcells** GMT multiple segment format
The operator exports the first field to the GMT multiple segment ASCII format. The output can be used to create shaded gridfill plots with the GMT module psxy.

Example

- 1) GMT shaded contour plot of a global temperature field with a resolution of 4 degree. The contour interval is 3 with a rainbow color table.

```
cdo gmtxyz temp > data.gmt
makecpt -T213/318/3 -Crainbow > gmt.cpt
pscontour -K -JQ0/10i -Rd -I -Cgmt.cpt data.gmt > gmtplot.ps
pscoast -O -J -R -Dc -W -B40g20 >> gmtplot.ps
```


- 2) GMT shaded gridfill plot of a global temperature field with a resolution of 4 degree. The contour interval is 3 with a rainbow color table.

```
cdo gmtcells temp > data.gmt
makecpt -T213/318/3 -Crainbow > gmt.cpt
psxy -K -JQ0/10i -Rd -L -Cgmt.cpt -m data.gmt > gmtplot.ps
pscoast -O -J -R -Dc -W -B40g20 >> gmtplot.ps
```


2.15. Miscellaneous

This section contains miscellaneous modules which do not fit to the other sections before.

Here is a short overview of all operators in this section:

gradsdes	GrADS data descriptor file
after	ECHAM standard post processor
bandpass	Bandpass filtering
lowpass	Lowpass filtering
highpass	Highpass filtering
gridarea	Grid cell area
gridweights	Grid cell weights
smooth	Smooth grid points
smooth9	9 point smoothing
setvals	Set list of old values to new values
setrtoc	Set range to constant
setrtoc2	Set range to constant others to constant2
const	Create a constant field
random	Create a field with random numbers
topo	Create a field with topography
seq	Create a time series
stdatm	Create values for pressure and temperature for hydrostatic atmosphere
timsort	Sort over the time
uvDestag	Destaggering of u/v wind components
rotuvNorth	Rotate u/v wind to North pole.
projuvLatLon	Cylindrical Equidistant projection
rotuvb	Backward rotation
mrotuvb	Backward rotation of MPIOM data
mastrfu	Mass stream function
sealevelpressure	Sea level pressure
gheight	Geopotential height
adisit	Potential temperature to in-situ temperature
adipot	In-situ temperature to potential temperature
rhopot	Calculates potential density
histcount	Histogram count
histsum	Histogram sum
histmean	Histogram mean
histfreq	Histogram frequency
sethalo	Set the left and right bounds of a field

wct	Windchill temperature
fdns	Frost days where no snow index per time period
strwin	Strong wind days index per time period
strbre	Strong breeze days index per time period
strgal	Strong gale days index per time period
hurr	Hurricane days index per time period
cmorlite	CMOR lite
verifygrid	Verify grid coordinates

2.15.1. GRADSDES - GrADS data descriptor file

Synopsis

```
gradsdes[,mapversion] infile
```

Description

Creates a [GrADS] data descriptor file. Supported file formats are GRIB1, NetCDF, SERVICE, EXTRA and IEG. For GRIB1 files the GrADS map file is also generated. For SERVICE and EXTRA files the grid have to be specified with the **CDO** option '-g <grid>'. This module takes *infile* in order to create filenames for the descriptor (*infile.ct1*) and the map (*infile.gmp*) file.

Parameter

mapversion INTEGER Format version of the GrADS map file for GRIB1 datasets. Use 1 for a machine specific version 1 GrADS map file, 2 for a machine independent version 2 GrADS map file and 4 to support GRIB files >2GB. A version 2 map file can be used only with GrADS version 1.8 or newer. A version 4 map file can be used only with GrADS version 2.0 or newer. The default is 4 for files >2GB, otherwise 2.

Example

To create a GrADS data descriptor file from a GRIB1 dataset use:

```
cdo gradsdes infile.grb
```

This will create a descriptor file with the name *infile.ct1* and the map file *infile.gmp*.

Assumed the input GRIB1 dataset has 3 variables over 12 timesteps on a Gaussian N16 grid. The contents of the resulting GrADS data description file is approximately:

```
DSET ^infile.grb
DTYPE GRIB
INDEX ^infile.gmp
XDEF 64 LINEAR 0.000000 5.625000
YDEF 32 LEVELS -85.761 -80.269 -74.745 -69.213 -63.679 -58.143
          -52.607 -47.070 -41.532 -35.995 -30.458 -24.920
          -19.382 -13.844 -8.307 -2.769 2.769 8.307
          13.844 19.382 24.920 30.458 35.995 41.532
          47.070 52.607 58.143 63.679 69.213 74.745
          80.269 85.761
ZDEF 4 LEVELS 925 850 500 200
TDEF 12 LINEAR 12:00 Z1jan1987 1mo
TITLE infile.grb T21 grid
OPTIONS yrev
UNDEF -9e+33
VARS 3
geosp 0 129,1,0 surface geopotential (orography) [m^2/s^2]
t      4 130,99,0 temperature [K]
tslm1 0 139,1,0 surface temperature of land [K]
ENDVARS
```

2.15.2. AFTERBURNER - ECHAM standard post processor

Synopsis

```
after[,vct] infile outfile
```

Description

The "afterburner" is the standard post processor for [ECHAM] GRIB and NetCDF data which provides the following operations:

- Extract specified variables and levels
- Compute derived variables
- Transform spectral data to Gaussian grid representation
- Vertical interpolation to pressure levels
- Compute temporal means

This operator reads selection parameters as namelist from stdin. Use the UNIX redirection "<namelistfile" to read the namelist from file.

The input files can't be combined with other **CDO** operators because of an optimized reader for this operator.

Namelist

Namelist parameter and there defaults:

```
TYPE=0, CODE=-1, LEVEL=-1, INTERVAL=0, MEAN=0, EXTRAPOLATE=1
```

TYPE controls the transformation and vertical interpolation. Transforming spectral data to Gaussian grid representation and vertical interpolation to pressure levels are performed in a chain of steps. The **TYPE** parameter may be used to stop the chain at a certain step. Valid values are:

```
TYPE = 0 : Hybrid level spectral coefficients
TYPE = 10 : Hybrid level fourier coefficients
TYPE = 11 : Hybrid level zonal mean sections
TYPE = 20 : Hybrid level gauss grids
TYPE = 30 : Pressure level gauss grids
TYPE = 40 : Pressure level fourier coefficients
TYPE = 41 : Pressure level zonal mean sections
TYPE = 50 : Pressure level spectral coefficients
TYPE = 60 : Pressure level fourier coefficients
TYPE = 61 : Pressure level zonal mean sections
TYPE = 70 : Pressure level gauss grids
```

Vorticity, divergence, streamfunction and velocity potential need special treatment in the vertical transformation. They are not available as types 30, 40 and 41. If you select one of these combinations, type is automatically switched to the equivalent types 70, 60 and 61. The type of all other variables will be switched too, because the type is a global parameter.

CODE selects the variables by the ECHAM GRIB1 code number (1-255). The default value **-1** processes all detected codes. Derived variables computed by the afterburner:

Code	Name	Longname	Units	Level	Needed Codes
34	low_cld	low cloud		single	223 on modellevel
35	mid_cld	mid cloud		single	223 on modellevel
36	hih_cld	high cloud		single	223 on modellevel
131	u	u-velocity	m/s	atm (ml+pl)	138, 155
132	v	v-velocity	m/s	atm (ml+pl)	138, 155
135	omega	vertical velocity	Pa/s	atm (ml+pl)	138, 152, 155
148	stream	streamfunction	m ² /s	atm (ml+pl)	131, 132
149	velopot	velocity potential	m ² /s	atm (ml+pl)	131, 132
151	slp	mean sea level pressure	Pa	surface	129, 130, 152
156	geopoth	geopotential height	m	atm (ml+pl)	129, 130, 133, 152
157	rhumidity	relative humidity		atm (ml+pl)	130, 133, 152
189	scfs	surface solar cloud forcing		surface	176-185
190	tcfs	surface thermal cloud forcing		surface	177-186
191	scf0	top solar cloud forcing		surface	178-187
192	tcf0	top thermal cloud forcing		surface	179-188
259	windspeed	windspeed	m/s	atm (ml+pl)	sqrt(u*u+v*v)
260	precip	total precipitation		surface	142+143

LEVEL selects the hybrid or pressure levels. The allowed values depends on the parameter **TYPE**. The default value **-1** processes all detected levels.

INTERVAL selects the processing interval. The default value **0** process data on monthly intervals. **INTERVAL=1** sets the interval to daily.

MEAN=1 compute and write monthly or daily mean fields. The default value **0** writes out all timesteps.

EXTRAPOLATE=0 switch of the extrapolation of missing values during the interpolation from model to pressure level (only available with **MEAN=0** and **TYPE=30**). The default value **1** extrapolate missing values.

Possible combinations of **TYPE**, **CODE** and **MEAN**:

TYPE	CODE	MEAN
0/10/11	130 temperature	0
0/10/11	131 u-velocity	0
0/10/11	132 v-velocity	0
0/10/11	133 specific humidity	0
0/10/11	138 vorticity	0
0/10/11	148 streamfunction	0
0/10/11	149 velocity potential	0
0/10/11	152 LnPs	0
0/10/11	155 divergence	0
>11	all codes	0/1

Parameter

vct STRING File with VCT in ASCII format

Example

To interpolate ECHAM hybrid model level data to pressure levels of 925, 850, 500 and 200 hPa, use:

```
cdo after infile outfile << EON
  TYPE=30 LEVEL=92500,85000,50000,20000
EON
```

2.15.3. FILTER - Time series filtering

Synopsis

```
bandpass,fmin,fmax infile outfile
lowpass,fmax infile outfile
highpass,fmin infile outfile
```

Description

This module takes the time series for each gridpoint in `infile` and (fast fourier) transforms it into the frequency domain. According to the particular operator and its parameters certain frequencies are filtered (set to zero) in the frequency domain and the spectrum is (inverse fast fourier) transformed back into the time domain. To determine the frequency the time-axis of `infile` is used. (Data should have a constant time increment since this assumption applies for transformation. However, the time increment has to be different from zero.) All frequencies given as parameter are interpreted per year. This is done by the assumption of a 365-day calendar. Consequently if you want to perform multiyear-filtering accurately you have to delete the 29th of February. If your `infile` has a 360 year calendar the frequency parameters *fmin* respectively *fmax* should be multiplied with a factor of 360/365 in order to obtain accurate results. For the set up of a frequency filter the frequency parameters have to be adjusted to a frequency in the data. Here *fmin* is rounded down and *fmax* is always rounded up. Consequently it is possible to use `bandpass` with *fmin=fmax* without getting a zero-field for `outfile`. Hints for efficient usage:

- to get reliable results the time-series has to be detrended (`cdo detrend`)
- the lowest frequency greater zero that can be contained in `infile` is $1/(N*dT)$,
- the greatest frequency is $1/(2dT)$ (Nyquist frequency),

with N the number of timesteps and dT the time increment of `infile` in years.

Missing value support for operators in this module is not implemented, yet!

Operators

bandpass	Bandpass filtering Bandpass filtering (pass for frequencies between <i>fmin</i> and <i>fmax</i>). Suppresses all variability outside the frequency range specified by [<i>fmin</i> , <i>fmax</i>].
lowpass	Lowpass filtering Lowpass filtering (pass for frequencies lower than <i>fmax</i>). Suppresses all variability with frequencies greater than <i>fmax</i> .
highpass	Highpass filtering Highpass filtering (pass for frequencies greater than <i>fmin</i>). Suppresses all variability with frequencies lower than <i>fmin</i> .

Parameter

<i>fmin</i>	FLOAT	Minimum frequency per year that passes the filter.
<i>fmax</i>	FLOAT	Maximum frequency per year that passes the filter.

Note

For better performance of these operators use the **CDO** configure option `--with-fftw3`.

Example

Now assume your data are still hourly for a time period of 5 years but with a 365/366-day- calendar and you want to suppress the variability on timescales greater or equal to one year (we suggest here to use a number x bigger than one (e.g. $x=1.5$) since there will be dominant frequencies around the peak (if there is one) as well due to the issue that the time series is not of infinite length). Therefore you can use the following:

```
cdo highpass,x -del29feb infile outfile
```

Accordingly you might use the following to suppress variability on timescales shorter than one year:

```
cdo lowpass,1 -del29feb infile outfile
```

Finally you might be interested in 2-year variability. If you want to suppress the seasonal cycle as well as say the longer cycles in climate system you might use

```
cdo bandpass,x,y -del29feb infile outfile
```

with $x \leq 0.5$ and $y \geq 0.5$.

2.15.4. GRIDCELL - Grid cell quantities

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile outfile
```

Description

This module reads the grid cell area of the first grid from the input stream. If the grid cell area is missing it will be computed from the grid coordinates. The area of a grid cell is calculated using spherical triangles from the coordinates of the center and the vertices. The base is a unit sphere which is scaled with the radius of the earth. The default earth radius is 6371000 meter. This value can be changed with the environment variable `PLANET_RADIUS`. Depending on the chosen operator the grid cell area or weights are written to the output stream.

Operators

gridarea	Grid cell area Writes the grid cell area to the output stream. If the grid cell area have to be computed it is scaled with the earth radius to square meters.
gridweights	Grid cell weights Writes the grid cell area weights to the output stream.

Environment

<code>PLANET_RADIUS</code>	This variable is used to scale the computed grid cell areas to square meters. By default <code>PLANET_RADIUS</code> is set to an earth radius of 6371000 meter.
----------------------------	---

2.15.5. SMOOTH - Smooth grid points

Synopsis

```
smooth[,options] infile outfile
smooth9 infile outfile
```

Description

Smooth all grid points of a horizontal grid. Options is a comma-separated list of "key=value" pairs with optional parameters.

Operators

- smooth** Smooth grid points
Performs a N point smoothing on all input fields. The number of points used depend on the search radius (radius) and the maximum number of points (maxpoints). Per default all points within the search radius of 1degree are used. The weights for the points depend on the form of the curve and the distance. The implemented form of the curve is linear with constant default weights of 0.25 at distance 0 (weight0) and at the search radius (weightR).
- smooth9** 9 point smoothing
Performs a 9 point smoothing on all fields with a quadrilateral curvilinear grid. The result at each grid point is a weighted average of the grid point plus the 8 surrounding points. The center point receives a weight of 1.0, the points at each side and above and below receive a weight of 0.5, and corner points receive a weight of 0.3. All 9 points are multiplied by their weights and summed, then divided by the total weight to obtain the smoothed value. Any missing data points are not included in the sum; points beyond the grid boundary are considered to be missing. Thus the final result may be the result of an averaging with less than 9 points.

Parameter

<i>nsmooth</i>	INTEGER	Number of times to smooth, default nsmooth=1
<i>radius</i>	STRING	Search radius, default radius=1deg (units: deg, rad, km, m)
<i>maxpoints</i>	INTEGER	Maximum number of points, default maxpoints=<gridsize>
<i>form</i>	STRING	Form of the curve, default form=linear
<i>weight0</i>	FLOAT	Weight at distance 0, default weight0=0.25
<i>weightR</i>	FLOAT	Weight at the search radius, default weightR=0.25

2.15.6. DELTAT - Difference between timesteps

Synopsis

```
deltat infile outfile
```

Description

This operator computes the difference between each timestep.

2.15.7. REPLACEVALUES - Replace variable values

Synopsis

```
setvals,oldval,newval[...] infile outfile
setrtoc,rmin,rmax,c infile outfile
setrtoc2,rmin,rmax,c,c2 infile outfile
```

Description

This module replaces old variable values with new values, depending on the operator.

Operators

setvals Set list of old values to new values
Supply a list of n pairs of old and new values.

setrtoc Set range to constant

$$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} c & \text{if } i(t, x) \geq rmin \wedge i(t, x) \leq rmax \\ i(t, x) & \text{if } i(t, x) < rmin \vee i(t, x) > rmax \end{cases}$$

setrtoc2 Set range to constant others to constant2

$$o(t, x) = \begin{cases} c & \text{if } i(t, x) \geq rmin \wedge i(t, x) \leq rmax \\ c2 & \text{if } i(t, x) < rmin \vee i(t, x) > rmax \end{cases}$$

Parameter

<i>oldval,newval,...</i>	FLOAT	Pairs of old and new values
<i>rmin</i>	FLOAT	Lower bound
<i>rmax</i>	FLOAT	Upper bound
<i>c</i>	FLOAT	New value - inside range
<i>c2</i>	FLOAT	New value - outside range

2.15.8. VARGEN - Generate a field

Synopsis

const,*const,grid* outfile
random,*grid[,seed]* outfile
topo[*,grid*] outfile
seq,*start,end[,inc]* outfile
stdatm,*levels* outfile

Description

Generates a dataset with one or more fields

Operators

const Create a constant field
 Creates a constant field. All field elements of the grid have the same value.

random Create a field with random numbers
 Creates a field with rectangularly distributed random numbers in the interval [0,1].

topo Create a field with topography
 Creates a field with topography data, per default on a global half degree grid.

seq Create a time series
 Creates a time series with field size 1 and field elements beginning with a start value in time step 1 which is increased from one time step to the next.

stdatm Create values for pressure and temperature for hydrostatic atmosphere
 Creates pressure and temperature values for the given list of vertical levels. The formulas are:

$$P(z) = P_0 \exp \left(-\frac{g}{R} \frac{H}{T_0} \log \left(\frac{\exp(\frac{z}{H}) T_0 + \Delta T}{T_0 + \Delta T} \right) \right)$$

$$T(z) = T_0 + \Delta T \exp \left(-\frac{z}{H} \right)$$

with the following constants

$T_0 = 213\text{K}$: offset to get a surface temperature of 288K
 $\Delta T = 75\text{K}$: Temperature lapse rate for 10Km
 $P_0 = 1013.25\text{hPa}$: surface pressure
 $H = 10000.0\text{m}$: scale height
 $g = 9.80665 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}^2}$: earth gravity
 $R = 287.05 \frac{\text{J}}{\text{kgK}}$: gas constant for air

This is the solution for the hydrostatic equations and is only valid for the troposphere (constant positive lapse rate). The temperature increase in the stratosphere and other effects of the upper atmosphere are not taken into account.

Parameter

<i>const</i>	FLOAT	Constant
<i>seed</i>	INTEGER	The seed for a new sequence of pseudo-random numbers [default: 1]
<i>grid</i>	STRING	Target grid description file or name
<i>start</i>	FLOAT	Start value of the loop
<i>end</i>	FLOAT	End value of the loop
<i>inc</i>	FLOAT	Increment of the loop [default: 1]
<i>levels</i>	FLOAT	Target levels in metre above surface

Example

To create a standard atmosphere dataset on a given horizontal grid:

```
cdo enlarge,gridfile -stdatm,10000,8000,5000,3000,2000,1000,500,200,0 outfile
```

2.15.9. TIMSORT - Timsort**Synopsis**

```
timsort infile outfile
```

Description

Sorts the elements in ascending order over all timesteps for every field position. After sorting it is:

$$o(t_1, x) \leq o(t_2, x) \quad \forall (t_1 < t_2), x$$

Example

To sort all field elements of a dataset over all timesteps use:

```
cdo timsort infile outfile
```

2.15.10. WINDTRANS - Wind Transformation

Synopsis

```
uvDestag,u,v[, -/+0.5[, -/+0.5]] infile outfile
rotuvNorth,u,v infile outfile
projuvLatLon,u,v infile outfile
```

Description

This module contains special operators for datasets with wind components on a rotated lon/lat grid, e.g. data from the regional model HIRLAM or REMO.

Operators

uvDestag	Destaggering of u/v wind components This is a special operator for destaggering of wind components. If the file contains a grid with temperature (name='t' or code=11) then grid_temp will be used for destaggered wind.
rotuvNorth	Rotate u/v wind to North pole. This is an operator for transformation of wind-vectors from grid-relative to north-pole relative for the whole file. (FAST implementation with JACOBIANS)
projuvLatLon	Cylindrical Equidistant projection Thus is an operator for transformation of wind-vectors from the globe-spherical coordinate system into a flat Cylindrical Equidistant (lat-lon) projection. (FAST JACOBIAN implementation)

Parameter

<i>u,v</i>	STRING	Pair of u,v wind components (use variable names or code numbers)
<i>-/+0.5,-/+0.5</i>	STRING	Destaggered grid offsets are optional (default -0.5,-0.5)

Example

Typical operator sequence on HIRLAM NWP model output (LAMH_D11 files):

```
cdo uvDestag,33,34 inputfile inputfile_destag
cdo rotuvNorth,33,34 inputfile_destag inputfile_rotuvN
```

2.15.11. ROTUVB - Rotation

Synopsis

```
rotuvb,u,v,... infile outfile
```

Description

This is a special operator for datasets with wind components on a rotated grid, e.g. data from the regional model REMO. It performs a backward transformation of velocity components U and V from a rotated spherical system to a geographical system.

Parameter

`u,v,...` **STRING** Pairs of zonal and meridional velocity components (use variable names or code numbers)

Note

This is a specific implementation for data from the REMO model, it may not work with data from other sources.

Example

To transform the u and v velocity of a dataset from a rotated spherical system to a geographical system use:

```
cdo rotuvb,u,v infile outfile
```

2.15.12. MROTUVB - Backward rotation of MPIOM data

Synopsis

```
mrotuvb infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

MPIOM data are on a rotated Arakawa C grid. The velocity components U and V are located on the edges of the cells and point in the direction of the grid lines and rows. With mrotuvb the velocity vector is rotated in latitudinal and longitudinal direction. Before the rotation, U and V are interpolated to the scalar points (cell center). U is located with the coordinates for U in infile1 and V in infile2. mrotuvb assumes a positive meridional flow for a flow from grid point(i,j) to grid point(i,j+1) and positive zonal flow for a flow from grid point(i+1,j) to point(i,j).

Note

This is a specific implementation for data from the MPIOM model, it may not work with data from other sources.

2.15.13. MASTRFU - Mass stream function

Synopsis

```
mastrfu infile outfile
```

Description

This is a special operator for the post processing of the atmospheric general circulation model [ECHAM]. It computes the mass stream function (code=272). The input dataset have to be a zonal mean of v-velocity [m/s] (code=132) on pressure levels.

Example

To compute the mass stream function from a zonal mean v-velocity dataset use:

```
cdo mastrfu infile outfile
```

2.15.14. DERIVEPAR - Derived model parameters

Synopsis

```
<operator> infile outfile
```

Description

This module contains operators that calculate derived model parameters. These are currently the parameters sea level pressure and geopotential height. All necessary input parameters are identified by their GRIB1 code number or the NetCDF CF standard name. Supported GRIB1 parameter tables are: WMO standard table number 2 and ECMWF local table number 128.

CF standard name	Units	GRIB 1 code
surface_air_pressure	Pa	134
air_temperature	K	130
specific_humidity	kg/kg	133
surface_geopotential	m ² s ⁻²	129
geopotential_height	m	156

Operators

- sealevelpressure** Sea level pressure
This operator computes the sea level pressure (air_pressure_at_sea_level). Required input fields are surface_air_pressure, surface_geopotential and air_temperature on hybrid sigma pressure levels.
- gheight** Geopotential height
This operator computes the geopotential height (geopotential_height) on model levels in metres. Required input fields are surface_air_pressure, surface_geopotential, specific_humidity and air_temperature on hybrid sigma pressure levels. Note, this procedure is an approximation, which doesn't take into account the effects of e.g. cloud ice and water, rain and snow.

2.15.15. ADISIT - Potential temperature to in-situ temperature and vice versa

Synopsis

```
<operator>[,pressure] infile outfile
```

Description

Operators

- adisit** Potential temperature to in-situ temperature
This is a special operator for the post processing of the ocean and sea ice model [MPIOM]. It converts potential temperature adiabatically to in-situ temperature to(t, s, p). Required input fields are sea water potential temperature (name=tho; code=2) and sea water salinity (name=sao; code=5). Pressure is calculated from the level information or can be specified by the optional parameter. Output fields are sea water temperature (name=to; code=20) and sea water salinity (name=s; code=5).
- adipot** In-situ temperature to potential temperature
This is a special operator for the post processing of the ocean and sea ice model [MPIOM]. It converts in-situ temperature to potential temperature tho(to, s, p). Required input fields are sea water in-situ temperature (name=t; code=2) and sea water salinity (name=sao;s; code=5). Pressure is calculated from the level information or can be specified by the optional parameter. Output fields are sea water temperature (name=tho; code=2) and sea water salinity (name=s; code=5).

Parameter

pressure FLOAT Pressure in bar (constant value assigned to all levels)

2.15.16. RHOPOT - Calculates potential density

Synopsis

```
rhopot[,pressure] infile outfile
```

Description

This is a special operator for the post processing of the ocean and sea ice model [MPIOM]. It calculates the sea water potential density (name=rhopot; code=18). Required input fields are sea water in-situ temperature (name=to; code=20) and sea water salinity (name=sao; code=5). Pressure is calculated from the level information or can be specified by the optional parameter.

Parameter

pressure FLOAT Pressure in bar (constant value assigned to all levels)

Example

To compute the sea water potential density from the potential temperature use this operator in combination with [adisit](#):

```
cdo rhopot -adisit infile outfile
```

2.15.17. HISTOGRAM - Histogram

Synopsis

```
<operator>,<bounds> infile outfile
```

Description

This module creates bins for a histogram of the input data. The bins have to be adjacent and have non-overlapping intervals. The user has to define the bounds of the bins. The first value is the lower bound and the second value the upper bound of the first bin. The bounds of the second bin are defined by the second and third value, aso. Only 2-dimensional input fields are allowed. The output file contains one vertical level for each of the bins requested.

Operators

histcount	Histogram count Number of elements in the bin range.
histsum	Histogram sum Sum of elements in the bin range.
histmean	Histogram mean Mean of elements in the bin range.
histfreq	Histogram frequency Relative frequency of elements in the bin range.

Parameter

bounds FLOAT Comma-separated list of the bin bounds (-inf and inf valid)

2.15.18. SETHALO - Set the left and right bounds of a field

Synopsis

```
sethalo,<lhalo>,<rhalo> infile outfile
```

Description

This operator sets the left and right bounds of the rectangularly understood fields. Positive numbers of the parameter *lhalo* enlarges the left bound by the given number of columns from the right bound. The parameter *rhalo* does the similar for the right bound. Negative numbers of the parameter *lhalo/rhalo* can be used to remove the given number of columns of the left and right bounds.

Parameter

<i>lhalo</i>	INTEGER	Left halo
<i>rhalo</i>	INTEGER	Right halo

2.15.19. WCT - Windchill temperature

Synopsis

```
wct infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

Let `infile1` and `infile2` be time series of temperature and wind speed records, then a corresponding time series of resulting windchill temperatures is written to `outfile`. The wind chill temperature calculation is only valid for a temperature of $T \leq 33$ °C and a wind speed of $v \geq 1.39$ m/s. Whenever these conditions are not satisfied, a missing value is written to `outfile`. Note that temperature and wind speed records have to be given in units of °C and m/s, respectively.

2.15.20. FDNS - Frost days where no snow index per time period

Synopsis

```
fdns infile1 infile2 outfile
```

Description

Let `infile1` be a time series of the daily minimum temperature `TN` and `infile2` be a corresponding series of daily surface snow amounts. Then the number of days where $TN < 0$ °C and the surface snow amount is less than 1 cm is counted. The temperature `TN` have to be given in units of Kelvin. The date information of a timestep in `outfile` is the date of the last contributing timestep in `infile`.

2.15.21. STRWIN - Strong wind days index per time period

Synopsis

```
strwin[,v] infile outfile
```

Description

Let `infile` be a time series of the daily maximum horizontal wind speed `VX`, then the number of days where $VX > v$ is counted. The horizontal wind speed `v` is an optional parameter with default $v = 10.5$ m/s. A further output variable is the maximum number of consecutive days with maximum wind speed greater than or equal to `v`. Note that both `VX` and `v` have to be given in units of m/s. Also note that the horizontal wind speed is defined as the square root of the sum of squares of the zonal and meridional wind speeds. The date information of a timestep in `outfile` is the date of the last contributing timestep in `infile`.

Parameter

<code>v</code>	FLOAT	Horizontal wind speed threshold (m/s, default $v = 10.5$ m/s)
----------------	-------	---

2.15.22. STRBRE - Strong breeze days index per time period

Synopsis

```
strbre infile outfile
```

Description

Let `infile` be a time series of the daily maximum horizontal wind speed VX , then the number of days where VX is greater than or equal to 10.5 m/s is counted. A further output variable is the maximum number of consecutive days with maximum wind speed greater than or equal to 10.5 m/s. Note that VX is defined as the square root of the sum of squares of the zonal and meridional wind speeds and have to be given in units of m/s. The date information of a timestep in `outfile` is the date of the last contributing timestep in `infile`.

2.15.23. STRGAL - Strong gale days index per time period

Synopsis

```
strgal infile outfile
```

Description

Let `infile` be a time series of the daily maximum horizontal wind speed VX , then the number of days where VX is greater than or equal to 20.5 m/s is counted. A further output variable is the maximum number of consecutive days with maximum wind speed greater than or equal to 20.5 m/s. Note that VX is defined as the square root of the sum of square of the zonal and meridional wind speeds and have to be given in units of m/s. The date information of a timestep in `outfile` is the date of the last contributing timestep in `infile`.

2.15.24. HURR - Hurricane days index per time period

Synopsis

```
hurrr infile outfile
```

Description

Let `infile` be a time series of the daily maximum horizontal wind speed VX , then the number of days where VX is greater than or equal to 32.5 m/s is counted. A further output variable is the maximum number of consecutive days with maximum wind speed greater than or equal to 32.5 m/s. Note that VX is defined as the square root of the sum of squares of the zonal and meridional wind speeds and have to be given in units of m/s. The date information of a timestep in `outfile` is the date of the last contributing timestep in `infile`.

2.15.25. CMORLITE - CMOR lite

Synopsis

```
cmorlite,table[,convert] infile outfile
```

Description

The [CMOR] (Climate Model Output Rewriter) library comprises a set of functions, that can be used to produce CF-compliant NetCDF files that fulfill the requirements of many of the climate community's standard model experiments. These experiments are collectively referred to as MIP's. Much of the metadata written to the output files is defined in MIP-specific tables, typically made available from each MIP's web site.

The **CDO** operator cmorlite process the header and variable section of such MIP tables and writes the result with the internal IO library [CDI]. In addition to the CMOR 2 and 3 table format, the **CDO** parameter table format is also supported. The following parameter table entries are available:

Entry	Type	Description
name	WORD	Name of the variable
out_name	WORD	New name of the variable
type	WORD	Data type (real or double)
standard_name	WORD	As defined in the CF standard name table
long_name	STRING	Describing the variable
units	STRING	Specifying the units for the variable
comment	STRING	Information concerning the variable
cell_methods	STRING	Information concerning calculation of means or climatologies
cell_measures	STRING	Indicates the names of the variables containing cell areas and volumes
missing_value	FLOAT	Specifying how missing data will be identified
valid_min	FLOAT	Minimum valid value
valid_max	FLOAT	Maximum valid value
ok_min_mean_abs	FLOAT	Minimum absolute mean
ok_max_mean_abs	FLOAT	Maximum absolute mean
factor	FLOAT	Scale factor
delete	INTEGER	Set to 1 to delete variable
convert	INTEGER	Set to 1 to convert the unit if necessary

Most of the above entries are stored as variables attributes, some of them are handled differently. The variable **name** is used as a search key for the parameter table. **valid_min**, **valid_max**, **ok_min_mean_abs** and **ok_max_mean_abs** are used to check the range of the data.

Parameter

```
table    STRING    Name of the CMOR table as specified from PCMDI
convert  STRING    Converts the units if necessary
```

Example

Here is an example of a parameter table for one variable:

```
prompt> cat mypartab
&parameter
  name          = t
```

```
out_name      = ta
standard_name = air_temperature
units         = "K"
missing_value = 1.0e+20
valid_min     = 157.1
valid_max     = 336.3
/
```

To apply this parameter table to a dataset use:

```
cdo -f nc cmorlite,mypartab,convert infile outfile
```

This command renames the variable **t** to **ta**. The standard name of this variable is set to **air_temperature** and the unit is set to **[K]** (converts the unit if necessary). The missing value will be set to **1.0e+20**. In addition it will be checked whether the values of the variable are in the range of **157.1** to **336.3**. The result will be stored in NetCDF.

2.15.26. VERIFYGRID - Verify grid coordinates

Synopsis

```
verifygrid infile
```

Description

This operator verifies the coordinates of all horizontal grids found in *infile*. Among other things, it searches for duplicate cells, non-convex cells, and whether the center is located outside the cell bounds. Use the **CDO** option **-v** to output the position of these cells. This information can be useful to avoid problems when interpolating the data.

3. Contributors

3.1. History

CDO was originally developed by Uwe Schulzweida at the Max Planck Institute for Meteorology (MPI-M). The first public release is available since 2003. The MPI-M, together with the DKRZ, has a long history in the development of tools for processing climate data. **CDO** was inspired by some of these tools, such as the PINGO package and the GRIB-Modules.

PINGO¹ was developed by Jürgen Waszkewitz, Peter Lenzen, and Nathan Gillet in 1995 at the DKRZ, Hamburg (Germany). **CDO** has a similar user interface and uses some of the PINGO routines.

The GRIB-Modules was developed by Heiko Borgert and Wolfgang Welke in 1991 at the MPI-M. **CDO** is using a similar module structure and also some of the routines.

3.2. External sources

CDO has incorporated code from several sources:

afterburner is a postprocessing application for ECHAM data and ECMWF analysis data, originally developed by Edilbert Kirk, Michael Ponater and Arno Hellbach. The afterburner code was modified for the **CDO** operators [after](#), [ml2pl](#), [ml2hl](#), [sp2gp](#), [gp2sp](#).

SCRIP is a software package used to generate interpolation weights for remapping fields from one grid to another in spherical geometry [[SCRIP](#)]. It was developed at the Los Alamos National Laboratory by Philip W. Jones. The SCRIP library was converted from Fortran to ANSI C and is used as the base for the remapping operators in **CDO**.

YAC (Yet Another Coupler) was jointly developed by DKRZ and MPI-M by Moritz Hanke and Rene Redler [[YAC](#)]. **CDO** is using the clipping and cell search routines for the conservative remapping with [remapcon](#).

libkdtree a C99 implementation of the kd-tree algorithm developed by Jörg Dietrich.

CDO uses tools from the GNU project, including automake, and libtool.

3.3. Contributors

The primary contributors to the **CDO** development have been:

Uwe Schulweida : Concept, design and implementation of **CDO**, project coordination, and releases.

Luis Kornblueh : He supports **CDO** from the beginning. His main contributions are GRIB performance and compression, GME and unstructured grid support. Luis also helps with design and planning.

Ralf Müller : He is working on **CDO** since 2009. His main contributions are the implementation of the User Portal, the ruby and python interface for all **CDO** operators, the building process and the Windows support. The **CDO** User Portal was funded by the European Commission infrastructure project IS-ENES. Ralf also helps a lot with the user support. Implemented operators: [intlevel3d](#), [consecsum](#), [consects](#), [ngrid](#), [ngridpoints](#), [reducegrid](#)

¹Procedural INterface for GRIB formatted Objects

Cedrick Anso : He worked on the software package **CDO** as a student assistant at MPI-M from 2007-2011. Implemented operators: [eof](#), [eof3d](#), [enscrps](#), [ensbrs](#), [maskregion](#), [bandpass](#), [lowpass](#), [highpass](#), [smooth9](#)

Oliver Heidmann : He worked on the software package **CDO** as a student assistant at MPI-M from 2015-2018.

Karin Meier-Fleischer : She is working in the **CDO** user support since 2017.

Fabian Wachsmann : He is working on **CDO** for the CMIP6 project since 2016. His main task is the implementation and support of the cmor operator. He has also implemented the ETCCDI Indices of Daily Temperature and Precipitation Extremes.

Ralf Quast : He worked on **CDO** on behalf of the Service Gruppe Anpassung (SGA), DKRZ in 2006. He implemented all ECA Indices of Daily Temperature and Precipitation Extremes, all percentile operators, module [YDRUNSTAT](#) and [wct](#).

Kameswarrao Modali : He worked on CDO from 2012-2013.
Implemented operators: [contour](#), [shaded](#), [grfill](#), [vector](#), [graph](#).

Michal Koutek : Implemented operators: [selmulti delmulti](#), [changemulti](#), [samplegrid](#), [uvDestag](#), [rotuvNorth](#), [projuvLatLon](#).

Etienne Tourigny : Implemented operators: [setclonlatbox](#), [setcindexbox](#), [setvals](#), [splitsel](#), [histfreq](#), [setrtoc](#), [setrtoc2](#).

Karl-Hermann Wieners : Implemented operators: [aexpr](#), [aexprf](#), [selzaxisname](#).

Asela Rajapakse He worked on CDO from 2016-2017 as part of the EUDAT project.
Implemented operator: [verifygrid](#)

Many users have contributed to **CDO** by sending bug reports, patches and suggestions over time. Very helpful is also the active participation in the user forum of some users. Here is an incomplete list:

Jaison-Thomas Ambadan, Harald Anlauf, Andy Aschwanden, Stefan Bauer, Simon Blessing, Renate Brokopf, Michael Boettinger, Tim Brücher, Reinhard Budich, Martin Claus, Traute Crüger, Brendan de Tracey, Irene Fischer-Bruns, Chris Fletscher, Helmut Frank, Kristina Fröhlich, Oliver Fuhrer, Monika Esch, Pier Giuseppe Fogli, Beate Gayer, Veronika Gayler, Marco Giorgetta, David Gobbett, Holger Goettel, Helmut Haak, Stefan Hagemann, Angelika Heil, Barbara Hennemuth, Daniel Hernandez, Nathanael Huebbe, Thomas Jahns, Frank Kaspar, Daniel Klocke, Edi Kirk, Yvonne Küstermann, Stefanie Legutke, Leonidas Linardakis, Stephan Lorenz, Frank Lunkeit, Uwe Mikolajewicz, Laura Niederdrenk, Dirk Notz, Hans-Jürgen Panitz, Ronny Petrik, Swantje Preuschmann, Florian Prill, Asela Rajapakse, Daniel Reinert, Hannes Reuter, Mathis Rosenhauer, Reiner Schnur, Martin Schultz, Dennis Shea, Kevin Sieck, Martin Stendel, Bjorn Stevens, Martina Stockhaus, Claas Teichmann, Jörg Trentmann, Álvaro M. Valdebenito, Geert Jan van Oldenborgh, Jin-Song von Storch, David Wang, Joerg Wegner, Heiner Widmann, Claudia Wunram, Klaus Wyser

Please let me know if your name was omitted!

Bibliography

- [CDI]
[Climate Data Interface](#), from the [Max Planck Institute for Meteorologie](#)
- [CM-SAF]
[Satellite Application Facility on Climate Monitoring](#), from the [German Weather Service \(Deutscher Wetterdienst, DWD\)](#)
- [CMOR]
[Climate Model Output Rewriter](#), from the [Program For Climate Model Diagnosis and Intercomparison \(PCMDI\)](#)
- [ecCodes]
[API for GRIB decoding/encoding](#), from the [European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts \(ECMWF\)](#)
- [ECHAM]
[The atmospheric general circulation model ECHAM5](#), from the [Max Planck Institute for Meteorologie](#)
- [GMT]
[The Generic Mapping Tool](#), from the [School of Ocean and Earth Science and Technology \(SOEST\)](#)
- [GrADS]
[Grid Analysis and Display System](#), from the [Center for Ocean-Land-Atmosphere Studies \(COLA\)](#)
- [GRIB]
[GRIB version 1](#), from the [World Meteorological Organisation \(WMO\)](#)
- [HDF5]
[HDF version 5](#), from the [HDF Group](#)
- [INTERA]
[INTERA Software Package](#), from the [Max Planck Institute for Meteorologie](#)
- [Magics]
[Magics Software Package](#), from the [European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts \(ECMWF\)](#)
- [MPIOM]
[Ocean and sea ice model](#), from the [Max Planck Institute for Meteorologie](#)
- [NetCDF]
[NetCDF Software Package](#), from the [UNIDATA Program Center of the University Corporation for Atmospheric Research](#)
- [PINGO]
[The PINGO package](#), from the [Model & Data group](#) at the [Max Planck Institute for Meteorologie](#)
- [REMO]
[Regional Model](#), from the [Max Planck Institute for Meteorologie](#)
- [Preisendorfer]
Rudolph W. Preisendorfer: [Principal Component Analysis in Meteorology and Oceanography](#), Elsevier (1988)
- [PROJ]
[Cartographic Projections Library](#), originally written by Gerald Evenden then of the USGS.
- [SCRIP]
[SCRIP Software Package](#), from the [Los Alamos National Laboratory](#)

[szip]

[Szip compression software](#), developed at University of New Mexico.

[vonStorch]

Hans von Storch, Walter Zwiers: *Statistical Analysis in Climate Research*, Cambridge University Press (1999)

[YAC]

[YAC - Yet Another Coupler Software Package](#), from DKRZ and MPI for Meteorologie

A. Environment Variables

The following table describes the environment variables that affect **CDO**.

Variable name	Default	Description
CDO_DOWNLOAD_PATH	./	Path where CDO stores downloads.
CDO_FILE_SUFFIX	None	Default file suffix. This suffix will be added to the output file name instead of the filename extension derived from the file format. NULL will disable the adding of a file suffix.
CDO_GRIDSEARCH_RADIUS	180	Grid search radius in degree. Used by the operators <code>setmisstonn</code> , <code>remapdis</code> and <code>remapnn</code> .
CDO_HISTORY_INFO	1	Append NetCDF global attribute <code>history</code>
CDO_ICON_GRIDS		Root directory of the ICON grids (e.g. <code>/pool/data/ICON</code>).
CDO_PCTL_NBINS	101	Number of histogram bins.
CDO_RESET_HISTORY	0	Set to 1 to reset the NetCDF <code>history</code> global attribute.
CDO_REMAP_NORM	<code>fracarea</code>	Choose the normalization for the conservative interpolation
CDO_TIMESTAT_DATE	None	Set target timestamp of a temporal statistic operator to the "first", "middle", "midhigh" or "last" contributing source timestep.
CDO_USE_FFTW	1	Set to 0 to switch off usage of FFTW. Used in the Filter module.
CDO_VERSION_INFO	1	Set to 0 to disable NetCDF global attribute <code>CDO</code>

B. Parallelized operators

Some of the **CDO** operators are parallelized with OpenMP. To use **CDO** with multiple OpenMP threads, you have to set the number of threads with the option '-P'. Here is an example to distribute the bilinear interpolation on 8 OpenMP threads:

```
cdo -P 8 remapbil,targetgrid infile outfile
```

The following **CDO** operators are parallelized with OpenMP:

Module	Operator	Description
Afterburner	after	ECHAM standard post processor
Detrend	detrend	Detrend
Ensstat	ens<STAT>	Statistical values over an ensemble
EOF	eof	Empirical Orthogonal Functions
Filter	bandpass	Bandpass filtering
Filter	lowpass	Lowpass filtering
Filter	highpass	Highpass filtering
Fourier	fourier	Fourier transformation
Genweights	genbil	Generate bilinear interpolation weights
Genweights	genbic	Generate bicubic interpolation weights
Genweights	gendis	Generate distance-weighted average remap weights
Genweights	gennn	Generate nearest neighbor remap weights
Genweights	gencon	Generate 1st order conservative remap weights
Genweights	gencon2	Generate 2nd order conservative remap weights
Genweights	genlaf	Generate largest area fraction remap weights
Gridboxstat	gridbox<STAT>	Statistical values over grid boxes
Intlevel	intlevel	Linear level interpolation
Intlevel3d	intlevel3d	Linear level interpolation from/to 3D vertical coordinates
Remapeta	remapeta	Remap vertical hybrid level
Remap	remapbil	Bilinear interpolation
Remap	remapbic	Bicubic interpolation
Remap	remapdis	Distance-weighted average remapping
Remap	remapnn	Nearest neighbor remapping
Remap	remapcon	First order conservative remapping
Remap	remapcon2	Second order conservative remapping
Remap	remaplaf	Largest area fraction remapping
Smooth	smooth	Smooth grid points
Spectral	sp2gp, gp2sp	Spectral transformation
Vertintap	ap2pl, ap2hl	Vertical interpolation on hybrid sigma height coordinates
Vertintgh	gh2hl	Vertical height interpolation
Vertintml	ml2pl, ml2hl	Vertical interpolation on hybrid sigma pressure coordinates

C. Standard name table

The following CF standard names are supported by **CDO**.

CF standard name	Units	GRIB 1 code	variable name
surface_geopotential	m ² s ⁻²	129	geosp
air_temperature	K	130	ta
specific_humidity	1	133	hus
surface_air_pressure	Pa	134	aps
air_pressure_at_sea_level	Pa	151	psl
geopotential_height	m	156	zg

D. Grid description examples

D.1. Example of a curvilinear grid description

Here is an example for the **CDO** description of a curvilinear grid. `xvals/yvals` describe the positions of the 6x5 quadrilateral grid cells. The first 4 values of `xbounds/ybounds` are the corners of the first grid cell.

```

gridtype = curvilinear
gridsize = 30
xsize    = 6
ysize    = 5
xvals    = -21  -11   0   11   21   30  -25  -13   0   13
           25   36  -31  -16   0   16   31   43  -38  -21
           0   21   38   52  -51  -30   0   30   51   64
xbounds  = -23  -14  -17  -28           -14  -5  -6  -17           -5   5   6  -6
           5   14   17   6           14   23  28   17           23  32  38  28
           -28 -17 -21 -34           -17  -6  -7  -21           -6   6   7  -7
           6   17   21   7           17   28  34   21           28  38  44  34
           -34 -21 -27 -41           -21  -7  -9  -27           -7   7   9  -9
           7   21   27   9           21   34  41   27           34  44  52  41
           -41 -27 -35 -51           -27  -9 -13 -35           -9   9   13 -13
           9   27   35   13           27   41  51   35           41  52  63  51
           -51 -35 -51 -67           -35 -13 -21 -51           -13  13  21  -21
yvals    = 13   35   51   21           35   51  67   51           51  63  77  67
           29  26  39  42  42           29  26  39  42  42           29  26  39  42  42
           39  35  48  51  52           39  35  48  51  52           39  35  48  51  52
           62  61  57  51  65           62  61  57  51  65           62  61  57  51  65
ybounds  = 23  26  36  32           26  27  37  36           27  27  37  37
           27  26  36  37           26  23  32  36           23  19  28  32
           32  36  45  41           36  37  47  45           37  37  47  47
           37  36  45  47           36  32  41  45           32  28  36  41
           41  45  55  50           45  47  57  55           47  47  57  57
           47  45  55  57           45  41  50  55           41  36  44  50
           50  55  64  58           55  57  67  64           57  57  67  67
           57  55  64  67           55  50  58  64           50  44  51  58
           58  64  72  64           64  67  77  72           67  67  77  77
           67  64  72  77           64  58  64  72           58  51  56  64

```


Figure D.1.: Orthographic and Robinson projection of the curvilinear grid, the first grid cell is colored red

D.2. Example description for an unstructured grid

Here is an example of the **CDO** description for an unstructured grid. `xvals/yvals` describe the positions of 30 independent hexagonal grid cells. The first 6 values of `xbounds/ybounds` are the corners of the first grid cell. The grid cell corners have to rotate counterclockwise. The first grid cell is colored red.

```

gridtype = unstructured
gridsize = 30
nvertex  = 6
xvals    = -36  36  0 -18  18 108 72 54 90 180 144 126 162 -108 -144
           -162 -126 -72 -90 -54 0 72 36 144 108 -144 180 -72 -108 -36
xbounds  = 339  0  0 288 288 309 21 51 72 72 0 0
           0 16 21 0 339 344 340 0 -0 344 324 324
           20 36 36 16 0 0 93 123 144 144 72 72
           72 88 93 72 51 56 52 72 72 56 36 36
           92 108 108 88 72 72 165 195 216 216 144 144
           144 160 165 144 123 128 124 144 144 128 108 108
           164 180 180 160 144 144 237 267 288 288 216 216
           216 232 237 216 195 200 196 216 216 200 180 180
           236 252 252 232 216 216 288 304 309 288 267 272
           268 288 288 272 252 252 308 324 324 304 288 288
           345 324 324 36 36 15 36 36 108 108 87 57
           20 15 36 57 52 36 108 108 180 180 159 129
           92 87 108 129 124 108 180 180 252 252 231 201
           164 159 180 201 196 180 252 252 324 324 303 273
           236 231 252 273 268 252 308 303 324 345 340 324
yvals    = 58 58 32 0 0 58 32 0 0 58 32 0 0 58 32
           0 0 32 0 0 -58 -58 -32 -58 -32 -58 -32 -58 -32 -32
ybounds  = 41 53 71 71 53 41 41 41 53 71 71 53
           11 19 41 53 41 19 -19 -7 11 19 7 -11
           -19 -11 7 19 11 -7 41 41 53 71 71 53
           11 19 41 53 41 19 -19 -7 11 19 7 -11
           -19 -11 7 19 11 -7 41 41 53 71 71 53
           11 19 41 53 41 19 -19 -7 11 19 7 -11
           -19 -11 7 19 11 -7 11 19 41 53 41 19
           -19 -7 11 19 7 -11 -19 -11 7 19 11 -7
           -41 -53 -71 -71 -53 -41 -53 -71 -71 -53 -41 -41
           -19 -41 -53 -41 -19 -11 -53 -71 -71 -53 -41 -41
           -19 -41 -53 -41 -19 -11 -53 -71 -71 -53 -41 -41
           -19 -41 -53 -41 -19 -11 -53 -71 -71 -53 -41 -41
           -19 -41 -53 -41 -19 -11 -19 -41 -53 -41 -19 -11
    
```


Figure D.2.: Orthographic and Robinson projection of the unstructured grid

Operator index

A

abs	90
acos	90
add	93
addc	92
addtrend	162
adipot	214
adisit	214
aexpr	87
aexprf	87
after	203
ap2pl	181
apply	34
asin	90
atan	90
atan2	93

B

bandpass	205
bottomvalue	56

C

cat	35
changemulti	48
chcode	73
chlevel	73
chlevelc	73
chlevelv	73
chname	73
chparam	73
chunit	73
cmorlite	218
codetab	32
collgrid	44
consecsum	108
consects	108
const	209
copy	35
cos	90

D

dayavg	131
daymax	131
daymean	131
daymin	131
daypctl	132
dayrange	131
daystd	131
daystd1	131
daysum	131

dayvar	131
dayvar1	131
delcode	49
delete	46
delgridcell	55
delmulti	48
delname	49
delparam	49
deltat	207
detrend	160
dhouravg	142
dhourmax	142
dhourmean	142
dhourmin	142
dhourrange	142
dhourstd	142
dhourstd1	142
dhoursum	142
dhourvar	142
dhourvar1	142
diff	28
diffn	28
distgrid	43
div	93
divc	92
divcoslat	100
divdpm	100
divdpy	100
duplicate	37
dv2ps	188
dv2uv	189

E

enlarge	81
ensavg	110
ensbrs	113
enscrps	113
enskurt	110
ensmax	110
ensmean	110
ensmedian	110
ensmin	110
enspctl	110
ensrange	110
ensrkhistspace	112
ensrkhisttime	112
ensroc	112
ensskew	110
ensstd	110
ensstd1	110

enssum	110
ensvar	110
ensvar1	110
eof	164
eof3d	164
eofcoeff	166
eofspatial	164
eoftime	164
eq	62
eqc	63
exp	90
expr	87
exprf	87

F

fdns	216
fldavg	115
fldcor	157
fldcovar	158
fldint	115
fldkurt	115
fldmax	115
fldmean	115
fldmedian	115
fldmin	115
fldpctl	115
fldrange	115
fldskew	115
fldstd	115
fldstd1	115
fldsum	115
fldvar	115
fldvar1	115
fourier	190

G

ge	62
gec	63
genbic	169
genbil	168
gencon	172
gencon2	174
gendis	171
genlaf	176
genlevelbounds	75
gennn	170
gh2hl	182
gheight	213
gmtcells	198
gmtxyz	198
gp2sp	187
gradsdes	202
gridarea	206
gridboxavg	121
gridboxkurt	121
gridboxmax	121
gridboxmean	121
gridboxmedian	121

gridboxmin	121
gridboxrange	121
gridboxskew	121
gridboxstd	121
gridboxstd1	121
gridboxsum	121
gridboxvar	121
gridboxvar1	121
griddes	32
gridweights	206
gt	62
gtc	63

H

highpass	205
histcount	215
histfreq	215
histmean	215
histsum	215
houravg	129
hourmax	129
hourmean	129
hourmin	129
hourpctl	130
hourrange	129
hourstd	129
hourstd1	129
hoursum	129
hourvar	129
hourvar1	129
hurr	217

I

ifnotthen	58
ifnotthenc	59
ifthen	58
ifthenc	59
ifthenelse	58
import_amsr	194
import_binary	192
import_cmsaf	193
info	26
infon	26
input	195
inputtext	195
inputsrv	195
int	90
intlevel	183
intlevel3d	183
intlevelx3d	183
intntime	184
inttime	184
intyear	185
invertlat	76
invertlev	76
isosurface	56

L

le	62
lec	63
ln	90
log10	90
lowpass	205
lt	62
ltc	63

M

map	26
maskindexbox	79
masklonlatbox	79
maskregion	78
mastrfu	213
max	93
maxc	92
meravg	119
merge	38
mergegrid	37
mergetime	38
merkurt	119
mermax	119
mermean	119
mermedian	119
mermin	119
merpctl	119
merrange	119
merskew	119
merstd	119
merstd1	119
mersum	119
mervar	119
mervar1	119
min	93
minc	92
ml2hl	180
ml2pl	180
monadd	94
monavg	133
monddiv	94
monmax	133
monmean	133
monmin	133
monmul	94
monpctl	134
monrange	133
monstd	133
monstd1	133
monsub	94
monsum	133
monvar	133
monvar1	133
mrotuvb	212
mul	93
mulc	92
mulcoslat	100
muldpm	100
muldpy	100

N

ndate	29
ne	62
nec	63
ngridpoints	29
ngrids	29
nint	90
nlevel	29
nmon	29
not	90
npar	29
ntime	29
nyear	29

O

output	196
outputext	196
outputf	196
outputint	196
outputsrv	196
outputtab	197

P

pack	36
partab	32
pow	90
projuvLatLon	211

R

random	209
reci	90
reducegrid	60
regres	160
remap	177
remapbic	169
remapbil	168
remapcon	172
remapcon2	174
remapdis	171
remapeta	178
remaplaf	176
remapnn	170
replace	37
rhopot	214
rotuvb	212
rotuvNorth	211
runavg	125
runmax	125
runmean	125
runmin	125
runpctl	126
runrange	125
runstd	125
runstd1	125
runsum	125
runvar	125
runvar1	125

S

samplegrid	55	setmisstoc	82
sealevelpressure	213	setmisstodis	82
seasavg	138	setmisstonn	82
seasmax	138	setmissval	82
seasmean	138	setmon	71
seasmin	138	setname	70
seaspctl	139	setparam	70
seasrange	138	setpartabn	68
seasstd	138	setpartabp	68
seasstd1	138	setreftime	71
seassum	138	setrtoc	208
seasvar	138	setrtoc2	208
seasvar1	138	setrtomiss	82
selcircle	54	settaxis	71
selcode	49	settblimits	71
seldate	51	settime	71
selday	51	setunits	71
select	46	setunit	70
selgrid	49	setvals	208
selgridcell	55	setvrange	82
selhour	51	setyear	71
selindexbox	53	setzaxis	75
sellevel	49	shifttime	71
selleidx	49	shiftx	77
sellonlatbox	53	shifty	77
selltype	49	showattribute	31
selmonth	51	showcode	30
selmulti	48	showdate	30
selname	49	showformat	30
selparam	49	showlevel	30
selseason	51	showltype	30
selsmon	51	showmon	30
selstdname	49	showname	30
seltabnum	49	showstdname	30
seltime	51	showtime	30
seltimestep	51	showtimestamp	30
selyear	51	showyear	30
selyearidx	55	sin	90
selzaxis	49	sinfo	27
selzaxisname	49	sinfon	27
seq	209	smooth	207
setattribute	66	smooth9	207
setcalendar	71	sp2gp	187
setcindexbox	80	sp2sp	188
setclonlatbox	80	splitcode	39
setcode	70	splitday	41
setcodetab	70	splitgrid	39
setctomiss	82	splithour	41
setdate	71	splitlevel	39
setday	71	splitmon	41
setgrid	74	splitname	39
setgridarea	74	splitparam	39
setgridcell	84	splitseas	41
setgridmask	74	splitsel	42
setgridtype	74	splittabnum	39
sethalo	215	splityear	41
setlevel	70	splityearmon	41
setltype	70	splitzaxis	39

sqr	90
sqrt	90
stdatm	209
strbre	217
strgal	217
strwin	216
sub	93
subc	92
subtrend	162

T

tan	90
tee	36
timavg	127
timcor	157
timcovar	158
timcumsum	108
timmax	127
timmean	127
timmin	127
timpctl	128
timrange	127
timselavg	123
timselmax	123
timselmean	123
timselmin	123
timselctl	124
timselrange	123
timselstd	123
timselstd1	123
timselsum	123
timselvar	123
timselvar1	123
timsort	210
timstd	127
timstd1	127
timsun	127
timvar	127
timvar1	127
topo	209
topvalue	56
trend	161

U

uv2dv	189
uvDestag	211

V

varsavg	109
varsmax	109
varsmean	109
varsmin	109
varsrange	109
varsstd	109
varsstd1	109
varssum	109
varsvar	109
varsvar1	109

vct	32
verifygrid	219
vertavg	122
vertmax	122
vertmean	122
vertmin	122
verrange	122
vertstd	122
vertstd1	122
vertsum	122
vertvar	122
vertvar1	122

W

wct	216
-----	-----

Y

ydayadd	97
ydayavg	144
ydaydiv	97
ydaymax	144
ydaymean	144
ydaymin	144
ydaymul	97
ydaypctl	146
ydayrange	144
ydaystd	144
ydaystd1	144
ydaysub	97
ydaysum	144
ydayvar	144
ydayvar1	144
ydrunavg	153
ydrunmax	153
ydrunmean	153
ydrunmin	153
ydrunpctl	155
ydrunstd	153
ydrunstd1	153
ydrunsum	153
ydrunvar	153
ydrunvar1	153
yearadd	95
yearavg	136
yeardiv	95
yearmax	136
yearmaxidx	136
yearmean	136
yearmin	136
yearminidx	136
yearmonmean	135
yearmul	95
yearpctl	137
yearrange	136
yearstd	136
yearstd1	136
yearsub	95
yearsum	136

yearvar	136	zonstd	117
yearvar1	136	zonstd1	117
yhouradd	96	zonsum	117
yhouravg	140	zonvar	117
yhourdiv	96	zonvar1	117
yhourmax	140		
yhourmean	140		
yhourmin	140		
yhourmul	96		
yhourrange	140		
yhourstd	140		
yhourstd1	140		
yhoursub	96		
yhoursum	140		
yhourvar	140		
yhourvar1	140		
ymonadd	98		
ymonavg	147		
ymonddiv	98		
ymonmax	147		
ymonmean	147		
ymonmin	147		
ymonmul	98		
ymonpctl	149		
ymonrange	147		
ymonstd	147		
ymonstd1	147		
ymonsub	98		
ymonsum	147		
ymonvar	147		
ymonvar1	147		
yseasadd	99		
yseasavg	150		
yseasdiv	99		
yseasmax	150		
yseasmean	150		
yseasmin	150		
yseasmul	99		
yseaspctl	152		
yseasrange	150		
yseasstd	150		
yseasstd1	150		
yseassub	99		
yseassum	150		
yseasvar	150		
yseasvar1	150		

Z

zaxisdes	32
zonavg	117
zonkurt	117
zonmax	117
zonmean	117
zonmedian	117
zonmin	117
zonpctl	117
zonrange	117
zonskew	117